

Genotype-specific nutrient responses of wheat (*Triticum aestivum* L.), Maize (*Zea mays* L.) and sunflower (*Helianthus annuus* L.)

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Abstract. *The long-term experiments were carried out on chernozem soil in eastern part (Hajdúság) of Hungary. Our scientific data proved that the most important parameters for the characterization responses were the followings: natural nutrient utilization ability (yield in control), fertilizer utilization ability (yield surpluses of NPK fertilizers), maximum yield, fertilizer requirement ($N_{opt}+PK$). The genotypes of wheat, maize and sunflower could be classified into 4 groups: type A = modern genotype (high natural and fertilizer responses); type B = traditional intensive genotype (moderate natural nutrient utilization and excellent yield surplus of NPK fertilizer); type C = traditional extensive genotype (high control yield and low yield increase by NPK fertilizer); type D = old genotype (bad natural and fertilizer responses). By using of genotype fertilization crop model we can improve the efficiency of natural and fertilizer utilization in wheat, maize and sunflower production.*

Keywords: natural nutrient utilization, fertilizer response, genotype

1. Introduction

Winter wheat has a decisive role in Hungarian crop production. The sowing area of wheat varies between 1.0-1.2 million ha. The national average yield of wheat was 5.0-5.5 t ha⁻¹ in the 1980's but nowadays the average yield varies between 3.0-5.0 t ha⁻¹ depending on the climatic factors of the crop year [1].

According to Donohue and Brann [2], wheat varieties different in the utilization of the applied N fertilizer, which was indicated by the different N concentration of the plant tissues. Gricenko [3], Lahky [4], Tiscsenko and Blagovecsenszkaja [5], Moszkov [6], Ivanova and Matveeva [7] Morozov and Morozova [8], Klasen [9], Johnson and Raun [10] also pointed out the different fertilizer requirements of winter wheat varieties in their studies. In the experiments of Anderson [11], the N-response of wheat varieties was dependent upon the soil N content and the water supply.

Pepó [12, 1] differentiated four typical fertilizer response groups of winter wheat varieties in his experiments.

The different winter wheat genotypes utilized the applied fertilizers with different efficacy [13, 14, 15, 16]. Hungarian and foreign research results proved that the N requirements and fertilizer response of the different wheat genotypes greatly differ and the variety-specific fertilization based upon this knowledge is favourable from agronomical, economic and environmental aspects [17, 18, 19, 20, 21, 22].

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The most critical factors determining maize yield are the water and the nitrogen supply [23]. The crop year and different agrotechnical factors (fertilization, crop rotation, irrigation etc.) could modify the yields of different maize genotypes [24, 25, 26].

Maize requires a balanced NPK fertilization and nitrogen has a determining role from among the macroelements [27]. Uribelarrea et al. [28] found that the applied hybrid and the N supply have a great role in the N accumulation and in the efficacy of N uptake in maize. According to their results, the grain yield of maize increased gradually with increasing fertilizer doses up to the N_{160} fertilization level. On chernozem soils with medium-good NPK supply, the dosages above 120 kg ha^{-1} N active ingredient did not increase yields efficiently, furthermore, they even reduced it without irrigation [29,30]. According to Azeez [31], the dosage of 90 kg ha^{-1} N significantly increased the maize yield.

Sunflower is a crop which can utilize well the natural nutrient stock of the soil. The effects and efficacy of fertilization are greatly influenced by the agro-ecological (soil, weather) and agrotechnical conditions [32]. Domestic and foreign research results proved that, depending upon the conditions, the fertilization requirements of sunflower ranged within lower ($40\text{-}60 \text{ kg ha}^{-1}$ N+PK) [33, 34, 35] and higher ($75\text{-}120 \text{ kg ha}^{-1}$ +PK) intervals [36, 37]. In contrast to other crops (maize, wheat), there has been only limited research providing relevant data on the hybrid-specific fertilization of sunflower hybrids [38, 39, 40, 41].

2. Materials and methods

Long-term experiments were carried out in the experimental farm of the University of Debrecen Centre for Agricultural Sciences, Institute of Crop Sciences at Látókép. The site is located in Eastern-Hungary, 15 km from Debrecen in the Hajdúság loess region and its soil is calcareous chernozem soil (N $47^{\circ}33'$, E $21^{\circ}27'$). The experimental soil is of good culture-state, medium-hard loam. Its humus content is medium, 2.8 %, its pH value is almost neutral, $\text{pH}_{\text{KCl}}=6.4$. The soil has good water management characteristics. The long-term experiments were set up in 1983.

The structure of the other experiments was determined in accordance with the experimental objectives.

In the experiments, the same optimal agrotechniques were applied apart from the treatments, which provided an opportunity to compare the effect of the studied agrotechnical factors (fertilization, genotype) and the year.

3. Results

Winter wheat is a good nutrient indicator (mainly nitrogen) field crop which means that the higher or lower fertilizer doses comparing with optimum reduce the yield quantity and quality, too. The nutrient supply and fertilizer response of winter wheat varieties with different genotypes have been studied in a long-term experiment (established in 1983 year) on chernozem soil in Eastern part of Hungary (Hajdúság region).

Results of our long-term experiment carried out for 30 years proved that the fertilizer response of the different winter wheat varieties can be determined by the following parameters:

- Natural nutrient utilization ability
(indicated by the level of the variety's control yield)
- Fertilizer utilization ability
(yield surplus of fertilization)
- Realized maximum yield
(under specific ecological and agrotechnical conditions)
- Fertilizer requirement
(optimum N+PK dosage of the given variety)

Part of the varieties could utilize less the natural nutrient stock of chernozem soils (Mv Mazurka, GK Öthalom), while others utilized it very effectively (e.g. Mulan, Bitop, GK Csillag) (Figure 1). There were large differences also in the maximum yields of the varieties. In 2009, the difference between the highest (GK Csillag, 9117 kg ha⁻¹) and lowest yield (Lupus, 6800 kg ha⁻¹) was 2317 kg ha⁻¹. The fact that the optimum N+PK dosage of wheat varieties varied between 90-120-150 kg ha⁻¹ N+PK also draws the attention to the importance of variety-specific fertilization. This means that the species-specific N+PK optimum value should be determined specifically for each variety.

Fig. 1. The control and maximum yields of different winter wheat varieties (Debrecen, 2009)

Based on our long-term experiments of several decades, winter wheat varieties could be classified into four essentially different groups according to their fertilizer response (Figure 2). These 4 groups provide useful assistance in the variety-specific, environmentally-friendly fertilization of winter wheat.

Fig. 2. Fertilizer response of winter wheat varieties (Debrecen)

The types of winter wheat varieties according to their fertilizer response are as follows:

Type A: modern type (combines the advantages of the extensive and intensive types), it has an excellent utilization of both the natural soil nutrient stock and the fertilizers

- Type B: intensive type
it has traditionally weak natural nutrient utilizing ability, but high fertilizer response
- Type C: extensive type
it has traditionally excellent natural nutrient utilizing ability, but moderate fertilizer response
- Type D: unfavourable type
this type cannot utilize effectively either the soil nutrients or the fertilizers

Using different parameters we built up a variety-specific fertilization crop models. This crop model is shown graphically on the Figure 3. The studied 15 different wheat varieties can be classified into 4 groups by using the crop model.

This fertilization crop model gives excellent scientific support for the variety-specific fertilization of winter wheat, it can reduce the harmful environment effects of fertilization.

From among the field crops in Hungary, maize has the widest biological bases. There are great differences among the maize hybrids of different genetic background. The differences are manifested not only in the yield potential and yield stability of the hybrid (in its abiotic and biotic adaptation ability), but also in the responses of the hybrids to the different agrotechnical inputs. From among the agrotechnical responses, one of the most important ones is the fertilizer response of maize hybrids.

Fig. 3. Variety-specific classification of wheat genotypes nutrient utilization (Debrecen, 2013, chernozem soil)

In the vegetation period of 2013, the fertilizer response of maize hybrids with different genetic backgrounds was studied on chernozem soil in long-term experiments. The yields of the hybrids ranged from 9500 to 18600 kg ha⁻¹ depending upon the hybrid and the fertilizer treatment (Table 1). The yields of the hybrids varied between 9500 and 14600 kg ha⁻¹ in the control treatment. This means a difference of 5100 kg ha⁻¹ between the tested genotypes in 2013, which illustrates that there are huge differences between maize hybrids in their natural nutrient utilization ability. In 2013, the hybrids DKC 4025, DKC 4014, PR37M81 gave a relatively moderate yield in the control treatment (9500-10600 kg ha⁻¹). These hybrids had different FAO numbers, which indicates that the natural nutrient utilization ability of hybrids is primarily determined by the genotype. The hybrids PR37N01 and SY Afinity gave outstandingly high yields (14200-14500 kg ha⁻¹) in the control treatment in 2013, these hybrids also differed in their vegetation season-length.

In the season of 2013, the maximum yields of the hybrids varied within a very favourable range between 13500 and 18600 kg ha⁻¹ (Table 1). The maximum yield maximum of the hybrids DKC 4025, DKC 4014 and DKC 4490 was relatively lower than the average (between 13500 and 14800 kg ha⁻¹). Outstandingly high yields were obtained in the case of the hybrids SY Afinity, P9175, PR37N01, and P9494 (between 17100 and 18600 kg ha⁻¹).

Table 1) The effect of fertilization on the yield of maize hybrids (kg ha⁻¹) (Debrecen, chernozem soil, 2013)

Hybrids	Control	N ₃₀ +PK	N ₆₀ +PK	N ₉₀ +PK	N ₁₂₀ +PK	N ₁₅₀ +PK
P9578	11428	15710	15869	16105	16838	16475
DKC 4014	9774	11846	12349	12437	13622	13011
NK LUCIUS	11237	14392	15112	15017	16572	15553
P9175	11226	14880	15851	16311	16713	17736
DKC 4025	9530	11011	12982	12299	13514	12943
PR37M81	10630	14123	14611	14757	14838	16754
DKC 4490	11148	12741	13790	14364	14789	14414
PR37N01	14250	15641	15965	16519	17476	17127
P9494	11293	14388	15092	16263	17132	15206
SY AFINITY	14550	16570	16643	16736	18619	17718
LSD _{5%} (Hybrid)				1230		
LSD _{5%} (Nutrient level)				408		

When analyzing the efficacy of fertilization and nutrient supply as an average of the ten tested hybrids (Table 2), it was found that the absolute yield increase due to fertilization was the highest between the control and the N₃₀+PK treatment

(2623 kg ha⁻¹). In the fertilization treatments of higher dosage, the fertilization resulted in a more modest yield increment (696, 255 and 930 kg ha⁻¹ as an average of the hybrids), moreover, a small yield reduction (-317 kg ha⁻¹) was observed in the N₁₅₀+PK treatment. The relative yield increasement due to fertilization was also calculated as an average of the hybrids (Table 2), this index represents the maize yield increasement due to 1 kg NPK fertilizer. As regards the relative yield increment due to fertilization, the most favourable value (33.20 kg 1 kg NPK⁻¹) was also obtained between the control and the N₃₀+PK treatment, with increasing dosages, these valued were reduced (8.81, 3.23 and 11.77 kg 1 kg NPK⁻¹) and then became negative (-4.01 kg 1 kg NPK⁻¹).

Table 2) Study of nutrient efficiency of different maize genotypes (average of ten hybrids) (Debrecen, chernozem soil, 2013)

	Control	N ₃₀ +PK	N ₆₀ +PK	N ₉₀ +PK	N ₁₂₀ +PK	N ₁₅₀ +PK
Average yield (kg ha ⁻¹)	11507	14130	14826	15081	16011	15694
Absolute yield surplus of fertilization (kg ha ⁻¹)	-	2623	696	255	930	-317
Relative yield surplus of fertilization (kg 1 kg NPK ⁻¹)	-	33,20	8,81	3,23	11,77	-4,01
WUE (kg mm ⁻¹) (Rainfall March – Sept.)	30,25	37,26	39,10	39,77	42,22	41,39

For the complex evaluation of the fertilizer response of the tested maize hybrids such a graphic method was applied (Figure 4) which is suitable for the joint evaluation of

- the natural nutrient utilization ability (yield in the control treatment)
- and the maximum yield due to fertilization (yield in the N_{opt} +PK treatment).

Based on this, the tested maize hybrids could be classified into the following four fertilizer response groups:

A= hybrids which have a good natural nutrient utilization ability and give high maximum yields as a result of fertilization (SY Afinity, PR 37N01).

B= hybrids which have a moderate natural nutrient utilization ability and give high maximum yields as a result of fertilization (P 9175, P 9494, PR 37M81, P 9578, NK Lucius).

C= hybrids which have a good natural nutrient utilization ability and give moderate maximum yields as a result of fertilization (-).

D= hybrids which have a moderate natural nutrient utilization ability and give moderate yields as a result of fertilization (DKC 4014, DKC 4025, DKC 4490).

Fig. 4. Complex evaluation of the nutrient response of maize hybrids (Debrecen, 2013)

Our studies have also proved that the fertilizer response of sunflower hybrids can be significantly modified by the cropyear (Figure 5). In a dry year, the sunflower hybrids – due to the low infection level – showed a favourable fertilizer response (results of 2007 year). In years with an average water supply, the yield of the hybrids reduced (from a lower yield level) with increasing fertilization as a result of the increasing fungal infection due to fertilization (results of 2008 year).

Fig. 5. Fertilizer responses of sunflower genotypes (Debrecen, 2007-2008)

Fertilization had an effect not only on the amount of sunflower yield but also on its quality, that is on oil content (Figure 6). Results of 2009 year showed – as an average of the tested hybrids – that increasing fertilizer dosages reduced the oil content. Thus, the optimum NPK dose for maximum yield and maximum oil content differed.

Fig. 6. Effect of fertilization on the yield and oil content of sunflower (Debrecen, 2009) (average of the hybrids)

Conclusions

Results of our long term experiments on chernozem soil proved that the nutrient supply and fertilization had determining importance in winter wheat production even on chernozem soil with excellent water- and nutrient husbandry. According to our experimental results we built up a variety-specific fertilization crop model by using different parameters (natural nutrient utilization, yield surplus of fertilization, maximum yield, optimum N+PK dose, fertilization curve). The winter wheat varieties can be classified into 4 groups by using the fertilization crop model.

Maize is a crop with extremely high productivity. The year and the weather have a significant yield-determining effect in maize production. Very favourable yields were obtained also in the control, non fertilized treatment (9500-14600 kg ha⁻¹), which proved the excellent qualities and the good water and nutrient management of the chernozem soil. Fertilization had a yield-increasing effect even in spite of these high control yields. The maximum yield of the maize hybrids varied between 13500 and 18600 kg ha⁻¹. The yield-increasing effect of fertilization was 4798 kg ha⁻¹ as an average of the hybrids, ranging from 3226 to 6510 kg ha⁻¹ depending upon the genotype. Our experimental results proved that the water utilization of the maize hybrids can be improved with a proper nutrient supply and optimum fertilization. Based on their fertilizer response, maize hybrids could be classified into different groups. We proved that the significance of hybrid-specific fertilization and the different nutrient utilization of maize hybrids based on their experimental results. For this classification, the nutrient utilization of the hybrids (yield in the control treatment), and the maximum yield due to fertilization (yield

in the $N_{opt}+PK$ treatment) were used. Based on that, the tested hybrids can be classified into four different groups. As regards the nutrient utilization those hybrids are the most valuable, which can significantly increase their good control yield as a results of fertilization.

As compared with other field crops, sunflower has a different response to climate change. This is primarily due to its better adaptation ability and stress tolerance. However, even in the case of sunflower, the further development of the production technology elements and their site- and variety-specific adaptation are of exceptional importance. Among the technological elements, hybrid selection, fertilization had the special importance.

REFERENCES

- [1] Pepó, P: 2004 *Az évjárat hatása az őszi búza termésmennyiségére tartamkísérletben – Effect of year on the yield of winter wheat in long-term experiments.* Növénytermelés (Crop Production). 53. 4. 339-350.
- [2] Donohue, S.J.-Brann, D.E.: 1984. *Optimum N concentration in winter wheat grown in the Coastal Plain region of Virginia.* Communications in Soil Science and Plant Analysis. 15: 651-661.
- [3] Gricenko, A.A.: 1980. *Otzüvcsivosz szortov ozimój psenicü na udobrenija.* Trudü VIUA, Moszkva, 59. 62-64.
- [4] Lahky, J.: 1981. *Odrodové rozdeily vo vyzivovom stave ozimnych psenic.* Agrochémia, Bratislava, 21.3. 70-72.
- [5] Tiscsenko, A.T.-Blagovescsenszkaja, Z.K.: 1981. *Otzüvcsivoszt szortov ozimój psenicü na mineral nüe udobrenija.* SZEL Hoz. Rubezs. Moszkva. 12. 11-28.
- [6] Moszkov, G.: 1981. *Vlijanie na szorta I torento vörhu dobiva zimnata meka psenica.* Raszten, Nauki, Szofija, 18.4. 68-72.
- [7] Ivanova, M.L.-Matveeva, A.V.: 1983. *Szorta ozimój psenicü I effektivnoszt udobrenij.* Agrohimiija, Moszkva. 3. 120-136.
- [8] Morozov, N.A.-Morozová, Z.N.: 1983. *Reakcija szortov ozimój psenicü Szeverodonszkaja I Taraszovszkaja 29 na dozü I szroki azotnüü podkormok.* Szovers. tehnoł, vürasc. oz. psenicü I jar. jacsmenja. Perszianovka. 51-55.
- [9] Klasen, M.: 1984. *Sortenspezifische Getreideführung 1984.* L.Z. Rheinland, Bonn. 151. 4. 202-204.
- [10] Johnson, G.V.-Raun, W.R.: 2003. *Nitrogen response index as a guide to fertilizer management.* Journal of plant nutrition, 26. (2): 249-262.
- [11] Anderson, W.K.: 1985. *Differences in response of winter cereal varieties to applied nitrogen in the field. I. Some factors affecting the variability of responses between sites and seasons.* Field Crops Res., Amsterdam, 11. 4. 353-367.

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- [12] Pepó, P.: 1991. *Őszi búzafajták trágyázása és öntözése*. Kandidátusi értekezés. Debrecen.
- [13] Pesik, J.: 1982. *Sortenspezifische Anbautechnologie ein bedeutender Intensivierungsfaktor in der Weizenproduktion. Zehn Jahre Zusammenarbeit in Züchtung und Produktionsforschung bei Getreide zwischen der DDR und der CSSR*. Akad. Landw. DDR. 201.
- [14] Boreiko, V.S.-Morgun, V.V.-Chuchmii, I.P.: 1986. *Using the method of chemical mutagenesis to produce winter wheat varieties useful for commercial production. Geneticheskie metody uskoreniya selekcionnogo protsessa*. 92-96.
- [15] Istrati, E.-Doornescu, D.-Rusu, C.: 1997. *The evolution of some soil agrochemical indices and winter wheat yield as influenced by long-term fertilization*. Cercetari Agronomice in Moldova. 30: 1, 205-214.
- [16] Lloveras, J.-Lopez, A.-Ferran, J.-Espachs, S.-Solsona, J.: 2001. *Bread-making wheat and soil nitrate as affected by nitrogen fertilization in irrigated Mediterranean conditions*. Agronomy Journal. 93 (6): 1183-1190.
- [17] Pepó, P.: 1996. *Újabb adatok az őszi búza fajtaspecifikus tápanyagellátásához*. DATE Tudományos Közleményei. XXXII. 125-142.
- [18] Korobskoi, N.F.-Shirinyan, M.K.-Kravtsova, N.D.: 1997. *Responsiveness of winter wheat cultivars to mineral fertilizers*. Russian Agricultural Sciences 11: 19-21.
- [19] Podolska, G.: 1997. *Response of winter wheat cultivars and lines to certain agrotechnical factors. III. Effect of nitrogen fertilization on grain yield and yield components of new winter wheat cultivars and lines*. Biuletyn Instytutu Hodowli i Aklimatyzacji Roslin. 204: 169-172.
- [20] Filipov, K.H.-Dachev, Z.: 1999. *Varietal differentiation in wheat according to the effect of nitrogenous nutrition on grain yield*. Rasteniiev dni Nauki, 36, 1: 5-11.
- [21] Weber, R.-Hrynczuk, B.-Runowska-Hrynczuk, B.-Kita, W.: 1999. *Effect of tillage simplifications and differentiation of fertilization with nitrogen upon yield of selected spring wheat cultivars in periodical moisture deficiency*. Conference of soil tillage systems. Folia Universitas Agriculturae Stetinensis, 74: 157-162.
- [22] Pepó, P.: 1999. *Az ökológiai, biológiai és termesztéstechnológiai tényezők szerepe a minőségi őszi búza termesztés fejlesztésében. Talaj, növény és környezet kölcsönhatásai*. Szerk.: Nagy J., Debrecen, 160-179.
- [23] Moser, S.B.-Feil, B.-Jampatong, S.-Stamp, P.: 2006. *Effect of parenthesis drought, nitrogen fertilizer rate, and variety on grain yield, yield components, and harvest index of tropical maize*. Agricultural Water Management. 81. 1-2: 41-58.
- [24] Pepó, P.-Vad, A.-Berényi, S.: 2006. *Effect of some agrotechnical elements on the yield of maize on chernozem soil*. Cereal Research Communications. 34. 1. 621-624.
- [25] Berényi, S.-Vad, A.-Dóka, L.-Pepó, P.: 2007. *Effects of fertilization and crop years on maize (Zea mays L.) yields in different crop rotations*. Cereal Research Communications. 35. 2: 241-244.
- [26] Karancsi, L.G.-Pepó, P.: 2012. *Study of the effect of fertilization of maize (Zea mays L.) in crop years with different water-supply*. Növénytermelés. 61. Supplement 89-92.
- [27] Kovacevic, V.-Rastija, M.-Rastija, D.-Josipovic, M.: 2006. *Response of maize to fertilization with KCl on gleysol of Sava Valley Area*. Cereal Research Communications. 34. 2-3: 1129.
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- [28] Uribelarrea, M.-Crafts-Brandner, S.J.-Below, F.: 2007. *Physiological N response of field-grown maize hybrids (Zea mays L.) with divergent yield potential and grain protein concentration*. Plant Soil. 316: 151-160.
- [29] Zhou, J.B.-Wang, C.Y.-Zhang, H.-Gong, F.-Zheng, X.F.-Gate, W.-Li, S.X.: 2011. *Effect of water saving management practices and nitrogen fertilizer rate on crop yield and water use efficiency in a winter wheat-summer maize cropping system*. Field Crop Research. 122. 2: 157-163.
- [30] Sárvári, M.-Boros, B.: 2010. *A vetésváltás és az NPK tápanyagellátás hatása a kukorica termésére*. Növénytermelés, 59. 3: 37–52.
- [31] Azeez, J.O.: 2009. *Effect of nitrogen application and weed interference on performance of some tropical maize genotypes in Nigeria*. Pedosphere. 19. 5: 654-662.
- [32] Bíró, J.-Pepó, P.: 2008. *Néhány eltérő genotípusú napraforgó (Helianthus annuus L.) hibrid trágyareakciójának vizsgálata*. Növénytermelés. 57. 2, 149-157.
- [33] Stulin, A.F.: 1991. *Productivity of sunflowers under systematic application of fertilizers in a crop rotation on leached chernozem in the central chernozem zone*. Agrokhimiya. 10, 64-70.
- [34] Taha, M.-Acharya, N.-Mishra, B.K.: 1999. *Effect of irrigation and nitrogen on yield and quality of sunflower (Helianthus annuus L.)*. Journal of the Indian Society of Soil Science. 47. 4, 695-700.
- [35] Pepó, P.: 2001. *Napraforgó – eredményesen*. Magyar Mezőgazdaság. 56. 47, 12-13.
- [36] Malik, M.A.-Akram, M.-Tanyir, A.: 1992. *Effect of planting geometry and fertilizer on growth, yield and quality of a new sunflower cultivar 'SF-I 00'*. Journal of Agricultural Research Lahore. 30. 1, 59-63.
- [37] Reddy, M.P.-Shaik, M.M.S.: 2000. *Influence of nitrogen and phosphatic fertilizer on growth, yield components and yield of sunflower*. Crop Research Hisar. 20. 2, 293-296.
- [38] EI Nakhlawy, F.S.: 1993. *Defoliation effects on yield components and quality of sunflower*. Alexandria Journal of Agricultural Research. 38. 3, 257-267.
- [39] Vasudevan, S.N.-Virupakshappa, K.-Venugopal, N.-Bhaskar S.: 1997. *Response of sunflower (Helianthus annuus L.) to phosphorus, sulphur, micronutrients and humic acid under irrigated conditions on red sandy-loam soil*. Indian Journal of Agricultural Sciences. 67. 3, 110-112.
- [40] Pepó, P.-Borbélyné Hunyadi, É.-Zsombik, L.: 2002. *A napraforgó-termesztés agrotechnikai fejlesztési lehetőségei*. Agroforum, 13. 1. 19-22.
- [41] Pepó, P.-Bíró, J.: 2003. *A napraforgó,hibridspecifikus trágyázása*. Növénytermelés. 52. 1, 75-85.
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EVALUATION OF THE ROLE OF CRITICAL AGROTECHNICAL FACTORS IN SUNFLOWER CULTIVATION

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Abstract. *Today, cropyears with extreme weather conditions are becoming more and more frequent and increase the risk of sunflower production. The objective of researches into plant production is to minimize these effects as much as possible. In this sense, the optimization of agrotechnological factors is of high importance. Therefore, appropriate cropping technologies (crop density), nutrient supply and optimized, rational crop protection are highly important especially in highly sensitive sunflower cultures. The highest yield amount was measured in the treatment models treated two-times with fungicide and fertilized with NPK substances in case of all three hybrids. Regarding the average of the hybrids the highest yield without any fungicide treatment was measured in the treatment with harmonic nutrient supply with plant density of 55,000 plants ha⁻¹. When applying the plant density of 35,000 plants ha⁻¹ and 75,000 plants ha⁻¹ yield amounts were below 4,000 kg ha⁻¹ in case of all nutrient supply levels. Treatments with two-times fungicide treatment resulted maximal yield amounts in case of all three nutrient supply levels by the highest plant density, i.e. 75,000 plants ha⁻¹.*

Keywords: sunflower, plant density, nutrient supply, fungicide treatment, yield

1. Introduction

Due to the increase of the sowing area of sunflower production (600,000 ha in the country), sunflower got into the forefront of domestic field crop production. Despite the increase of the sowing area, the development of the technology was neglected. On more than half of the sowing area of sunflower, even nowadays, extensive or unreasonable agrotechnique is applied, despite the fact that 80% of the hybrids in cultivation needs intensive or at least average technology. The weather conditions of the recent years showed considerable differences, the extremes were frequent (unequal distribution of precipitation during the vegetation period, droughty periods, low temperature, etc.), that increased the risk of production to a considerable extent. The plant physiological, phenological, plant health, etc. studied will reveal the plant physiological relationships of the effects of agrotechnical methods.

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The cropyear and agrotechnical factors significantly influence the successfulness of sunflower production. We cannot influence the climatic factors, but the effects can be considerably reduced by the application of reasonable agrotechnique. The application of the sowing technological, nutrient supply and plant protection methods adequate for the hybrid, the production region and cropyear decrease the injuries caused by the diseases, increase yield amount and improves quality. The crucial element of sunflower production is the increased sensitivity of hybrids to fungal diseases. The appearance and injuries caused by the stalk and head diseases are lower during dry cropyears and more significant in moist ones. The prognosis of the climatic conditions of the vegetation period is currently not possible, but the significant reduction of the infections and injuries caused by the unfavourable weather can be possible by harmonic nutrient supply and plant protection operations applied by adequate timing.

According to Ragasits [1] sunflower was categorized as one with low demands and it was produced mainly on weak soil types. At first only some rows were sown on the edge of maize or potato fields. Later – according to the government regulations – fields that were unsuitable for any other field crop were utilized with it. After hybrids have become common and production was well equipped with machines this previous approach totally disappeared and sunflower has become one of the most important industrial crops lately.

The effect of crop year among agroecological factors is the opposite of other plant's demands. Apart from extreme occurrences, favourable yield and oil content can be expected in rather dry and warm crop years, which is corresponding to the excellent adapting ability of sunflower [2].

Due to the fact that production circumstances seem to be favourable sunflower production may be promising for many producers, however several expensive technological and unexpected plant protection aspects need to be considered during the vegetation. A crop year, in which every production factor is favourable, is rare, so sunflower production is always a risk [3].

Dry springs have become more frequent; however, the amount of precipitation during the vegetation period shows significant deviances in different crop years. Drought crop years have become two-times as frequent in contrast to the previous decades, but it is rather favourable for sunflower than unfavourable, because pathogens cause higher infection in wet crop years.

Biological factors in production technology cover the variety, in particular the hybrid. The very wide palette of currently available hybrids in Hungary is world-class both regarding yield amount and yield quality. The number of hybrids and varieties registered in the national plant variety catalogue is 87, which offer a wide range of choices. However, yield safety of hybrids is not that uniform, which

primarily refers to the resistance against abiotic (weather conditions and soil properties), biotic (pathogen organisms), just as against agrotechnical stress factors. Critical elements among agrotechnical factors shall be emphasized, that shall be ensured to an optimal input extent, while in case of other factors a minimal supply is essential which enables the effective, positive contribution of the critical elements. Critical production technology elements of sunflower production are the right choice of the hybrid, just as nutrient supply, sowing technology and plant protection. Genotype (hybrid) affects the effectiveness of sunflower production both directly and in an indirect way. Genetically determined productivity and oil content are determinant in a direct way, while resistance of hybrids against plant diseases, just as their adaptability (to both ecological and agrotechnical circumstances) and stem stability are determining from the aspect of yield [4].

Regarding nutrient supply harmonic NPK-supply needs to be implemented since it is of high importance in sunflower production. Nitrogen demand shall be supplied properly from the aspect of both yield amount and yield quality development, since the lack of nitrogen results in yield decrement, while overdosing it can lead to decreasing oil content. According to the previous studies nitrogen decreases the oil content, but it increases yield per hectare. Phosphorous promotes the accumulation of dry matter substance and increases oil content. Potassium enhances drought tolerance and pathogen resistance [5]. According to Geleta et al. [6] the realized sunflower grain yield amount depends on nitrogen- and phosphorous supply, temperature and water-supply, just as its distribution in the vegetation and the genetic potential of the applied hybrid.

Most of the about 70 pathogens that occur on sunflower are fungi. Fungal diseases reduce produced sunflower yields drastically each year, because the assimilation area of the infected plants decreases and thus less oil will be incorporated [7].

2. Material and methods

The small-plot field experiment was carried out in the year 2016 at the Látókép Research Site of the University of Debrecen CAS. The experimental soil is a lowland calcareous chernozem type with deep humus layer based on loess. This soil is in a good agricultural condition, medium set (plasticity value acc. to Arany: 43), regarding its soil physical conditions it can be classified as a loam soil type. Three hybrids were involved into the experiment: Sy Excellio, NK Alego, NK Neoma. The effect of unilateral N, just as PK supply and harmonic NPK nutrient supply were investigated by different plant densities of 35000, 55000 and 75000 plants per hectare (Table 1). The investigated acrotechnical factors have been evaluated in case of treatments without any fungicide plant protection (control

treatment), just as of treatments with two-times fungicide application (in the plant development state of 8-10 leaves and flowering).

Table 2) Fertilizer treatments applied in the experiment (Debrecen-Látókép, 2016)

1. treatment (N)	60 kg ha ⁻¹ N + 0 kg ha ⁻¹ P ₂ O ₅ +0 kg ha ⁻¹ K ₂ O
2. treatment (PK)	60 kg ha ⁻¹ N + 45 kg ha ⁻¹ P ₂ O ₅ +0 kg ha ⁻¹ K ₂ O
3. treatment (NPK)	60 kg ha ⁻¹ N + 45 kg ha ⁻¹ P ₂ O ₅ +75 kg ha ⁻¹ K ₂ O

Evaluation of the weather conditions of 2015-2016

Significantly higher amount of precipitation fell in October 2015 (86.6 mm) than the several years' average value (30.8 mm). November can be considered as rather average. But in December far lower amount of precipitation fell than the average value. Precipitation amount in January (58.6 mm) was also higher than the 30 years' average (37 mm) and February (78.8 mm) showed similar tendency as well (long-term average value: 30.2 mm). Overall, autumn and winter months were significantly wetter and warmer than the average. The amount of precipitation during the spring was also higher than the average. Thus later sunflower had favourable conditions for vegetative and generative development. All summer months were characterized by significantly higher amount of precipitation than the average value. Consequently weather circumstances were favourable for both sunflower development and the occurrence of fungal diseases of the population. Average temperature values proved to be higher than the several years' average values as well. (Figure 1).

Fig. 2. Precipitation end temperature in the examined year (Debrecen-Látókép, 2015-2016)

3. Results and discussions

Critical factors of sunflower production among agrotechnical production factors are balanced nutrient supply, sowing technology and the application of adequate fungicide plant protection measurements. Results of the present research work confirmed the yield amount determining effect of nutrient supply and fungicide treatment in case of all three studied sunflower hybrids. Regarding the average of the applied nutrient supply levels it can be stated that fungicide treatment of the studied hybrids resulted in significant yield amount increment in case of all three studied plant densities (Figure 2).

Fig. 3. Yield amount in different plant densities models and in fungicide treatment models regarding the average of hybrids and nutrient supplies (Debrecen-Látókép, 2016)

Hybrids produced the highest yield amounts in case of the application of harmonic nutrient supply. The highest yield amount was produced in treatment models of two-times fungicide application and NPK nutrient supply in case of all three studied hybrids. The highest yield was registered in case of the hybrid NK Neoma (4,428 kg ha⁻¹) regarding the average of the treatments (Figure 6). Regarding the average of the studied hybrids the highest yield amount (4,932 kg ha⁻¹) was produced in plots treated with two-times fungicide application and balanced nutrient supply by the application of a plant density of 75,000 plants ha⁻¹. Regarding the plots not treated with fungicides yield amounts remained below 4,250 kg ha⁻¹ in case of the application of both unilateral N and PK supply and balanced nutrient supply as well. Changes in the applied plant density affected yield amounts significantly too. Fungicide treatments affected the possibility of plant density increase of the studied hybrids to a significant extent. The highest reaction towards fungicide treatment was observed in case of the hybrid

NK Neoma. Due to the balanced nutrient and fungicide treatment of the hybrid NK Neoma the extent of yield increment exceeded 1,000 kg ha⁻¹ in case of the plant density of 55,000 plants ha⁻¹, while in case of 75,000 plants ha⁻¹ it was over 2,000 kg ha⁻¹ respectively (Figure 3).

Fig. 4. Yield amount of the hybrids in different plant densities models and in fungicide treatment models regarding the average of nutrient supplies (Debrecen-Látókép, 2016)

Regarding the average of the studied hybrids and nutrient supply levels yield increasing effect of fungicide treatments was 987 kg ha⁻¹ in case of the application of a plant density 75,000 plants ha⁻¹ that was higher than the increment in case of the plant densities 35,000-55,000 plants ha⁻¹ (Figure 4).

In treatments without fungicide application the highest yield (4,240 kg ha⁻¹) was produced in plots of a plant density 55,000 plants ha⁻¹ – regarding the average of the studied hybrids. In case of the plant densities 35,000 and 75,000 plants ha⁻¹ yield amounts remained below 4000 kg ha⁻¹ by the application of all nutrient supply levels. In populations with two-times fungicide treatments yield amounts reached maximal values by the application of a plant density 75,000 plants ha⁻¹ at all three studied nutrient supply models. In treatment combinations of balanced NPK supply yield amount was 4,932 kg ha⁻¹ in case of a plant density of 75,000 plants ha⁻¹. However, yield results were higher than 4,500 kg ha⁻¹ even in treatment combination of unilateral N and PK supply. As an effect of fungicide treatments yield amounts were higher than 3,700 kg ha⁻¹ in case of the plant densities 35,000 and 55,000 plants ha⁻¹ in all studied treatment combinations (Figure 4 and 5).

Fig. 5. Yield amount in different sowing technology and nutrient supply models in without fungicides treatment and regarding the average of the hybrids (Debrecen-Látókép, 2016)

Fig. 6. Yield amount in different sowing technology and nutrient supply models in two times fungicides treatment and regarding the average of the hybrids s (Debrecen-Látókép, 2016)

Conclusions

Critical factors of sunflower production are sowing technology, harmonic nutrient supply and the adequate fungicide plant protection measurements. The results of the present experiment confirm the yield determining effect of nutrient supply and fungicide treatments in case of all three studied hybrids.

The highest yield amount was measured in the treatment models treated two-times with fungicide and fertilized with NPK substances in case of all three hybrids. The highest yield amount was harvested in all treatments in case of the hybrid NK Ferti.

Regarding the average of the hybrids the highest yield (4,240 kg ha⁻¹) without any fungicide treatment was measured in the treatment with harmonic nutrient supply with plant density of 55,000 plants ha⁻¹. When applying the plant density of 35,000 plants ha⁻¹ and 75,000 plants ha⁻¹ yield amounts were below 4,000 kg ha⁻¹ in case of all nutrient supply levels. Treatments with two-times fungicide treatment resulted maximal yield amounts in case of all three nutrient supply levels by the highest plant density, i.e. 75,000 plants ha⁻¹.

R E F E R E N C E S

- [1] Ragasits I. (1994): *Napraforgó*. In: *Növénytermesztés*, Iványi K. – Kismányoky T. - Ragasits I., *Mezőgazda Kiadó*, Budapest. 282-294
 - [2] Pepó, P. (2010): *A napraforgó termésbiztonságának agronómiai feltételei* Agrofórum 21.3. 12-15 p.
 - [3] Nagy, Z. (2002): *A Napraforgó-termesztés dilemmái*. *Mezőhír* 13. 3. 12p.
 - [4] Pepó, P. (2007): *A hibridspecifikus napraforgó-termesztés néhány agrotechnikai eleme*. *Agrofórum* 18.11.10-14. p.
 - [5] Frank, J. (1999): *Napraforgó biológiája, termesztése*. *Mezőgazda Kiadó*, Budapest
 - [6] Geleta, S.- Baltensperger, D. D.- Binford, G. G.- Miller, J. F. (1997): *Sunflower response to nitrogen and phosphorus in wheat-fallow cropping-systems*. *Journal of Production Agriculture*. 10. 3. 466-472 p.
 - [7] Rikk, I. (2007): *Szálljon be Ön is az olajüzletbe!* *Agrofórum* 18.11.16p.
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STUDY OF RELATIONSHIPS BETWEEN YIELD AND SOIL WATER MANAGEMENT OF WINTER WHEAT IN BI- AND TRICULTURE CROP ROTATION SYSTEMS

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Abstract. *The present research work was carried out within the confines of a polifactorial long-term field experiment set up in 1983 with bi- (maize-winter wheat) and triculture (maize-pea-winter wheat) crop rotation systems in two following crop years (2011/2012 and 2012/2013). Winter wheat was studied as test plant. Lower soil moisture volume percentage content values were calculated in the triculture among the studied systems. Water deficit values calculated for the bi- and triculture crop rotation systems proved the higher water use of winter wheat populations sown after pea pre-crop. Water deficit values before sowing confirm the different effect of pre-crops on soil water management. According to the results of the present study it has been stated that water stock of the chernozem soil is significantly affected by crop rotation.*

Keywords: long-term field experiment, winter wheat, crop rotation, soil water stock, yield

1. Introduction

Future possibilities of plant production will likely be extended or even limited by the adapting level in response of climatic changes. This adapting urges mainly the more effective water management [1]. Soil water retention capacity has a major role in the undisturbed functioning and adequate water supply of agro-ecosystems, because spring water deficit of plants (e.g. winter plants) can be ensured and supplied only from the soil water stock filled during the autumn-winter period [2, 3]. Soil microbial life, their enzymatic activity, just as their carbon cycle will be improved in case soil water supply is adequate [4]. Efficiency of agricultural water management is solely possible with the enhancement of water utilization efficiency. Basic element of this is the effective regulation of soil water balance, moisture management [5, 6].

Winter wheat is one of the most important crops produced worldwide. There are significant differences in its yield production in different crop years; it shows sensitive reaction especially towards extreme conditions, such as too high amount of precipitation or even drought. Production of high yield amounts is ensured in case climatic conditions (first of all water supply) match the demands of the plant populations optimally. Water deficit affects yield amount to a significant extent, especially in the generative phase. Stress caused by early spring dry weather conditions does not decrease the number of ears but the amount of grain yield will

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be lower [7, 8, 9, 10, 11, 12, 13, 14]. Even a single time applied irrigation affects yield producing factors, yield and water utilization, just as leaf area index [15]. If soil water content decreases plants have to input more energy in water uptake. Intensity of transpiration does not decrease until at least 50% of plant available water stock of the soil is accessible. Winter wheat has an uptake of 400 mm water per vegetation period in Hungary. Water deficit during the stem elongation and grain filling vegetation phases result in significant yield decrement [16, 17].

2. Material and methods

The study of water management of a chernozem soil type was executed within the confines of a polifactorial long-term field experiment set up in 1983 at the University of Debrecen, Faculty of Agricultural and Food Sciences and Environmental Management, Institute of Crop Sciences, Experimental Station at Látókép. Experimental soil is a calcareous chernozem with good water infiltration and water retention properties. The area of each experimental plot is 41.1 m².

Nutrient supply level of N₁₀₀+PK, two irrigation models (with and without irrigation) and two crop rotation systems (bi- and triculture) were studied in the experiment. Maize and winter wheat are sown in the bi-, while maize, pea and winter wheat in the tri-culture crop rotation system. The studied winter wheat variety was GK Csillag. Soil tillage, plant protection and harvesting measurements were executed uniform. Irrigation was applied in the vegetation of the maize pre-crop in case of both studied crop rotation systems.

For the study of soil water management soil samples were taken from each 20 cm of the upper 200 cm soil layer with four replications four times per each vegetation. Thus altogether 1280 samples were processed. First soil samples were taken before sowing, while the fourth after harvest from the stubble. The other two samplings between were taken in the main phenological phases during winter wheat vegetation (stem elongation and heading-flowering).

The amount of fallen precipitation ensured the water demand of winter wheat during the two studied crop years (2011/2012, 2012/2013) (Table 1). However, the distribution of the precipitation showed significant differences. Extreme low amount of water was available during the germination and early development of winter wheat in the vegetation 2011/2012. Dry conditions were only dissolved by the amount of 71.1 mm precipitation that fell in December. The amount of precipitation during the winter months (December, January and February) was altogether 116.9 mm.

60% (228.9 mm) of the total amount of precipitation in the vegetation of winter wheat was registered in May, June and July.

Vegetation period of the crop year 2012/2013 was more balanced from the aspect of precipitation distribution. Dry conditions of the period before sowing were dissolved by the amount of precipitation in December that was 22.3 mm higher than the 30-years' average value. Altogether 157.4 mm amount of precipitation fell during the winter months (December, January and February) of the vegetation. In contrast to the previous crop year 2013 was wet right until the execution of harvest measurements (391 mm fell from January to July). Four times higher amount of precipitation was measured in the early spring period, i.e. in March than the 30-years' average value.

Table 3) Main weather condition parameters of the crop years 2011/2012 and 2012/2013 (Debrecen-Látókép, 2011/2012, 2012/2013)

Month	2011/2012		2012/2013		30-years' average	
	Prec. (mm)	Temp. (°C)	Prec. (mm)	Temp. (°C)	Prec. (mm)	Temp. (°C)
October	18.1	8.6	22.4	11.1	30.8	10.3
November	0	0.6	16.6	7.2	45.2	4.5
December	71.1	1.5	65.8	-1.2	43.5	-0.2
January	28.0	-0.6	38.7	-1.0	37.0	-2.6
February	17.8	-5.7	52.9	2.3	30.2	0.2
March	1.4	6.3	136.3	2.9	33.5	5.0
April	20.7	11.7	48.0	12	42.4	10.7
May	71.9	16.4	68.7	16.6	58.8	15.8
June	91.7	20.9	30.8	19.6	79.5	18.7
July	65.3	23.3	15.6	21.2	65.7	20.3
Total precipitation (mm)	386	-	495.8	-	466.6	-
Average temperature (°C)	-	8.3	-	9.1	-	8.3

Regarding average temperature values it can be sated that both studied crop years were warmer than the average of the previous 30 years. Exceptions were November and February in the vegetation 2011/2012, when temperature was on average 3.9 °C, just as 5.5 °C lower, while December and March in 2012/2013 were on average 1, just as 2.1 °C respectively colder than the long-term average values.

3. Results and discussion

Soil moisture content was expressed as volume percentage. Using these values water deficit values were calculated. Water deficit value explains the water amount the actual soil water stock is lower of at the time of sampling in contrast to the water content values of state when soil is filled to field capacity. Water deficit values of the crop years 2011/2012 and 2012/2013 were assessed (Figure 1.) and compared to yield amount results. Soil water deficit values in October 2012 were significantly lower (71.9 and 82.4 mm resp.) in both studied crop

rotation systems than those of the next crop year, which can be explained by the amount of precipitation in the end of the summer period.

Both August and September of 2013 were dry that is confirmed by soil water deficit values of both crop rotation systems (biculture: 255.7 mm, triculture: 213.4 mm). As an effect of soil water stock filling of winter precipitation water deficit values in April were lower in both crop years and in case of both crop rotation system soils (in 2012 by 78.2, just as 7.4 mm in bi- and triculture, while in 2013 by 113.7 and 46.8 mm respectively). Despite the rainfalls in May and June 2012 soil water deficit exceeded 200 mm as a consequence of water utilization of winter wheat populations, just as the increase of the average temperature. This tendency remained similar during the whole vegetation. Soil water deficit values did not decrease to a significant extent, but in case of the triculture crop rotation system they increased by 22.4 mm until the end of the vegetation period (Table 2).

However, in 2013 water deficit values calculated in June were similar to the previous sampling period (April), no significant difference could be determined between the two sampling times (biculture April: 142 mm, June 128.5 mm; triculture April: 166.6 mm, June 164.5 mm resp.). This confirms the favourable effect of the high amount of precipitation in March. This water management state was added to the amount of precipitation of the following months. Thus, the increasing water demand of vegetative and generative development stages of winter wheat populations could be ensured. Soil water deficit increased till the harvest (by 47.9 mm in biculture, by 104.7 mm in triculture) due to the increasing drought, the low amount of precipitation in July and the water demand of the plant population during the ripening processes.

According to the results of the present research work it can be stated that water stock of the chernozem soil is significantly affected by the applied crop rotation system. In the studied two crop years regarding the two crop rotation systems involved triculture system showed higher water deficit values during the whole vegetation period of winter wheat. The highest water deficit values were calculated in this treatment combination: water deficit was 39 mm (April 2012), just as 22.6 mm (June 2012) and 56.6 mm (July 2012) higher in the triculture crop rotation system than in the biculture system. In 2013 these values were 24.6 mm in April, 36 mm in June and 92.8 mm in July respectively. The obtained results prove the higher water utilization of winter wheat sown after pea, because plants needed higher water amount in order to ensure the higher nutrient uptake of plants (for the nitrogen content increasing effect of the pre-crop). Water deficit values before sowing prove the different effect of different pre-crops. At the beginning of the vegetation period soil moisture content after the pre-crop pea – despite a dry summer – was still significantly higher (water deficit was 31.8 mm higher in

2012, while 42.3 mm higher in 2013 in case of the biculture crop rotation system than after maize). In contrast to maize pea is harvested much earlier and it uses less water. Thus pea populations leave higher available water amount in the soil for the disposal of the next population in the crop rotation system.

Regarding average yield results of the two studied crop years it can be stated that in the crop year 2011/2012 winter wheat produced a yield amount of 7.273 kg ha⁻¹ in the triculture, while 7.425 kg ha⁻¹ in the biculture crop rotation system. There was only 152 kg ha⁻¹ difference in the yield amounts, no significant difference (Table 2) was proved between the yield results of the two studied crop rotation systems.

Figure 1. Dynamic changes in yield amounts and soil water deficit values of bi- and triculture winter wheat populations (Debrecen-Látókép, chernozem soil type, 2011/2012, 2012/2013)

Table 4) Table of variance for the evaluation of water deficit values and yield result of the crop years 2011/2012 and 2012/2013

LSD _{5%} crop rotation	12.10.2011.	05.04.2012.	01.06.2012.	16.07.2012.
water deficit (mm)	64.7	62.3	67.2	42.9
yield (kg ha ⁻¹)	499.2			
	17.10.2012.	29.04.2013.	13.06.2013.	10.07.2013.
water deficit (mm)	10.1	22.7	16.3	41.0
yield (kg ha ⁻¹)	684.2			

In the crop year 2012/2013 6.382 kg ha⁻¹ grain yield was harvested in the biculture, while 8.441 kg ha⁻¹ in the triculture system. Consequently, significant (2.059 kg ha⁻¹) yield surplus was measured in winter wheat population of the triculture crop rotation system.

Conclusions

According to the calculated water deficit values and the obtained yield results it can be stated that regarding water supply the crop year 2012/2013 was more favourable from the aspect of yield producing processes of winter wheat. Pea – as a pre-crop in the triculture crop rotation system – has favourable effect on soil nutrient management. As soil moisture content enabled the production of higher yield amounts yield increasing effect of pea pre-crop is confirmed in the present study. In order to utilize the nutrients available in the soil winter wheat demands an adequate amount of disposable water. Yield results of the two studied crop years confirm this as well. In case – according to the demand of winter wheat – adequate water amount is not available in the soil in the critical phenological phases (stem elongation, heading-flowering) the favourable effect of the pre-crop cannot be confirmed – according to the yield results of the present research work.

Considering the results it can be stated that water deficit values of the triculture crop rotation system were higher in both studied crop years and water uptake of the plant population was more intensive. In contrast the winter wheat population of the biculture crop rotation system lower water deficit did not result in any significant yield surplus in the dryer crop year (2011/2012), because the population utilized the available soil water amount more wasting. Based on the results of the present work it can be stated that as an effect of the pea pre-crop (from the aspect of soil water and nitrogen stock) water utilization of the winter wheat population of the triculture crop rotation system was changed.

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R E F E R E N C E S

- [1] Jolánkai M. - Birkás M.: 2009. *Klímaváltozás és növénytermesztés. Növénytermesztés: Gazdálkodás – Klímaváltozás – Társadalom*. Szerk.: Harcsa M.. V. Növénytermesztési Tudományos Nap. 27-34.
-

-
- [2] Farkas Cs. - Tóth E. - Várallyay Gy.: 2004. *A talaj fizikai tulajdonságainak vizsgálata talajművelési kísérletben. „AGRO-21” Füzetek. Agroökológia. Agroökoszisztémák környezeti összefüggései és szabályozásának lehetőségei.* 2004. **37.** szám. 111.
- [3] Várallyay Gy.: 2005. *A magyar Alföld szélsőséges vízgazdálkodása és az ahhoz történő alkalmazkodás lehetőségei és korlátai.* In: Pepó P. (szerk.): *Korszakváltás a hazai mezőgazdaságban: a modern növénytermesztés alapjai.* Tudományos ülés. Debrecen. 43-51.
- [4] Kátai J.: 2006. *changes in Soil Characteristics in a Mono- and Triculture Long-term Field Experiment.* Agrochemistry and Soil Science. **55.** 1. 183-192.
- [5] Várallyay Gy. - Németh T.: 1999. *A környezetkímélő növénytermesztés talajtani-agrokémiai alapjai.* In: Ruzsányi L. - Pepó P. (szerk.): *Növénytermesztés és környezetvédelem. „Magyarország az ezredfordulón” – Stratégiai kutatások a Magyar Tudományos Akadémián.* Budapest. 69-75.
- [6] Várallyay Gy.: 1999. *A talaj vízgazdálkodásának szabályozása - mint a környezetkímélő növénytermesztés egyik kulcskérdése.* In: Ruzsányi L. - Pepó P. (szerk.): *Növénytermesztés és környezetvédelem. „Magyarország az ezredfordulón” – Stratégiai kutatások a Magyar Tudományos Akadémián.* Budapest. 56-65.
- [7] A. Kirkpatrick - L. Browning - J. W. Bauder - R. Waskom - M. Neibauer - G. Cardon: 2006. *Irrigating with Limited Water Supplies: A Practical Guide to Choosing Crops Well-Suited to Limited Irrigation.* Extension Water Quality Program. Bozeman. Montana State University. 15.
- [8] Domuța C.: 2010. *The influence of the irrigation suspending on water consumption, yield and on water use efficiency in maiza in the Crisurilor plain condition.* Analele Universității din Oradea, Fascicula: Protecția Mediului Vol. **XV.**, 2010 pp.87-93.
- [9] Harsh N. - Deepti G.: 2006. *Differential sensitivity of C3 and C4 plants to water deficit stress: Association with oxidative stress and antioxidants.* Environmental and Experimental Botany. **58.** 106–113.
- [10] Kassai M. K. - Nyárai H. F. - Máté A. - Tarnawa Á. - Szentpétery Zs. - Jolánkai M.: 2012. *Az évszázad hatása az őszi búza (Triticum aestivum L.) termésmennyiségére és –minőségére. Talaj – Víz – Növény – kapcsolatrendszer a növénytermesztési térben.* (Szerk.: Lehoczky É.) I. Talajtani, Vízgazdálkodási és Növénytermesztési Tudományos Nap. Debrecen. 197-204.
- [11] M. M. Ibrahim - S. A. Ouda - A. Taha - G. El Afandi - S. M. Eid: 2012. *Water management for wheat grown in sandy soil under climate change conditions.* Journal of Soil Science and Plant Nutrition. 12. **2.** 195-210.
- [12] Pepó P.: 2002. *A hazai őszi búzatermesztés helyzete és fejlesztési lehetőségei.* Gyakorlati agrofórum. 13. **9.** 2-5.
- [13] Szász G.: 1973. *A termesztett növények vízigényének és az öntözés gyakoriságának meteorológiai vizsgálata.* Növénytermelés. **22.** 3. 241-258.
- [14] Szécsényi M. - Cserháti M. - Zvara Á. - Dudits D. - Györgyey J.: 2013. *Monitoring of Transcriptional Responses in Roots of Six Wheat Cultivars during Mild Drought Stress.* Cereal Research Communications. **41.** 4. 527-538.
- [15] Zhang Bu - C. Huang G. - B. Li Feng-Min: 2007. *Effect of Limited Single Irrigation on Yield of Winter Wheat and Spring Maize Relay Intercropping.* Pedosphere. 17. **4.** 529–537.
- [16] Klupács H. – Tarnawa Á. – Balla I – Jolánkai M.: 2010. *Impact of water availability on winter wheat (Triticum aestivum L.) yield characteristics.* Agrokémia és Talajtan. 59. **1.** 151–156.
- [17] Varga B. - Veisz O.: 2013. *A szimulált aszály hatásai az őszi búza produkciójára és vízforgalmára.* In: Janda T. (szerk.): *II. ATK Tudományos Nap – Velünk Élő Tudomány.* 85-88.
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EFFECT OF IRRIGATION ON THE QUALITY OF POTATO VARIETIES

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Abstract. *Among agro-techniques, year effects, variety and irrigation factors have a considerable impact on potato yield quality and quantity. In Hungary, the biggest limiting factor of potato cultivation is the shortage of precipitation and the high average temperature during period of potato tuber development. Potato has a demand for high and even water supply, this crop can reach 100% of its growing capacity if properly irrigated, and the safety of growing and the quality can also be increased. The water shortage between May and August negatively affects the number of tubers, the tuber size and quality apart from the yield. For safe potato growing irrigation is essential.*

Keywords: Potato, varieties, irrigation, yield, quality

1. Introduction

In Hungary, the growing area of potato has dropped dramatically in the last few decades; moreover, we lag behind Western European countries as regards yields. The ecological and climatic conditions of Hungary are not suitable for potato growing everywhere [1], but the low yields also have other causes: the use of not suitable seeds, the low level of irrigation, nutrient supply and old-fashioned machines. The competitiveness of production is further decreased by the great alternation in yields from year to year, unpredictable market conditions, poor consumption habits and often the lack of quality products. For potato growing, considering its original place, humid areas are the most suitable, where the weather is slightly cool, and summer is moderately warm [2]. High temperature reduces the allocation of plant biomass to tubers and will result in smaller leaves, more nodes per stem, longer internodes, taller plants, higher leaf areas and lower ratios of leaf/stem leaf [3]. Water stress causes yield loss by reducing the growth of crop canopy and biomass. Water at 3–5 mm per day is necessary for evapotranspiration (ET) and the maintenance of optimal soil moisture tension (10–50 kPa) in growing potatoes [4, 5]. In order to maintain at least our domestic market positions we should improve the level of production. To achieve this, quality should improve besides the enhancement of yield per hectare and the

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simultaneous reduction of production costs [6]. The higher average of yield and tuber quality could be achieved by improving technological elements in the production chain. Ecological limits could be overcome by irrigation and tuber yields of 40-50 t ha⁻¹, or even higher could be attained [7].

2. Materials and methods

In our experiment we examined the yield and some quality parameters of 9 medium-early varieties in large plots. Among the examined varieties, 3 were Dutch (Kuroda Desirée és Kondor), and 6 were Hungarian breeding (Rioja, Lorett, Góliát, Kánkán, Hópehely, White Lady). The 9 varieties were examined in 4 replications in randomized blocks: two replications were irrigated and two were non-irrigated. Beside the yield of the varieties, we examined the effect of irrigation on the quality parameters (dry matter-, starch-, protein content and index of frying).

2 way-anova and Pearson correlation coefficient were calculated using SPSS for Windows 13.0 statistical software package.

2.1. Weather conditions

In 2004, during the vegetation period of the potato, the amount of the precipitation was 342.6 mm, 2.6 mm lower than the 30 years' average (345.1 mm), but the distribution of precipitation was unfavourable. May was extremely dry; the monthly amount of precipitation was only 17 mm, 41.8 mm lower than the average. In July the quantity of rainfall was twice higher than the average (142 mm), which was unfavourable in terms of pathological parameters. The average monthly temperature was 19.3°C in June and 21.1°C in July, which is higher than the requirement of the potato (17-18°C).

In 2005, the amount of precipitation was sufficient during the vegetation period of the potato, and also the distribution of precipitation was relatively even. The amount of precipitation only in June (54.3 mm) was lower than the average of the last 30 years (79.5 mm). The amount of precipitation was higher than the 30 years' average in April, May, July, August (with 75 mm) and in September. The average monthly temperature was about the 30 years' average; the monthly average temperature only in July (21°C) was higher than the average (20.3°C).

In 2006, during the vegetation period of the potato the amount of rainfall was 326.2 mm, 18.9 mm lower than the 30 years' average (345.1 mm). The amount of precipitation in April (92.3 mm) was 49.9 mm higher than the average (42.4 mm), and the planting date was at the end of April. The amount of precipitation was about the 30 years' average in May, June and August, but the monthly amount of precipitation in July was almost the half of the average. September was droughty;

the amount of the rainfall was only 5.3 mm. The monthly average temperature was 1.4°C higher in April and 2.2°C higher in September than the average. In July, in the most critical period the average monthly temperature was 2.9°C higher than the 30 years' average (20.3°C).

2.2. Soil characteristics of the experimental site

The experiment was carried out at the experimental site of the Farm and Regional Research Institute, University of Debrecen, at Látókép. The soil of the experiment field was calciferous chernozem developed on loess with deep mould. The experiment's soil is in good condition, according to the soil physics it is classified as a middle bound loam soil. The thickness of the mould layer is between 80 and 90 cm, and the evenly mould layer's average mould content is 2.8%. CaCO₃ appears in the transitional layer of the soil profile, at the depth of 70–100 cm.

The cultivated layer's acidity (KCL pH) is between 6.3 and 6.5, the N content is 0.12-0.15%. The experimental site's soil has good potassium content (240 mg kg⁻¹), the phosphorous content is variable, the average phosphorous content is medium (133 mg kg⁻¹). The minimum field water capacity (FCmin) ranges between 33.65 and 46 %, the non-available water (NW) ranges between 8.5-15.7 % in the 0-200 cm soil layer. Soil water table is in 8-10 m depth, the soil can store a substantial amount of water.

2.3. Agro-technology used in the experiment

The applied fertilizer dose was 165 kg ha⁻¹ N, 210 kg ha⁻¹ P₂O₅, and 220 kg ha⁻¹ K₂O in all the 3 year. The experiment was set up on 50 m² parcels, after winter wheat (2004 and 2006) and two rowed barley (2005) as a forecrop. The plant density was 51.000 plants ha⁻¹.

Table 5) Main agro-technical parameters

Name	2004	2005	2006
Date of fertilizer	9 April: N: 160; P ₂ O ₅ : 120; K ₂ O: 220 kg ha ⁻¹	18 April N: 160; P ₂ O ₅ : 120; K ₂ O: 220 kg ha ⁻¹	24 April: N: 160; P ₂ O ₅ : 120; K ₂ O: 220 kg ha ⁻¹
Planting date	21-22 April	2 May	24 April
Irrigation	22 May: 15 mm (all repetitions)	2 June: 30 mm	19 July: 30 mm
	5 June: 25 mm	28 July: 30 mm.	13 July: 30 mm
	11 June: 30 mm		
	8 July: 30 mm		
Harvesting	22 September	6-27 September	25 September

The replications were irrigated 4 times in 2004: on 22 May 2004 with 15 mm; on 05 June 2004 with 25 mm; on 11 June 2004 with 30 mm; on 08 July 2004 with 30 mm. In May we had to irrigate all of the repetitions, because of the drought and the chapped soil. In 2005 the dates of irrigation were 01 June and 28 July with 30 mm. In 2006 the repetitions were irrigated 2 times: 19 and 30 July with 30 mm. Table 1 shows the main agro-technical parameters.

3. Experimental results and discussions

3.1. The effect of irrigation on yield

In 2004, the yield of the non-irrigated experiments was 32.36 t ha^{-1} , and under irrigation the average yield of the 9 examined varieties was 34.64 t ha^{-1} . Irrigation did not increase the yield significantly ($\text{LSD}_{5\%}=2.49 \text{ t ha}^{-1}$). Without irrigation the yield of Hópehely (55.37 t ha^{-1}) and White Lady (46.00 t ha^{-1}) varieties was salient. The yield of Desirée (non-irrigated: 17.27 t ha^{-1} , irrigated: 17.35 t ha^{-1}) and Góliát varieties was under 30 t ha^{-1} , as a consequence of diseases caused by the large amount of precipitation. The yield of Lorett, Rioja, White Lady and Hópehely varieties was higher than the yield of Desirée, Góliát, Kánkán and Kondor varieties respectively ($\text{LSD}_{5\%}=4.50 \text{ t ha}^{-1}$) (figure 1).

Fig. 1: The effect of irrigation on the yield of potato varieties (t ha^{-1}). Debrecen-Látókép, 2004-2006.

In 2005, there was not substantial difference between irrigated (46.45 t ha^{-1}) and non-irrigated (44.50 t ha^{-1}). Irrigation increased the yield significantly, but the difference between the yield of irrigated and non-irrigated treatments was on the edge of significance ($\text{LSD}_{5\%}=1.94 \text{ t ha}^{-1}$). The yield of Rioja (36.35 t ha^{-1} ; 36.55 t ha^{-1}) and Góliát (38.00 t ha^{-1} ; 38.00 t ha^{-1}) varieties was lower than 40.00 t ha^{-1} both under non-irrigated and irrigated conditions. Under irrigated conditions the yield of Hópehely variety was 57.45 t ha^{-1} , and the yield of Desirée (55.28 t ha^{-1}) and Loret (51.11 t ha^{-1}) varieties was higher than 50 t ha^{-1} as well. The yield of White Lady was higher than the yield of Rioja respectively ($\text{LSD}_{5\%}=7.82 \text{ t ha}^{-1}$).

In 2006, the yield of the non-irrigated repetitions was 35.93 t ha^{-1} . Irrigation increased the yield respectively to 41.21 t ha^{-1} ($\text{LSD}_{5\%}=2.49 \text{ t ha}^{-1}$). Irrigation increased the yield of every variety which proves the importance of the even water supply in July. Without irrigation the yield of Loret (42.69 t ha^{-1}) and Kuroda (42.16 t ha^{-1}) varieties was higher than 40 t ha^{-1} . Under irrigation the yield of the Loret variety was the highest (46.24 t ha^{-1}), and the yield of Kondor, Kuroda, Hópehely, Desirée and White Lady varieties was over 40 t ha^{-1} . The yield of Góliát variety was lower than the yield of Kuroda and Loret varieties ($\text{LSD}_{5\%}=11.20 \text{ t ha}^{-1}$).

3.2. The effect of irrigation on the dry matter content

In 2004, the average dry matter content was 21.93% under non-irrigated and 22.00% under irrigated conditions. The dry matter content of Rioja variety was higher than 26% both under non-irrigated and irrigated cultivations. The dry matter content of Kuroda (non-irrigated: 25.35%), Hópehely (non-irrigated: 22.50%, irrigated: 24.53%) and White Lady (non-irrigated: 23.57%, irrigated: 23.46%) varieties was favourable. Without irrigation the dry matter contents of Desirée (18.95%) and Loret (17.22%) varieties were under 20%, which is unfavourable in respect of storage and frying quality (table 2).

In 2005, the dry matter content of the non-irrigated replications was 22.35%, and with irrigation it was 21.62%. The dry matter content of Rioja variety was 24.83% under non-irrigated and 24.42% under irrigated cultivation. In 2005 the dry matter content of Desirée variety was favourable (non-irrigated: 24.42%, irrigated: 22.08%) in consequence of the even precipitation. Under non-irrigated cultivation the dry matter content of White Lady (22.71%) and Hópehely (22.54%) varieties was higher than the average of the 9 varieties as well. The dry matter content of Góliát (19.82%) and Loret (18.19%) were under 20% under irrigation, too.

The dry matter content was lower in 2006 than in preceding years. The average dry matter content was 20.13% without irrigation. As a result of irrigation the dry matter content in the average of the examined varieties increased to 21.39%

(LSD_{5%}=1.02%). The dry matter content of Rioja (non-irrigated: 23.81%, irrigated: 24.48%) and Kuroda (non-irrigated: 23.16%, irrigated: 22.39%) varieties was the highest. Without irrigation the dry matter content of Loret (17.98%), Kánkán (17.88%) and Kondor (17.00%) varieties was low. At such a low dry matter content the potato cannot be storage safely. The dry matter content of Kondor (19.69%) and Loret (18.34%) varieties was lower than 20% under irrigation as well.

Table 6 The effect of irrigation on the dry matter content of potato varieties (%). Debrecen-Látókép, 2004-2006.

	2004		2005		2006	
	Irrigated	Non-irrigated	Irrigated	Non-irrigated	Irrigated	Non-irrigated
Rioja	26.44	26.40	24.42	24.83	24.48	23.81
Góliát	20.24	21.34	19.82	20.43	19.68	20.06
White Lady	23.46	23.57	21.20	22.71	21.81	22.18
Kánkán	23.24	21.51	23.89	22.16	23.19	17.88
Hópehely	24.53	22.50	21.08	22.54	22.08	20.90
Desirée	20.06	18.95	22.80	24.42	20.89	18.20
Kondor	18.62	21.13	21.69	21.15	19.69	17.00
Kuroda	22.96	25.35	21.47	21.74	22.39	23.16
Loret	17.88	17.22	18.19	21.23	18.34	17.98
Average	21.93	22.00	21.62	22.35	21.39	20.13
LSD _{5%}	Varieties: 5.25 Irrigation: 1.16 Interaction: 3.74		Varieties: 5.14 Irrigation: 1.16 Interaction: 3.74		Varieties: 4.10 Irrigation: 1.02 Interaction: 3.05	

The dry matter content of Rioja (25.06%) variety was the highest in every year, and the dry matter content of Kuroda (22.84%), White Lady (22.49%) and Hópehely (22.27%) varieties was favourable as well. The dry matter content of Kondor (19.88%) and Loret (18.47%) was the lowest. In the average of the 3 year of the experiment, the dry matter content of Rioja variety was higher than the dry matter content of Loret variety (LSD_{5%}=4.25%).

In 2004 (0.846**) and 2006 (0.749**) there was positive correlation between the dry matter and the starch content and the protein content as well (2004: 0.711**, 2006: 0.443**). There was negative correlation between the dry matter content and the index of frying colour in each year during the experiment (2004: -0.712**, 2005: -0.592**, 2006: -0.375*) and between the content of reducing sugars (2004: -0.383*, 2005: -0.369*, 2006: -0.395*). The varieties with higher dry matter content had lower index of frying colour and reducing sugar content (Rioja, Kuroda).

3.3. The effect of irrigation on the starch content

In 2004, the starch content was 14.75% under non-irrigated and 15.52% under irrigated conditions. The starch content of Rioja variety was the highest both under non-irrigated (21.58%) and irrigated (17.91%) cultivation. Similarly to the dry matter content, the starch content of White Lady (non-irrigated: 16.66%, irrigated: 17.63%) and Kuroda (non-irrigated: 17.40%, irrigated: 16.05%) varieties was higher than the average of the 9 varieties. The starch content of Desirée (irrigated: 12.44%, non-irrigated: 13.45%) and Lorett (irrigated: 12.76%, non-irrigated: 12.37%) varieties was unfavourable. The starch content of Rioja variety was higher than the starch content of Góliát, Kánkán, Desirée, Kondor and Lorett varieties, respectively ($LSD_{5\%}=5.02\%$) (Table 3).

Table 7) The effect of irrigation on the starch content of potato varieties (%). Debrecen-Látókép, 2004-2006.

	2004		2005		2006	
	Irrigated	Non-irrigated	Irrigated	Non-irrigated	Irrigated	Non-irrigated
Rioja	21.58	17.91	18.77	16.63	17.37	17.53
Góliát	13.27	14.12	15.97	18.02	14.94	14.08
White Lady	17.63	16.66	16.18	20.77	16.02	15.05
Kánkán	15.58	12.38	17.69	15.54	16.40	14.02
Hópehely	16.62	14.44	18.45	16.08	14.73	11.65
Desirée	13.45	12.44	18.45	16.13	12.62	11.33
Kondor	13.19	14.67	15.00	15.48	12.30	13.00
Kuroda	16.05	17.40	18.98	17.96	16.46	15.81
Lorett	12.37	12.76	14.89	14.57	12.68	12.30
Average	15.52	14.75	17.15	16.79	14.83	13.86
$LSD_{5\%}$	Varieties: 5.02 Irrigation: 1.24 Interaction: 3.73		Varieties: 10.56 Irrigation: 1.42 Interaction: 4.25		Varieties: 2.98 Irrigation: 0.56 Interaction: 1.68	

The even water supply is favourable in a respect of the starch content of potato; the highest starch content was measured in 2005. The average starch content was 16.79% under non-irrigated and 17.15% under irrigated conditions. In spite of the even water supply the starch content increased in case of 6 varieties. Under non-irrigated cultivation the starch content of White Lady variety (20.77 %) and under irrigation the starch content of Rioja variety (18.77 %) was the highest. The starch content of Lorett (non-irrigated: 14.57%, irrigated: 14.89%) and Kondor (non-irrigated: 15.48%, irrigated: 15.00%) varieties was low.

During the experiment the starch content was the lowest in 2006. The amount of precipitation was only 31 millimetres in July, and the irrigation increased the starch content respectively ($LSD_{5\%}=0.56\%$), which proves that the even water

supply during the development of tubers is very important. The average starch content was 13.86% under non-irrigated and 14.83% under irrigated conditions. With irrigation the starch content increased in case of 7 varieties. The starch content of Rioja variety was the highest both under non-irrigated (17.53%) and irrigated (17.37%) cultivation. The starch content of Rioja variety was higher than the starch content of Desirée, Lorett, Kondor and Hópehely varieties ($LSD_{5\%}=2.98\%$).

Irrigation increased the starch content each 3 years, but significant difference was found only in 2006, when the precipitation was low. The starch content of Rioja, White Lady and Kuroda varieties was higher than 15% in every year. The starch content of Kánkán, Hópehely and Desirée varieties increased as a result of irrigation in every year, their quality can be improved by even water supply. The starch content of Lorett variety was low, but it was higher with 2% than in 2004 and 2006 in consequence of the relatively good weather conditions. There was positive correlation between the starch and the protein content (2004: 0.603**, 2006: 0.360*). There was negative correlation between the starch content and the index of frying colour (2004:-0.645**, 2006: -0.385*).

3.4. The effect of irrigation on protein content

In 2004, under irrigation the protein content of every examined variety was higher than 2.00%. The protein content was 2.38% under non-irrigated and 2.28% under irrigated conditions. The protein content of the Rioja (non-irrigated: 2.78%, irrigated: 2.77%) and Kuroda (non-irrigated: 2.55%, irrigated: 2.56%) varieties was the highest. The starch content was higher in the case of these varieties as well (table 4).

In 2005, without irrigation the average protein content of the varieties was 1.90%. Irrigation increased the average protein content to 2.06%, respectively ($LSD_{5\%}=0.13\%$). Irrigation increased the protein content in case of 7 varieties. The protein content of Kánkán, Rioja (non-irrigated: 1.99%, irrigated: 2.28%), Kuroda (non-irrigated: 1.95%, irrigated: 2.08%) and Desirée (non-irrigated: 1.94%, irrigated: 2.35%) varieties was favourable. Without irrigation the protein content of Góliát (1.78%), White Lady (1.76%) and Kondor (1.72%) varieties was low. The protein content of White Lady (1.92%), Hópehely (1.76%) and Kondor (1.74%) varieties was lower than 2.00% under irrigation as well.

In 2006, the protein content was lower than in the precedent years. In 2006 the average protein content was 1.85% under non-irrigated cultivation and 1.87% under irrigation. The protein content of Rioja (non-irrigated: 2.38%, irrigated: 2.09%) and Kuroda (non-irrigated: 2.30%, irrigated: 2.14%) varieties was the highest in 2006 as well. Under irrigation the protein content of Lorett (1.48%) and Kánkán (1.45%) varieties was very low.

Table 8) The effect of irrigation on the protein content of potato varieties (%). Debrecen-Látókép, 2004-2006.

	2004		2005		2006	
	Irrigated	Non-irrigated	Irrigated	Non-irrigated	Irrigated	Non-irrigated
Rioja	2.77	2.78	2.28	1.99	2.09	2.36
Góliát	1.94	2.17	2.15	1.78	2.10	1.76
White Lady	2.16	2.54	1.92	1.76	1.82	1.62
Kánkán	2.52	2.34	2.13	2.22	1.45	1.63
Hópehely	2.38	2.12	1.76	1.87	1.81	1.67
Desirée	2.33	2.43	2.35	1.94	2.12	1.64
Kondor	2.00	2.43	1.74	1.72	1.83	1.65
Kuroda	2.56	2.55	2.08	1.95	2.14	2.30
Lorett	1.86	2.05	2.14	1.86	1.48	2.03
Average	2.28	2.38	2.06	1.90	1.87	1.85
LSD _{5%}	Varieties: 0.81 Irrigation: 0.17 Interaction: 0.50		Varieties: 0.52 Irrigation: 0.13 Interaction: 0.39		Varieties: 0.94 Irrigation: 0.20 Interaction: 0.59	

The highest protein contents were measured in 2004, without irrigation the protein content of all varieties was higher than 2%. The varieties with higher protein content (Rioja, Kuroda) had higher starch content as well, which shows the positive correlation between these two factors. The shortage of precipitation during the summer is disadvantageous in the point of view of protein content of potato tubers; the lowest protein content was measured in 2006 in the case of most of the varieties. The amount of precipitation in July influences the protein content in a large measure (0.524). There was positive correlation between the protein- and the starch content in every year during the experiment. The protein content is in correlation with the frying quality. There was negative correlation between the protein content and the index of frying colour in 2004 (-0.653**) and 2006 (-0.410*).

3.5. The effect of irrigation on index of frying colour

The index of frying colour is result of a subjective method. The lower if index of frying colour is more favourable. For the food industry the value under 3 is very good, between 3 and 4 is acceptable.

The index of frying colour was the lowest in 2005 and the highest in 2006 which proves that the relatively favourable year effect and the even water supply have favourable effect on the frying quality of potato as well (table 5). The index of frying colour depends on the variety in the first place; there was significant difference between the indexes of the varieties in every year. The index of frying colour of Rioja variety was under value 2.00 in every year, and the index of Lorett

variety changed about value 3 in every year. There was significant difference between the indexes of frying colour of the varieties in the average of the years as well; the average colour of frying index of Rioja variety was lower than the index of the other varieties, respectively. The colour of frying colour of Lorett variety was higher than the indexes of Rioja, Desirée, Kuroda, Hópehely and Kondor varieties (LSD5%=0.78).

Table 9) The effect of irrigation on the colour of frying index of potato varieties. Debrecen-Látókép, 2004-2006.

	2004		2005		2006	
	Irrigated	Non-irrigated	Irrigated	Non-irrigated	Irrigated	Non-irrigated
Rioja	1,05	1,10	1,80	1,25	1,90	1,60
Góliát	2,93	3,00	3,23	2,46	2,25	2,40
White Lady	2,98	2,40	2,58	2,60	2,80	3,05
Kánkán	2,65	2,60	2,50	2,43	2,85	2,80
Hópehely	2,30	2,40	2,25	2,55	2,50	3,15
Desirée	2,53	2,60	2,28	1,85	2,20	2,50
Kondor	2,75	2,33	2,39	2,88	2,50	2,65
Kuroda	2,48	2,40	2,38	2,40	2,35	2,60
Lorett	3,00	3,53	3,63	3,25	3,55	3,33
Average	2,52	2,48	2,56	2,41	2,54	2,68
LSD5%	Varieties: 0.77 Irrigation: 0.19 Interaction: 0.57		Varieties: 1.38 Irrigation: 0.20 Interaction: 0.61		Varieties: 0.90 Irrigation: 0.21 Interaction: 0.63	

Conclusions

On the base of the results of our experiment it can be stated, that irrigation and even water supply increased the yield in the average of the examined varieties respectively, and the quality also improved as a result of irrigation.

The protein content of the potato tubers depends on the year effect primarily. The protein content was higher in those years (2004 and 2005) when the summer was rainy during the development of the tubers. In 2006, there was lower precipitation during the summer than in 2004 and 2005, and the protein content was 1.85% under irrigated and 1.87% under non-irrigated cultivations. The difference between the varieties is distinct. The varieties with higher protein content (Rioja, Kuroda) had higher starch content as well, which shows the positive correlation between these two factors (2004: 0.645**, 2006: -0.385*). The protein content is in correlation with the frying quality. The varieties with higher protein content have more favourable frying quality (Kuroda, Rioja varieties).

REFERENCES

- [1] SÁRVÁRI, M. (2001): *A termesztési tényezők hatása a burgonya termésére*. In: Burgonyatermesztés, 2001. augusztus. 21.p.
 - [2] MÉSZÁROS F. (1979): *A burgonya termesztése*. Mezőgazdasági Kiadó Budapest.;
 - [3] A KHEDHER, B. – EWING, E. E. (1985) *Growth analyses of eleven potato cultivars grown in the greenhouse under long photoperiods with and without heat stress*. American potato journal 62. 537-554.p;
 - [4] MARUTANI, M. - CRUZ, F. (1989): *Influence of supplemental irrigation on development of potatoes in the tropics*. HortScience 24 6 (1989), pp. 920–9-23;
 - [5] KRUPPA, J. – GYŐRI, Z. – SÁRVÁRI, M.: 2003. *A burgonya minőségét, piacosságát befolyásoló ökológiai és agrotechnikai tényezők*. Burgonyatermesztés. 2003. augusztus. 7-14.p.
 - [6] KRUPPA, J. – ZSOM, E. (2001): *The effect of potassium fertilization on potato yield quality and quantity*. In: Fertilizers in context with resource management in agriculture; volume II. p. 664-670.
 - [7] HORVÁTH, S. (2002): *Analysis of the present status of Hungarian potato production with special regard of its expected competitiveness in the EU*. In: 50 éves az Acta Agronomica Hungarica. 155-160.p.
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EFFECTS OF CROP YEAR AND NUTRIENT SUPPLY ON THE YIELD OF DIFFERENT WINTER WHEAT VARIETIES ON CHERNOZEM SOIL

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Abstract. *The nutrient uptake and fertilizer response of wheat varieties of different genotypes with different dosage of fertilizers was examined in different crop years. In the analyzed crop years we were searching for answers to how different climate and crop year conditions effect the yield. The yield of five winter wheat genotypes was investigated in three different growing seasons on chernozem soil. The results suggest that the genotype and the nutrient supply had a considerable influence on the yield, while the growing season modified the yield in a significant manner.*

Keywords: winter wheat, fertilizer response, effect of season, yield

1. Introduction

According to Harnos and Erdélyi [1], the yields are greatly determined by the temperature and the precipitation. The average temperature of the April-June period and the amount of precipitation from March until June have a great effect on the yield of winter wheat. L-Baekstrom et al. [2] claim that the yield of wheat is determined by the year (precipitation and temperature), the agrotechnique and the nitrogen doses. Gutierrez et al. [3] found differences in yield due to genotype's differences. Different wheat varieties responded to specific environmental factors with different yields [4, 5]. Somnez [6] concluded that the yield and grain protein content were determined by the year, the genotype and the nutrient supply. According to Balla and Veisz [7], in response to higher temperature, wheat turns yellow due to a decrease in the chlorophyll content, which causes a drastic decline in photosynthetic activity. The resulting acceleration of the grain-filling process leads to yield loss in the case of varieties with poor heat stress tolerance.

2. Materials and methods

The long-term experiment was carried out at the Látókép Experimental Station of the Institute of Crop Sciences, University of Debrecen. The experimental station is located 15 km west of Debrecen in the Hajdúság. The soil of the experiment is calcareous chernozem and can be classified into the loam category, its pH is near neutral and it has medium humus content.

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The long-term experiment was set up in 1983. Our study contains the results of the period 2010-2012. The small-plot field experiment was set up in a split-split-spot design in four replications. Six fertilization levels were applied in the treatments. In addition to the control, the basic dosage of $N=30 \text{ kg ha}^{-1}$, $P_2O_5=22.5 \text{ kg ha}^{-1}$ and $K_2O=26.5 \text{ kg ha}^{-1}$ and 2-,3-, 4- and 5-fold dosages were applied. The total P and K dosages were applied in the autumn, 50% and 50 % of the N fertilizer dosages were applied in the autumn and in the spring. The forecrop was sweet maize.

In the experiment five different genotypes of winter wheat were examined: GK Öthalom, Lupus, Pannonikus, Mv Toldi, Genius.

Due to the dry weather of the first half of October in crop years 2009/2010, wheat sprouted very slowly, its shooting remained heterogeneous (Table 1). From mid-October precipitation was above average, and temperatures were favorable for development and firming of the wheat stands.

Table 1) Main meteorological data of the tested crop years (Debrecen, 2010-2012)

	Oct.	Nov.	Dec.	Jan.	Feb.	Marc.	Apr.	May	Jun.	Total/ Average
Precipitation (mm) 2009/2010	79.3	78.3	54.9	48.8	58.6	14.4	83.9	111.4	100.9	630.5
30 year's average	30.8	45.2	43.5	37.0	30.2	33.5	42.4	58.8	79.5	400.9
Difference	+48.5	+33.1	+11.4	+11.8	+28.4	-19.1	+41.5	+52.6	+21.4	+229.6
Precipitation (mm) 2010/2011	22.8	52.9	104.2	19.2	16.8	35.1	15.6	52.3	22.0	340.9
30 year's average	30.8	45.2	43.5	37.0	30.2	33.5	42.4	58.8	79.5	400.9
Difference	-8.0	+7.7	+60.7	-17.8	-13.4	+1.6	-26.8	-6.5	-57.5	-60.0
Precipitation (mm) 2011/2012	18.1	0.0	71.1	28.0	17.8	1.4	20.7	71.9	91.7	320.7
30 year's average	30.8	45.2	43.5	37.0	30.2	33.5	42.4	58.8	79.5	400.9
Difference	-12.7	-45.2	+27.6	-9.0	-12.4	-32.1	-21.7	+13.1	+12.2	-80.2
Temperature (°C) 2009/2010	11.4	7.6	2.3	-1.1	0.5	7.6	11.6	16.6	19.7	8.47
30 year's average	10.3	4.5	-0.2	-2.6	0.2	5.0	10.7	15.8	18.8	6.94
Difference	+1.1	+3.1	+2.5	+1.5	+0.3	+2.6	+0.9	+0.8	+0.9	+1.5
Temperature (°C) 2010/2011	6.9	7.7	-1.7	-1.2	-2.5	5.0	12.2	16.4	20.5	7.03
30 year's average	10.3	4.5	-0.2	-2.6	0.2	5.0	10.7	15.8	18.8	6.94
Difference	-3.4	+3.2	-1.5	+1.4	-2.7	0.0	+1.5	+0.6	+1.7	+0.1
Temperature (°C) 2011/2012	8.6	0.6	1.5	-0.6	-5.7	6.3	11.7	16.4	20.9	6.6
30 year's average	10.3	4.5	-0.2	-2.6	0.2	5.0	10.7	15.8	18.8	6.9
Difference	-1.7	-3.9	+1.7	+2.0	-5.9	+1.3	+1.0	+0.6	+2.1	-0.3

This favorable weather continued also in November and December. In January and February, the amount of precipitation exceeded and average temperature was milder than the average of many years. Precipitation was less only in March. During the months in the spring and the summer, the considerable amount of precipitation had a negative effect for the generative processes of winter wheat, and it caused significant extent of lodging and yield loss. 229.6 mm more rain fell than the average of many years (400.9 mm), and the average temperature of the growing season was 1.5 °C higher than the average of many years (6.9 °C).

In crop year 2010/2011, due to the colder weather in October, shooting of winter wheat stands was drawling, but the warmer weather in November had a positive impact on the development of the stand. The snow provided enough protection against winter frosts for wheat stands. The favorable warm spring weather had positive impact on the stands, and accelerated their growth. The low rainfall in June had an adverse effect on grain filling processes. In early July, rainy and cool weather helped the translocation processes, but had delayed the harvest. 60 mm less rain fell than the average of many years (400.9 mm), and the temperature of the growing season was 0.1 °C higher than the average of many years (6.9 °C).

Crop year 2011/2012 was extreme for winter wheat production. Due to dry months of October and November in 2011, shooting and initial development became drawling. In the wetter winter months, winter wheat varieties were able to gain strength, but the subsequent dry and warmer than average spring had a negative impact on vegetative development of wheat. In early summer, May and June, the rainfall and favorable temperatures positively affected the grain filling processes. 80.2 mm less rain fell than the average of many years (400.9 mm), and average temperature of the growing season was 0.3 °C lower than the average of many years (6.9 °C).

The experimental data were evaluated by programmes Microsoft Excel 2013, and SPSS 24.0 for Windows. Results were analyzed by two-way analysis of variance based on the method of Sváb (1981). Impact of genotype, nutrient management and crop year on yield was determined by partitioning variance components.

3. Results

In crop years 2009/2010 the lowest yield was gained from varieties GK Öthalom (2896 kg ha⁻¹) and Lupus (3110 kg ha⁻¹), while with varieties Pannonikus (3850 kg ha⁻¹) and Mv Toldi (3812 kg ha⁻¹) good yield was measured (Table 2). In the control treatment, variety Genius (4275 kg ha⁻¹) had the maximum yield. Maximum yields were realized at lower nutrient levels. The optimal nutrient level in case of varieties GK Öthalom (5175 kg ha⁻¹), Lupus (5675 kg ha⁻¹) and Mv Toldi (5196 kg ha⁻¹) was N₆₀+PK. In case of Pannonikus (5271 kg ha⁻¹) and Genius (5986 kg ha⁻¹) dose of N₃₀+PK was the best in crop year 2010. In crop

year 2010/2011 in the control plots variety Genius (4019 kg ha⁻¹) had also good results as well as variety Pannonikus. Lupus (3102 kg ha⁻¹), GK Öthalom (3019 kg ha⁻¹) and Mv Toldi (3316 kg ha⁻¹) had low average yield. The lowest maximum yield (6150 kg ha⁻¹) was obtained with variety Lupus at N₉₀+PK nutrient level. Variety GK Öthalom also had low yield maximum (6819 kg ha⁻¹), variety Mv Toldi reached good yield maximum (7620 kg ha⁻¹). The highest maximum yields were reached with Pannonikus (8224 kg ha⁻¹) at N₁₂₀+PK nutrient level, and with variety Genius (8462 kg ha⁻¹) at optimal nutrient level (N₁₅₀+PK).

Table 2) Effect of year and fertilization on the yields (kg ha⁻¹) in the long-term experiment (Debrecen, 2010-2012)

Crop year	Variety	GK Öthalom	Lupus	Pannonikus	Mv Toldi	Genius	Average
	Treatment	Yield kg ha ⁻¹					
2010	<i>Control</i>	2986	3110	3850	3812	4275	3607
	<i>N₃₀+PK</i>	4750	5250	5271	4576	5986	5167
	<i>N₆₀+PK</i>	5175	5675	4779	5196	5550	5275
	<i>N₉₀+PK</i>	4680	5350	4103	5013	4972	4824
	<i>N₁₂₀+PK</i>	4375	5476	3725	4850	4796	4644
	<i>N₁₅₀+PK</i>	3429	5063	3561	4927	4600	4316
	<i>Average</i>	4233	4987	4215	4729	5030	-
		LSD _{5%} Genotype 177		LSD _{5%} Fertilization 179		LSD _{5%} Interaction 401	
2011	<i>Control</i>	3019	3102	4719	3316	4019	3635
	<i>N₃₀+PK</i>	4682	3814	5927	4542	5436	4880
	<i>N₆₀+PK</i>	5745	4873	7072	6119	6717	6105
	<i>N₉₀+PK</i>	6172	6150	8123	6526	7105	6815
	<i>N₁₂₀+PK</i>	6500	5902	8224	6938	7736	7060
	<i>N₁₅₀+PK</i>	6819	5718	7692	7620	8462	7262
	<i>Average</i>	5490	4927	6960	5844	6579	-
		LSD _{5%} Genotype 250		LSD _{5%} Fertilization 230		LSD _{5%} Interaction 514	
2012	<i>Control</i>	3176	3132	4210	3607	3610	3547
	<i>N₃₀+PK</i>	4513	4610	5303	5676	5751	5171
	<i>N₆₀+PK</i>	5360	5427	6650	6163	6642	6048
	<i>N₉₀+PK</i>	5548	5688	6925	6307	6804	6254
	<i>N₁₂₀+PK</i>	5810	6129	7880	6509	7127	6691
	<i>N₁₅₀+PK</i>	6175	6408	8139	6868	7209	6960
	<i>Average</i>	5097	5232	6518	5855	6191	-
		LSD _{5%} Genotype 246		LSD _{5%} Fertilization 250		LSD _{5%} Interaction 558	

In crop year 2011/2012, varieties Lupus (3132 kg ha⁻¹) and GK Öthalom (3176 kg ha⁻¹) had the lowest control yield. Mv Toldi (3607 kg ha⁻¹) and Genius (3610 kg ha⁻¹) had nearly the same average yield. The highest yield in the control plots was achieved by variety Pannonikus (4210 kg ha⁻¹). The lowest yield maximum was gained with GK Öthalom (6175 kg ha⁻¹). Lupus (6408 kg ha⁻¹) and Mv Toldi

(6868 kg ha⁻¹) reached a medium yield maximum. The best yields also in this crop year were achieved by Pannonikus (7880 kg ha⁻¹) and the Genius (7127 kg ha⁻¹) at N₁₂₀+PK nutrient level.

Evaluating the three crop years together (Table 3), in average of the varieties it can be concluded that natural nutrient assimilation capacity of the varieties was the best in 2011 (3635 kg ha⁻¹), while the relatively lowest average yield (3547 kg ha⁻¹) was gained in the control treatment in 2012.

Table 3) Effects of fertilization on the yield and the fertilizer utilization capacity in the average of varieties (Debrecen, 2010-2012)

Crop year	Control kg ha ⁻¹	Maximum yield kg ha ⁻¹	Yield increment kg ha ⁻¹	NPK dose of maximum yield	Specific surplus of max. yield kg
2010	3607	5461	1854	<i>N₃₀₋₆₀+PK</i>	15.70
2011	3635	7455	3820	<i>N₉₀₋₁₅₀+PK</i>	11.14
2012	3547	6960	3413	<i>N₁₂₀₋₁₅₀+PK</i>	13.42
Average	3596	6625	3029	--	13.42

The varieties reached the lowest maximum yield (5461 kg ha⁻¹) in rainy year 2010, while the best yield (7455 kg ha⁻¹) could be measured again in the average crop year 2011. Yield increment of the varieties was the lowest in 2010 (1854 kg ha⁻¹), it was moderate in 2012 (3413 kg ha⁻¹), while in 2011 it was the highest (3820 kg ha⁻¹). The optimal levels of nutrient supply was low (N₃₀₋₆₀+PK) in 2010, then due to the extreme wet weather, in 2011, they varied between N₉₀₋₁₅₀+PK levels, while in 2012, this level was N₁₂₀₋₁₅₀+PK, probably due to the lower fertilizer utilization caused by draught and disturbances in nutrient uptake caused by water shortages.

The yield increment per applied 1 kg of NPK active ingredient was the highest (15.70 kg) in 2010, it was medium (11.14 kg) in 2011, and it was the lowest (8.64 kg) in 2012.

Analyzing the nutritional response of varieties in three-year average (Figure 1) it can be concluded that varieties can be classified into two groups. GK Óthalom, Lupus and Mv Toldi had a poor response to extreme and different crop years, they performed a poor natural nutrient utilization and weak capability of fertilizer utilization. In contrast, varieties Genius and Pannonikus had a good natural nutrient utilization character and had good response to fertilizers in each of the three years, in spite of varying crop year effects.

Fig. 1. Types of nutrient response of the examined winter wheat genotypes in the average of the three crop years (Debrecen, 2010-2012)

By dividing of variance components, we were able to accurately quantify the effect of the crop year, the genotype and the nutrient supply to the harvested yield. To determine the significance of the studied factors, we took the minimum values measured on control nutrient levels as a base, and we divided the increase belonged to maximum values reached with the combination of the analyzed parameters among the analyzed factors.

In 2010, in the control treatment, the average yield was 3607 kg ha⁻¹ the average of maximum yields was 5461 kg ha⁻¹, which was 1856 kg ha⁻¹ yield increment (Figure 2). 71% of the yield increment was due to genotype, which was 1316 kg ha⁻¹ increase in yield. The nutrient supply contributed to the increase in only 29% (538 kg ha⁻¹). The minor role of nutrition can be explained by the low yield maximums due to extreme amount of precipitation in crop year 2010, and varieties reach the highest yield at N₃₀₋₆₀+PK nutrient levels. The more considerable role of genotype expressed in percentage proved that to achieve higher maximum yields the varieties had to have good ability to adapt (better endurance against lodging and diseases) to extreme environmental conditions. In average crop year 2011, average of the control treatments was 3635 kg ha⁻¹, while average of maximum yields was 7455 kg ha⁻¹, which gave 3820 kg ha⁻¹ yield increment. In this year, the genotype caused 25% (972 kg ha⁻¹), but the nutrient supply contributed to 75% (2848 kg ha⁻¹) of production of yield increment. The result can be explained by the fact that the in average crop year not that ability of varieties to adapt but their better nutrient response played a greater role in yield increment production. In 2012, average of the harvested yield was 3547 kg ha⁻¹ in

the control plots, while the average of maximum yields was 6960 kg ha⁻¹, i.e. 3413 kg ha⁻¹ yield increment was gained. The genotype resulted 26% (904 kg ha⁻¹), while nutrient treatment caused 74%, which equals 2509 kg ha⁻¹, of formation of the yield increment. Also in 2012, the nutrient response affected more significantly the production of yield increment, due to the fact that nutrients distributed in the drier spring period of 2012, was solubilized to a lesser extent.

Fig. 2. The significance of the studied factors in determining yield of the winter wheat (Debrecen, 2010-2012)

Evaluating the three crop years together, in the control plots, the average yield was 3596 kg ha⁻¹, the maximum yield in average of the varieties was 6625 kg, which gave 3029 kg ha⁻¹ yield increment. The genotype caused 22% (661 kg ha⁻¹), the nutrient supply contributed to 52% (1588 kg ha⁻¹), and the crop year resulted 26% (780 kg ha⁻¹) of production of yield increment. The fact that the three distinct and rich in extreme effects crop year had a slighter influence on production of yield increment shows the good ability of the varieties to adapt. The high percentage of the contribution of nutrient supply to the formation of yield increment shows that in order to achieve high yields, even regardless of the crop year, it is important to ensure adequate supply of nutrients. 26% of contribution of genotypes showed that to gain high yields, good biological base and nutritional response is essential.

Conclusions

The results suggest that genotype and nutrient supply had considerable influence on yield, while the season modified the investigated parameters in significant manner. The large amount of precipitation is the most harmful, compared to the average crop year, varieties achieved 1994 kg ha⁻¹ lower yield, and the optimum dose of nutrients was formed at N₃₀₋₆₀ + PK nutrient levels. During the average year (2011) the varieties produced highest yields at both the control (3635 kg ha⁻¹) and N₉₀₋₁₅₀+PK levels (7455 kg ha⁻¹). The effect of drought could be reduced with proper nutrient treatment, 495 kg ha⁻¹ decrease in yield was observed at N₁₂₀₋₁₅₀+PK nutrient level. The optimal dose of fertilizer was determined by amount of precipitation of the crop year. The unfavorable effect of the crop year could be reduced with proper nutrient treatment. In the wet crop year, lower doses of fertilizer cause lower yield increase (1854 kg ha⁻¹). In average crop year, N₉₀₋₁₅₀+PK nutrient doses proved to be optimal (3820 kg ha⁻¹). In the drier crop year, the N₁₂₀₋₁₅₀+PK nutrient dose proved to be optimal to counteract the negative crop year effect. The Genius and Pannonikus varieties have good nutrient utilization ability and fertilizer response, even in spite of varying crop year effects. In the average of the three examined crop year, in the development of yield increment, the genotype took part in 22%, the nutrient supply participated in it up to 52%, and the crop year increased the yield in 26%.

REFERENCES

- [1] Harnos N., Erdélyi É.: 2011. *Sustainable wheat production in a changing climate*. Acta Agronomica Hungarica, 59. 3. 261–266
 - [2] L-Baekstrom, G. Lundegardh, B. Hanell, U.: 2006. *The interactions between nitrogen dose, year and stage of ripeness on nitrogen and trace element concentrations and seed-borne pathogens in organic and conventional wheat*. Journal of the Science of Food and Agriculture, 86.15. 2560-2578.
 - [3] Gutierrez, M., Reynolds, M. P., Raun, W. R., Stone, M. L., Klatt, A. R. (2010): *Spectral water indices for assessing yield in elite bread wheat genotypes under well-irrigated, water-stressed, and high-temperature conditions*. Crop Sci., 50, 197–213.
 - [4] Mengistu, N., Baenziger, P. S., Nelson, L. A., Eskridge, K. M., Klein, R. N., Baltensperger, D. D., Elmore, R. W. (2010): *Grain yield performance and stability of cultivar blends vs. component cultivars of hard winter wheat in Nebraska*. Crop Sci., 50, 617–623.
 - [5] Borghi, B., Corbellini, M., Minoia, C., Palumbo, M., Di Fonzo, N., Perenzin, M. (1997): *Effects of Mediterranean climate on wheat bread-making quality*. Eur. J. Agron., 6, 145–154.
 - [6] Sonmez, F. (2007): *Effect of nitrogenous fertilizer on grain yield and grain protein concentration in winter wheat*. Asian J. Chem., 19, 256–260.
 - [7] Balla, K., Veisz, O. (2008): *Temperature dependence of wheat development*. Acta Agron. Hung., 56, 313–320.
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INVESTIGATION OF SOYBEAN PRODUCTION WITH MICROBIOLOGICAL PREPARATION ON THE SOIL, IN WEST HUNGARIAN REGION

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Abstract. *More and more research is conducted, how to reduce nitrogen, phosphorus and potassium fertilizer use in crop production. Application of soil replacement products are becoming too often in Hungary. In the experiment, we get a nearer view of a neutral microbial soil preparation in soybean production and the development of nitrogen-fixing nodule, the content of chlorophyll and after harvest the plants yield and contents. The soil suspension composition may exert both positive and negative effects, which depends on what has been combined with bacterial strains of soybean seed. We searched for the operating trial to answer to how changes in the treated soil the soybean production relative to the control.*

Keywords: soybean, microbiological preparation, nitrogen-fixing, nodule

1. Introduction

The agricultural aid due increased to the soybean area in Hungary, between in 2015-2016. In order ensure a higher level of production, more and more company will hold to the farmer's soybean roadshow, which demonstrate the characteristics of the varieties and the minimum agronomic conditions. More and more farmers are using a variety of additional bacteria manure in crop production, in hopes to grow the yield (M. Miransari, 2015). The foliage manure or manure on soil bacteria is not an increase in the yield, but speed the plough the stress tolerance of plants to changing climate conditions. Number of studies demonstrate that foliage manure or soil bacteria manure will be reduced to drought stress and torridity days when using the plants (J. G. Streeter, 2002, D. B. Lobell et al., 2007, J.H.G. Stephens et al., 2000). However, most of the enterprise purpose is not the protection, but also to increase the yield. In the field trial experiment, we tried modeling the farmers thought, to see how we could even help the better yield (E. A. Ampofo et al., 2016, E. L. Piper et al., 1999).

2. Material and Methods

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The field trial experiment was in Mosonudvar, Győr-Moson-Sopron county, Hungary. The soil is sandy-loam region, good water management, nitrogen and phosphorus content was medium, and low potassium levels, pH is 7,55, humus content 1,62. Nutrient supply was 300 kg/ha 7-20-30 npk fertilizer and the experimental area of 20 hectares. After selecting the experimental area, determined by dividing the border and outwork the soil bacteria is one of the five-acre parcel (Figure 1). The field trial applied a very early and high yield as well as protein content soybean variety. We examined based on the BBCH Scale in the following phases: 21-23 (two times), 51-59, 70-79. The development of nodules in appreciable soybean growing therefore we measured all the four phases of the treated and untreated surfaces. The SPAD values amply demonstrated the activity of nodules, because the SPAD values were higher, though this was not accompanied by a high nodules numbers. We investigated number of nodules and SPAD value addition to the yield and composition content (humidity, protein- and oil content).

Fig. 1. field trial in Mosonudvar, 2016.

Chlorophyll Meter SPAD-502Plus:

The SPAD-502Plus enables quick, easy measurement of the chlorophyll content of plant leaves without damaging the leaf. Chlorophyll content is one indicator of plant health, and can be used to optimize the timing and quantity of applying additional fertilizer to provide larger crop yields of higher quality with lower environmental load.

Mininfra smart:

Mininfra instruments are scanning spectrophotometers operating in the Near Infrared (NIR) wavelength range. Mininfra grain analysers are transmission mode (NIT – Near Infrared Transmission) instruments that apply light of 780-1064nm wavelength for the measurement because grains and flour transmit this type of light in a measurable extent. The instrument trans-illuminates the material to be

analysed and measures the intensity (spectrum) of the transmitted light at several wavelengths. The measurement of the spectrum is done at some selected wavelengths: the light of these wavelengths are produced by a so called grating monochromator.

Statistical analysis:

The statistical analysis of variance analysis (SPSS) was used and accepted as significant difference in P levels in case of 0.05 met.

Results:

In the first survey has measured the nodules number (phase 21-23) (Table 1) the control field was higher than on the treated soil. We dug 10 plants per field trial, after that cleaned and counted in the lab the nodules. The treated soil does not always occur immediately positive effect, hence the importance of continuous monitoring.

Table 1) First nodule survey in field trial, Mosonudvar, 2016.

<i>Phase: 21-23</i>		
<i>Nodules numbers pro plants</i>		
<i>date</i>	<i>Control</i>	<i>Treated soil</i>
06.06.2016.	11	4
	18	3
	9	8
	4	4
	11	3
	5	3
	2	3
	11	2
	11	4
	7	5
Average	9 *	4

remarks: * significant difference p<0,05

The second survey has been seen the beneficial influence bacteria manure. We dug out 10 plants pro area again, thereupon cleaning and calculated the nodules in the lab (Table 2). The treated area was more crops with nodules, such as control area, but no significant differences can be found between the two treatments. Therefore, we started to measure the SPAD value and we trust that found of difference between the treated and untreated areas. The third survey has marked the 10 selected samples, measured the SPAD value, and then dug up the plants

and counted the nodules in the laboratory (Table 3-4). We were found significant differences between the control and the treated area in phase 51-59. Higher nodules number and SPAD value get by treated area. It is clear, that the preparation of the soil began take to the effect and help the crop to the yield increase in July. The last measurement was the beginning of maturation (phase 70-79). The plants began to air dry, so it was even more interesting to examine the content of chlorophyll. We found high nodules numbers and get by higher the SPAD value in the treatment area, in the control nodules started to die away and the chlorophyll content was less well (Table 5-6). The harvest already knew that bacteria in the manure area to receive a higher yield than the control because previous studies support this. The spectacular difference behindhand by the yield. The experiment proved that the use of bacteria in large quantities of manure does not increase the yield (Table 7). The moisture and protein content of the treated soil was favorable. The protein was significantly higher compared in the treated soil than the control, which is important component for the processing industry.

Table 2) Second nodule survey in field trial, Mosonudvar, 2016.

<i>Phase: 21-23</i>		
<i>Nodules numbers</i>		
<i>date</i>	<i>Control</i>	<i>Treated soil</i>
24.06.2016.	1	7
	0	4
	0	5
	0	8
	0	1
	1	3
	2	2
	5	4
	2	2
	2	1
Average	1	4

Table 3) Third nodule survey in field trial, Mosonudvar, 2016.

<i>Phase: 51-59</i>		
<i>Nodules numbers</i>		
<i>date</i>	<i>Control</i>	<i>Treated soil</i>
21.07.2016.	1	23
	1	2
	0	5
	0	12
	0	0
	4	22
	4	7
	4	4
	5	4
	0	18
Average	2	10 *

remarks: * significant difference $p < 0,05$

Table 4) SPAD-value at the end of flowering, Mosonudvar, 2016.

<i>Phase: 51-59</i>		
<i>SPAD value</i>		
<i>date</i>	<i>Control</i>	<i>Treated soil</i>
21.07.2016.	51.92	50.72
	51.01	51.07
	46.67	49.3
	49.88	51.49
	47.61	48.85
	42.87	50.28
	45.03	52.87
	46.79	51.9
	43.98	51.91
	48.38	48.95
Average	47.41	50.73 *

remarks: * significant difference $p < 0.05$

Table 5) Fourth nodule survey in field trial, Mosonudvar, 2016.

<i>Phase: 70-79</i>		
<i>Nodules numbers</i>		
<i>date</i>	<i>Control</i>	<i>Treated soil</i>
23.08.2016.	31	11
	21	22
	14	18
	0	19
	0	15
	2	9
	2	11
	17	12
	9	16
	12	30
Average	11	16 *

remarks: * significant difference $p < 0.05$

Table 6) SPAD -value at early ripening, Mosonudvar, 2016.

<i>Phase: 70-79</i>		
<i>SPAD value</i>		
<i>date</i>	<i>Control</i>	<i>Treated soil</i>
23.08.2016.	12.5	30.53
	14.89	30.96
	42.18	37.96
	39.42	42.66
	16.06	44.39
	29.03	35.94
	32.87	38.99
	31.39	34.89
	34.14	31.0
	31.04	37.43
Average	28.35	36.48 *

remarks: * significant difference $p < 0.05$

Table 7) Values measured after harvest (yield, moisture, protein, oil content), Mosonudvar, 2016.

	<i>Yield (t/ha)</i>	<i>Moisture (%)</i>	<i>Protein content (%)</i>	<i>Oil content (%)</i>
<i>Control</i>	4.29	12.05	33.65	19.10
<i>Treated soil</i>	4.11	11.25	35.63*	18.23

remarks: * significant difference $p < 0.05$

Conclusions

The area was good to the soybean product in 2016. Right time, sufficient rainfall fell (575 mm), which has been good for the ripening. Average crop yield of 3.5-4 t/ha was in 2016. We measured on the heat days the chlorophyll content and thanks to microbiological preparation the values were better than control field. The area with microbial preparation can be said that a nitrogen-fixing bacteria to a slow start at the cross-contamination, but then continuously has been increased the numbers of nodules. The control area of the plants can be said that highly variable was the number of nodules and even during maturation, we found the plant that was not nodules. It is apparent that the bacteria manure do not cause the increased yield but improves at harvest the moisture content and the protein content. Most inoculum on the market has a reliable number of bacteria, which helps the formation of nodules in the main roots. The experiment based on better help the soybeans of the soil bacterial manure during the growing season, which is the future of the yield and content also seen. In order to achieve safe yield of the seed put out fungicidal necessary, but important for the green crops and the corresponding nutrient supply as well.

REFERENCES

- [1] M. Miransari, *Abiotic and Biotic Stresses in Soybean Production: Soybean Production*, eBook ISBN:9780128017302 (2015).
- [2] J. G. Streeter, *Effects of drought on nitrogen fixation in soybean root nodules*, Plant, Cell and Environment, 26, 1199 (2003).
- [3] D. B. Lobell, C. B. Field, *Global scale climate–crop yield relationships and the impacts of recent warming*, IOP Publishing, Environmental Research Letters, 1 (2007).
- [4] J.H.G. Stephens, H.M. Rask, *Inoculant production and formulation*, Field Crops Research, 65, 249 (2000).
- [5] E. A. Ampofo, P. K. Kwakye, K. A. Frimpong, A. Alwa, *Irrigation and Bradyrhizobium Japonicum Inoculation Effects on Performance of Soybean Production in Tropical Guinea Savanna Zone of Ghana*, Journal of Natural Sciences Research, 6, 32 (2016).

THE EFFECT OF THE CROP YEAR AND THE AGROTECHNICAL FACTORS ON THE YIELD STABILITY OF MAIZE

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Abstract. In our research we examined the effect of the hybrid, the nutrient supply, the number of plants and the abiotic factors (temperature, amount of precipitation) on the yield, crop quality and yield stability of maize. We devoted special attention to the natural nutrient utilization ability and fertilizer reaction of maize. We tested six hybrids with different genetic characteristics and growing seasons. I analysed the correlation between the nutrient supply and the yield of maize hybrids with control treatment (treatment without fertilisation) and with N 80, P₂O₅ 60, K₂O 70 kg ha⁻¹ and N 160, P₂O₅ 120, K₂O 140 kg ha⁻¹ fertilizer treatments. Yield increasing effect of the fertilizer also depended on the number of plants per hectare at a great extent. The number of plants of the six tested hybrids was 60, 70, and 80 thousand plants/ha. The six tested hybrids is 10.65 t ha⁻¹ in the average of the stand density of 60, 70 and 80 thousand plants per hectare without fertilisation, while it is 12.24 t ha⁻¹ with N80+PK fertilizer treatment. That increase in the yield is 1.6 t ha⁻¹, it is significant. In average, the yield of maize was 6.81 t ha⁻¹ in 2015, which was a drought year and 11.86 t ha⁻¹ in 2016 that was a favourable year.

Keywords: maize, nutrient supply, number of plants, hybrid

1. Introduction,

Maize is one of the most important plants of humankind. It is easy to produce, it can be diversely used, it has a high yield potential, it is our most significant export item and main cereal crop. The crop year of 2016 was favourable for stoop crops, thus for maize as well. The distribution of precipitation was especially advantageous. In 2016 the total yield of maize on 947000 ha exceeded 9.2 million tonnes, which is a domestic average yield of more than 8.6 t/ha. This figure highly exceeds the domestic average yield of 5.7 t/ha of 2015, which can be explained by the effect of the crop year. The yield results of the last 2 years excellently demonstrate the extent of the fluctuation in yield, which reached even 50-60% in the past 20 years. The aim of my research is to decrease fluctuation of yields and to reach a higher yield. To achieve that, to choose the proper hybrids and to apply modern, balanced, hybrid-specific agrotechnique are essential.

To increase yield stability the adverse effects of the weather can be reduced by choosing hybrids adjusted to the place of production and with application of the

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right hybrid-specific agrotechnique which meets the needs of the plant [1]. In the production of modern hybrids chosen for the given ecological conditions, the adequate level of inputs and to ensure balanced NPK fertilisation and effective plant protection are important [2].

According to Marton's [3] experiments, in optimum conditions, the yield of new hybrids is not higher than or just hardly exceeds that of the older hybrids. Compared to the older hybrids, their advantageous characteristics are proved mainly in conditions of stress. He examined hybrids in dry and irrigated conditions, and he detected more genetic progress in adverse conditions.

According to Sárvári's [4] experiments, the agroecological fertilizer dosage is 80-120 kg/ha nitrogen with proportionate amount of phosphorous and potassium. In the future, those hybrids can gain more ground which adjust well to an environmentally friendly and cost-effective production technology, thus the ones that have good natural nutrient usage and fertilizer response [5]. Nagy's [6] research results of decades show that the crop year, specifically the precipitation, significantly affects the fertilizer response of maize hybrids.

During the analysis of the results of his experiments conducted over many years Sárvári [7] concluded that with increasing the number of plants with 10000 plants/ha, yield can increase with 1.5-2 t/ha in favourable conditions, while in dry environment it can decrease by the same quantity. Berzsenyi et. al. [8] analysing the results of more than 10 years (1981-1992), found that in the average of rainy years the optimum number of plants was 80000 plants/ha, when the yield reach 8.2 t/ha. In the average of dry years, the optimum number of plants was 50000 plants/ha, which resulted in a yield of 6.6 t/ha. With increasing the number of plants, the ratio of infertile plants exponentially increased, and the number of inclined plants showed a linear decrease. During the examinations of the yield stability, it turned out that with increasing the stand density up to 60000 plants/ha the yield was gradually increasing, while above that number of plants the yield decreased. The yield, in the average of 22 years (taking weather conditions into account), was the most stable with 60000 plants/ha.

According to Sárvári and Bene [9], for the modern hybrid-specific nutrient supply it is essential to find the NPK fertilizer dosages that are optimal for the plants. That can be supported by soil analysis and results of field experiments. In the preparation of the fertilization plan, besides the nutrient content of the soil, the plant species, the nutrient requirements of the variety/hybrid, its yield potential, the aim of production, quality requirements, the cultivation conditions of the soil, the date of spreading and the dosage of livestock manure, the intensity of production technology and the irrigation facilities should also be taken into consideration.

According to the experiments of Zoltán and Jakab [10], we need to have information on the nutrient content of the soil, and have to try to supply nutrients which are in minimum quantity, because with that the efficiency of production can the most easily be increased.

2. Material and method

Our experiment took place in Hajdúszoboszló on on calcareous chernozem soil, on a nearly 8 ha land. The size of one plot was 206 m². We tested six hybrids with different genetic characteristics and growing seasons. Sowing took place on 23 April 2016, the crop was harvested on 5 November. The correlation between the nutrient supply and the yield of maize hybrids was analysed with control treatment (treatment without fertilization) and with N 80, P₂O₅ 60, K₂O 70 kg/ha and N 160, P₂O₅ 120, K₂O 140 kg/ha fertilizer treatments. In my experiment, the same fertilizer dosages have been applied for the 2nd year now (it is not a long-term experiment). The yield increasing effect of the NPK fertilizer depended also on the number of plants per hectare at a great extent. The plant number of the six tested hybrids was 60, 70, 80 thousand plants/ha.

In our research, we analysed the effect of the hybrid, the nutrient supply, the number of plants and the abiotic factors (temperature, precipitation) on the yield, yield quality and yield stability. The natural capability of nutrient intake and usage and the fertilizer response of maize were expressed in numbers.

Fig. 7. The weather in Hajdúszoboszló, 2016

In 2016 the crop year was favourable for stoop crops. The distribution of precipitation was especially advantageous. Due to climate changes, mainly in summer months, the amount of rain decreases. But in 2016, in contrast with the previous year, June and July were rainy, which increased the yield and yield stability of maize. In Hajdúszoboszló, in 2016, the total amount of rain from

January to October was 605 mm which is more by 160mm than the average of 30 years (see Figure 1). Except for April, in each month, the amount of precipitation was above the average. It was especially ideal that also in the period of flowering, fertilization and grain filling plenty of water was available. It considerably contributed to the outstanding yield results.

3. Results

Figures 2, 3, 4, clearly show the effect of the treatments and the differences in the yield potential of the different hybrids. In the average of the number of plants, without fertilizer treatments the hybrids produced 9.6-11.6 t/ha yield, where the Kamaria and the P9486 hybrids were outstanding: produced a yield of more than 11 t/ha with control treatment and 80000 plants/ha (see Figure 2). The modern hybrids have a very good capability of natural soil nutrient intake and usage, which is a genetically heritable characteristic.

Fig. 8. The effect of the increase of the number of plants on the yield of maize hybrids (control), Hajdúszoboszló, 2016

Note: LSD_{5%} number of plants: 0.15 t/ha, hybrid: 0.22 t/ha, correlation: 0.38 t/ha

The analysis of the effect of increasing the number of plants revealed the following results: the yield with a stand density of 60000 plants/ha was 11.4 t/ha, with a plant number increase of 10000 it was 11.79 t/ha, and it was 12.38 t/ha with the highest number of plants of 80000 plants/ha. It means that increasing the number of plants from 60000 to 70000 produces a yield increase of 0.4 t/ha, and further increase in the plant number resulted in 0.6 t/ha yield increase. Thus, if we applied a stand density of 80000 plants/ha instead of 60000 plants/ha, I measured 1 t/ha yield increase. Of course, it was caused mainly by the favourable weather conditions.

Based on the results of the examinations it can be considered, that the hybrids produced the highest yield with the N160+PK treatment and with a stand density of 80000 plants/ha (see Figure 3). This confirms that interactions are close also between the agrotechnical factors. Provided that the water supply is adequate, the correlation between the hybrid, the nutrient supply and the number of plants is very strong and positive.

Fig. 9. The effect of the increase of the number of plants on the yield of maize hybrids (N160+PK), Hajdúszoboszló, 2016

Note: LSD_{5%} number of plants: 0.15 t/ha, hybrid: 0.22 t/ha, correlation: 0.38 t/ha

The effect of fertilizers excellently predominated in 2016. Compared to the N₈₀+PK treatment, the N₁₆₀+PK kg/ha treatment also significantly increased the yield (see Figure 4). Compared to the control treatment (10.65 t/ha), the N₈₀+PK treatment (12.24 t/ha) increased the yield by 1.6 t/ha, while the N₁₆₀+PK treatment (12.69 t/ha) increased it by further 0.6 t/ha, in the average of the hybrids and numbers of plants. With N₁₆₀+PK treatment the highest yield (13.48-13.81 t/ha) was produced by hybrids Kamaria, Da Sonka, P9486 and P924, with 80000 plants/ha. The maximum yield in 2016 was reached by the Kamaria hybrid, which produced 13.81 t/ha yield with N₁₆₀+PK treatment and with 80000 plants/ha.

It can be concluded that the lowest yield was produced by the Kenéz hybrid with all the treatments. With the adequate nutrient supply, hybrids P9241, DKC 4717 and Kamaria showed the best response to the change in the plant number, which increased their yield. The individual production of those hybrids also developed positively. In 2016 the values of grain moisture content were higher (17-18%). Due to the crop year with above average precipitation, it happened that in some rainy periods not only the daily water release of the grain crop decreased but it became moisty again.

Fig. 10. The effect of NPK fertilizer on the yield of maize hybrids (70000 plants ha⁻¹), Hajdúszoboszló, 2016

Note: LSD_{5%} fertilizer level: 0.17 t/ha, hybrid: 0.24 t/ha, correlation: 0.41 t/ha

Comparing this year's results with the yield results of 2015, quite large differences can be observed. In 2015, also in Hajdúszoboszló, as in the whole country, the weather conditions were very unfavourable for plant production. In the January-October period the amount of precipitation was by 105 mm less than the 30-year average. The most serious problem was that the lower amount of rain fell in the period of flowering and fertilization, the most critical periods for maize.

Fig. 11. Effect of maize genotypes in 2015 year (Hajdúszoboszló, in average of plant density of doses of fertilizers)

The monthly average temperature was higher by 2.6-3.7 °C than the average of many years. In a 40-day period from the end of June, only there was only 8 mm, and only 1-2 mm a day. The number of days of extreme heat was 30, the number of hot days was 15 in that period. In that extreme weather all the leaves of maize under the cobs had dried already by the middle of August. The yield changed

between 6.27 and 7.47 t/ha in the average of fertilizer treatments and plant numbers (see Figure 5). Hybrids DA Sonka and Kenéz had the lowest, while hybrids Kamaria and Pioneer had the highest yield.

In 2016, hybrids Kamaria, DA Sonka and P9486 reached the highest, while hybrid Kenéz had the lowest yield (see Figure 6).

Fig. 12. Effect of maize genotypes in 2016 year (Hajdúszoboszló, in average of plant density of doses of fertilizers)

By comparing those 2 years and ranking the hybrids based on yield results, a number of observations can be made. Hybrid DA Sonka is very sensitive to the weather, compared to draughty years, in favourable conditions it can produce by 6 t/ha more yield, but its stress tolerance is very weak. Hybrids Kamaria and Pioneer had the highest yield stability. In both years, they were among the 3 hybrids that had the best yield results, thus proved that they are able to produce outstanding yield in favourable also in adverse conditions as well.

Conclusions

The crop year has an extremely strong effect on the yield. In the draughty year of 2015, the average yields produced by the hybrids was 6.81 t/ha, while in 2016 it was 11.86 t/ha. The importance of the biological bases is obvious. The performance of hybrid Kamaria and Pioneer hybrids were satisfactory in both years. The adaptability of those hybrids is excellent, they have stronger root system, their anthesis and silking are synchronized, thus flowering takes place at the same time, which results in more secure fertilization.

Based on the results of the 2 years, it can be assessed that the optimum number of plants per hectare is 70 000 plants ha⁻¹. In a favourable year the higher plant number can result in some increase in the yield, but in an unfavourable year it can cause a more considerable loss of production.

Compared to the N80+PK fertilizer dosage, the N160+PK dosage did not bring the expected results. In 2015, as an effect of the higher fertilizer dosage, a depression in yield had occurred, and it decreased by 0.2 t/ha in the average of the hybrids and plant numbers. In 2016 some increase was observed in the yield, but the costs of inputs have not returned. Thus, it can be concluded that the N160+PK fertilizer dosage proved to be too high in my experiment, and to determine the exact optimum fertilizer dosage needs further examinations.

REFERENCES

- [1] P. Pepó, *Fejlesztési alternatívák a magyar kukoricatermesztésben*. Agrofórum Extra, **13**, 7 (2006).
 - [2] M. Sárvári *et al.*, *A biológiai alapok jelentősége a kukoricatermesztésben*. Agrofórum, **17**, 4 (2006).
 - [3] L. Cs. Marton, *A kukorica termésátlagok alakulása a világban és itthon*. Az MTA agrártudományi kutatóközpont közleménye, **26**, 4 (2014).
 - [4] M. Sárvári, *A hatékony trágyázás tényezői a kukoricatermesztésben*. Agrofórum Extra, **57**, 60 (2014).
 - [5] P. Pepó and I. Ruzsányi, *A kukorica hibridspecifikus trágyázása*. Agrofórum Extra, **11**, 51 (2000).
 - [6] J. Nagy, *Versenyképes kukoricatermesztés a szántóföldi gyakorlatban* (Mezőgazda Kiadó, Budapest, 2012) pp. 258-259.
 - [7] M. Sárvári, *Rationalization of Cropping System and Their Effect on The Effective Utilisation of Yield Potential and Quality of Field Crop Production under Sustainable Development*. Slovak-Hungarian Project. (2006) pp. 25-45.
 - [8] Z. Berzsényi *et al.*, *A növényszám és az évjárat hatása a kukorica szemtermésének és terméskomponenseinek alakulására az 1981-1992. években*. Növénytermelés, **1**, 61 (1994).
 - [9] M. Sárvári and E. Bene, *Az NPK tápanyag-gazdálkodás helyzete és fejlesztési lehetőségei termésdepresszió ellen*. Agrárunió, **16**, 38 (2015).
 - [10] G. Zoltán and P. Jakab, *Lombtrágya készítmények hatása a kukorica termésére és beltartalmára*. XXXVI. Óvári Tudományos Nap: *Hagyomány és innováció az agrár-élelmiszergazdaságban, I-II*, 453 (2016).
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SWEET POTATO PRODUCTION ON ALLUVIAL SOIL WITH HIGH CLAY CONTENT

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Abstract. *The comprehensive goals of our research program are to develop the domestic production technology and to examine the possibilities of the utilization of sweet potato. In 2016 we set up a production technology experiment of four repetitions in randomized block design on clay loam soil in Deszk, Hungary. The storage root yields of plants developing from cuttings derived directly from sprouting storage roots (primary cuttings) and from the sprouting of primary cuttings (secondary cuttings) did not show significant differences. On hectare level, however, the differences can reach even as much as 10 tons. The evaluation of the effects of different nutrient doses on the storage root yields did not show significant differences. The reason can be the good nutrient supply of the soil of the experimental fields. Despite the heavy soil where usually ridge planting is preferred, the comparison of planting on ridges and flat proved the production technology without ridges being more effective here.*

Keywords: *Ipomoea batatas*, sweet potato, production technology

1. Introduction

The sweet potato also called batata [*Ipomoea batatas* (L.) Lam.] is a tropical-subtropical plant by the origin, however it has also been grown in temperate climate for centuries. The sweet potato belongs to the Morning glory (*Convolvulaceae*) family and the *Ipomoea* genus [1].

Sweet potato is grown for its storage roots, which are formed by the special thickening of the 2-3 cm roots initiated from the underground part of the stems [2]. The root skin color can be whitish, cream, yellow, orange, brown-orange, pink, red-purple, and very dark purple. The color of the root flesh can be white, cream, yellow, orange or purple. Sweet potato belongs to the traditional cultures in the Southern states of the US (North Carolina, Mississippi, Louisiana, California, Oklahoma, Arkansas, etc.). It is one of the main food crops in Africa and other tropical-subtropical regions, but it can be found anywhere in the world where the climate is suitable [3]. An increasing farmers' and consumers' demand can be observed in the last decades in several European countries. Sweet potato

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production in Spain, Portugal, Italy and Greece is registered in FAO databases [4], however its production is also known from Hungary, Croatia [5, 6, 7], Slovenia [8, 9], Romania [10], Poland [11] and England [12], among others.

Sweet potato is cultivated in Hungary for thirty years [13, 14] but it became well-known and popular in the last years only – thanks to media appearances and its growing commercial availability. It has recently become so popular here that the farmers cannot produce enough sweet potatoes to fill up the market from domestic harvest. Besides the growing area of still unsatisfactory size, other reasons of the problem can be local anomalies in yield stability still occurring frequently, despite the available practical guides and experiences in cultivation technology. The practical experiences can serve as starting point that can be verified or open to be modified according to experiments. It is essential to set up experiments from the production of planting material up to the storage.

The comprehensive goal of our research work is to develop the regional technology of sweet potato production, establishing site- and cultivar-specific practical guides based on experiments that comprise both the local and the international experiences.

Our main objectives in the current work:

Comparison of the effect of planting primary or secondary cuttings on yield. To produce high quality planting material it can be an important information whether slips directly cut from sprouting storage roots (primary cuttings) or those derived by sprouting of the primary cuttings (secondary cuttings) result in higher yield.

Comparison of ridge and flat cultivation. Internationally, sweet potato is usually planted on ridges, regardless of the soil conditions [15]. It is important to determine whether among the local conditions planting on ridges or flat (without ridges) results in higher yields of storage roots.

Comparison of fertilizer doses. Fertilizer doses applied in practice compared to untreated control mean the first step in the optimization of sweet potato nutrient supply.

2. Materials and methods

The experiment was performed in Deszk, Hungary on clay loam soil of medium to very good nutrient content (Table 1). The experimental setup was four repetitions in randomized block design. The planting material derived from the Bivalyos Tanya Family Farm. In our experiment, we used the Ásotthalmi-12 orange-fleshed sweet potato variety. Spring tillage was followed by soil disinfection two times (Bora).

Table 1) Results of soil analysis

pH-KCl	Total salt	Soil plasticity	CaCO ₃	Humus	P ₂ O ₅	K ₂ O	Na	Mg
	m/m %	K _A	m/m %	m/m %	mg/kg			
7.10	0.04	46	1.77	3.46	1310	770	36.3	177

The cuttings were planted on 31st May 2016, altogether ca. 1,000 pieces on the whole experimental area of 300 m². The cuttings were planted manually with a dibble. The bottom 2/3 part of the slips was placed into the soil, followed by thorough irrigation. The plot size is 6 m x 2 m containing 40 transplants in two rows (1.0 m row distance, 0.3 m plant-to-plant distance). On sandy soils, flat cultivation (without ridges) is preferred, although world-wide in general, especially on heavy soils, ridge cultivation is common [16, 17]. Ridges were formed on one half of our experimental area, on the other half rows were formed flat.

The experiments with the planting material were started early April. Ten plastic trays were chosen where the sprouting of sweet potato storage roots had already been started. The primary cuttings were cut directly from the storage roots, watered, the lower leaves removed, and the slips were planted into the experimental trays. Secondary cuttings were derived from the sprouting of the primary ones. Both primary and secondary cuttings were used in the field experiments to get information that the primary or the secondary cuttings will give us more yield.

Fertilizers were applied on 22nd June in the forms of calcium ammonium nitrate (CAN), superphosphate and potassium sulphate, respectively. The control plots did not get any fertilizer. In active substances, the first fertilizer treatment is nitrogen 45 kg ha⁻¹, phosphorus 90 kg ha⁻¹, potassium 135 kg ha⁻¹, the second fertilizer treatment is nitrogen 67.5 kg ha⁻¹, phosphorus 90 kg ha⁻¹, potassium 180 kg ha⁻¹. Boron was also applied as foliar fertilizer in split-plot system, however, without any significant result thus we do not report these data in details.

3. Results

The experimental plots were harvested on 15th October 2016. The first five plants from each row were harvested and weighed separately. These plants had grown from primary or secondary cuttings, respectively.

On the experimental plots with ridges, plants grown from primary cuttings gave higher yields. Figure 1 shows that the control and the second fertilizer treatment produced nearly the same results, while the first fertilizer treatment gave the poorest result. Extrapolating the yields per plant to one hectare (33,000 plants), in

the case of the control treatment, the difference is below 1 ton (36.795 vs. 37.686 t ha⁻¹) while in the first treatment it is more than 3 tons (29.535 vs. 32.835 t ha⁻¹) between the yields of plants originating from primary and secondary cuttings, respectively.

Fig. 1. Effects of slip origin on sweet potato yield in ridge planting

Control: no fertilizer applied

Treatment 1: N 45 kg ha⁻¹, P 90 kg ha⁻¹, K 135 kg ha⁻¹

Treatment 2: N 67.5 kg ha⁻¹, P 90 kg ha⁻¹, K 180 kg ha⁻¹

Standard deviation (s) values (from left to right): 0.257; 0.195; 0.120; 0.207; 0.100; 0.236

Figure 2 shows that in flat planting without ridges, in the first fertilizer treatment the usage of secondary cuttings while in the second fertilizer treatment and in the control the usage of primary cuttings resulted in higher yield of storage roots. Extrapolating the yields per plant to one hectare, in the control treatment, the difference between the yields of plants originating from primary and secondary cuttings (38.445 vs. 28.215 t ha⁻¹) can be even 10 tons.

The total sweet potato yield harvested on the experimental plots with ridges was 433 kg while from the plots without ridges we harvested a total of 537 kg. Regarding the total number of plants being 960, it means 1.01 kg sweet potato yield per plant that is a good result according to bibliographical data.

Fig. 2. Effects of slip origin on sweet potato yield in flat (without ridges) planting

Control: no fertilizer applied

Treatment 1: N 45 kg ha⁻¹, P 90 kg ha⁻¹, K 135 kg ha⁻¹

Treatment 2: N 67.5 kg ha⁻¹, P 90 kg ha⁻¹, K 180 kg ha⁻¹

Standard deviation (s) values (from left to right): 0.359; 0.106; 0.159; 0.327; 0.210; 0.218

Figure 3 and 4 show that the sweet potato yield per plant was higher in the flat experimental plots (1.08-1.15 kg plant⁻¹) compared to the plots with ridges (0.87-0.91 kg plant⁻¹). On the level of the total area it means ca. 100 kg more sweet potatoes. This is an unexpected result because on heavier soils the ridge planting is recommended and preferred worldwide.

Fig. 3. Average yield of sweet potato plants in ridge planting

Control: no fertilizer applied

Treatment 1: N 45 kg ha⁻¹, P 90 kg ha⁻¹, K 135 kg ha⁻¹

Treatment 2: N 67.5 kg ha⁻¹, P 90 kg ha⁻¹, K 180 kg ha⁻¹

Standard deviation (s) values (from left to right): 0.068; 0.079; 0.109

Neither with nor without ridges, fertilizer treatments did not have a significant effect on sweet potato yield. In both cases, the fertilizer treatment 1 even decreased the yield by ca. 40 g at the single plant level compared to the control (Figures 3 and 4). The enhanced N and K doses in treatment 2 resulted in the same or nearly the same yield as the control.

Fig. 4. Average yield of sweet potato plants in flat (without ridges) planting

Control: no fertilizer applied

Treatment 1: N 45 kg ha⁻¹, P 90 kg ha⁻¹, K 135 kg ha⁻¹

Treatment 2: N 67.5 kg ha⁻¹, P 90 kg ha⁻¹, K 180 kg ha⁻¹

Standard deviation (s) values (from left to right): 0.136; 0.151; 0.276

We can conclude that under the given soil (Table 1) and agronomical conditions, fertilizer application could not increase sweet potato yield.

4. Conclusions

In our field experiment with sweet potato we got novel results about the utility of cuttings of different origin, as well as about the effects of planting method and various fertilizer doses on storage root yield.

To determine whether plants derived from primary cuttings or those originating from secondary cuttings give better yield, further experiments are needed. It is clearly shown, however, that under given conditions, the proper choosing of planting material can result even an extra sweet potato yield of 10 tons. To our knowledge, under temperate climate where planting material is grown from storage roots, both primary and secondary cuttings are commercially available and used for transplanting [14, 18].

The different fertilizer doses applied in our experiments, did not have a significant positive effect on sweet potato yield. Moreover, the first treatment resulted in a

slight decrease in yield although it meets the required N:P:K proportion of 1:2:3 [19]. The presumed explanation for the lack of yield increasing effect of fertilizers can be the relatively good nutrient supply of the soil at the experimental site. As the drop in yield can hardly be explained, this experiment needs a repetition.

All over the world, especially on clayey soils, sweet potato growing on ridges or beds is common. This offers well-aerated and well-drained conditions for storage root development, furthermore facilitates harvesting [20, 21]. Regarding the heavy structure of our soil, the better performance of sweet potatoes in flat planting was unexpected. Even the foliage developed more intensively (data not shown). The possible explanation can be found in the beneficial conditions of flat areas compared to ridges (e.g. better conservation of water), however, it requires further examination also focusing on the agrotechnical characteristics of the soil.

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REFERENCES

- [1] V. Heywood, H., Brummitt, R.K., Culham, A., O Seberg, (2007): *Flowering plant families of the world*. Richmond: Royal Botanic Gardens, Kew
 - [2] L. Horváth. (1991a): *A batáta és termesztése: Az édesburgonya Magyarországon*. Kertészet és Szőlészet 40 (15): 16-17.
 - [3] Http1. <http://www.greenfo.hu/hirek/2014/07/01/batatafalvi-batata-baratai>
 - [4] Fao (2014): <http://faostat3.fao.org/download/Q/QC/E>
 - [5] B. Novak, I Žutić, N Toth. (2007a): *Effects of mycorrhizal fungi and colored mulch in sweet potato production*. Acta Hort. 729: 245-248.
 - [6] B. Novak, I. Žutić, N. Toth, N. Dobričević. (2007b): *Sweet potato [Ipomoea batatas (L.) Lam] yield influenced by seedlings and mulching*. Agriculturae Conspectus Scientificus 72 (4): 357-359.
 - [7] B. Novak, I. Žutić, N. Toth, B. Benko, S. Fabek. (2008): *Evaluation of sweet potato growing in different environments of Croatia*. Cereal Research Communications 36 (Suppl. 5): 291-294.
 - [8] F. Bavec, M. Bavec, (2006): Sweet potato. In: Bavec, F., Bavec, M.: *Organic production and use of alternative crops*. CRC Press, Taylor & Francis Group. Pp. 189-200. 214 p.
 - [9] N. Kunstelj, D. Žnidarčič, B. Šter. (2013): *Using association rules mining for sweet potato (Ipomoea batatas L.) in Slovenia: A case study*. Journal of Food, Agriculture and Environment 11 (1): 253-258.
-

-
- [10] M. Dinu, R Soare. (2015): *Researches on the sweet potato (Ipomea batatas L.) behaviour under the soil and climatic conditions of the South-West of Romania*. Journal of Horticulture, Forestry and Biotechnology 19 (1): 79-84
- [11] B. Krochmal-Marczak, B Sawicka. (2010): *Variability of economic characteristics of Ipomoea batatas L. (Lam.) in the conditions of cultivation under cover*. Annales Universitatis Mariae Curie-Sklodowska Lublin – Polonia 65 (4): 29-40.
- [12] I. Lucas. (2013): *Ipomoea batatas – Sweet Potato or When is a potato not a potato* <http://blogs.reading.ac.uk/tropical-biodiversity/2013/01/ipomoea-batatas/>
- [13] L. Horváth. (1991b): *A batáta Magyarországon: Védelem, tárolás*. Kertészet és Szőlészet 40 (16): 16
- [14] L. Horváth. (1991c): *A batáta szaporítása*. Kertészet és Szőlészet 40 (21): 7
- [15] L. Brandenberger, J Shrefler, E Rebeck, J Damicone. (2014): *Sweet potato production*. Oklahoma Cooperative Extension Service, HLA-6022. Oklahoma State University, 8 p.
- [16] G. Kuepper. (2014): *Small-scale technology and practices for sweet potato growing in Southeast Oklahoma*. Kerr Center for Sustainable Agriculture, Poteau, Oklahoma. 12 p.
- [17] Http2 http://media.wix.com/ugd/a6aecc_7311b235e08a49cf817a3bd7de7bb6fe.pdf
- [18] C. Henderson (2015): *Managing sweetpotato plant beds in Australia. Literature review March 2015. For HIA Ltd Project VG13004 – Innovating new virus diagnostics and plant bed management in the Australian sweetpotato industry*. Horticulture Innovation Australia Ltd, State of Queensland. 18 p.
- [19] Http3: <http://www.infoagro.com/hortalizas/batata.htm>
- [20] C. Clark. (2013): *Cultivation and storage*. In: Clark, C.A., Ferrin, D.M., Smith, T.P., Holmes, G.J. (eds.): *Compendium of sweet potato disease, pests, and disorders*. Second edition. APS Press, St. Paul, Minnesota. Pp. 4-7.
- [21] V. Lebot, (2009). *Tropical root and tuber crops: cassava, sweet potato, yams and aroids*. Crop production science in horticulture (17), CAB books, CABI, Wallingford, UK
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THE ANNUAL WEATHER EFFECT ON TWO MAINLY USED MAIZE HYBRID YIELD IN HUNGARY

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Abstract. *In crop production the most modern hybrids are available for us, therefore the yield and yield stability is determined by the agro technology. The purpose of the experiment is to adapt the modern agrotechnology to the new type of hybrids. The long-term experiment was set up in 2015-2016 on chernozem soil in the Hajdúság (eastern Hungary). The plots were set up in 76 thousand ha⁻¹ plant density. We examined some mainly use hybrids of Hungary. The conducted studies are the effect of annual weather for the yield. We use three different sowing date as early, average and late, and measure how many plant germinated during the germination process. In the experiment we observed the hybrids in 4 replication. The yield was measured buy a special plot harvester - the Sampo Rosenlew 2010 – what measured the weight of the harvested plot and also took a sample from it. We determined the water content of the samples. After we calculated the yield (t ha⁻¹) of each plot at 14% of moisture content to compare them. We evaluated the data using Microsoft Excel 2015. The annual weather in each crop year define the maize yield*

Keywords: annual weather, maize, yield

1. Introduction

Hungary climate all in all is optimal for maize production. From the ecological factors the rain has the highest effect on crop yield. Recently dry years more and more occur when the maize suffering significant yield loss [1]. The nowadays average temperature exceeded the average of many years and this is coupled with a lack of rainfall has a direct impact on the crop production [2]. As an effect of global warming, optimum sowing date of some arable plants what requiring high temperature can change in the future. Optimum sowing date is crucial from the aspect of adaptation to rapidly changing conditions in the case of maize yield, especially in dry years. With the decrease of fossil fuels, usage of maize as bioethanol is becoming an increasingly important topic. Therefore, the analysis of the nutritional parameters of maize is strongly reasonable and this factor is also affected by sowing date [3]. The climate has large variability and the biggest risk factor in crop production [4] Berzsenyi and Gyórrffy in a dry crop year get 3.83 t ha⁻¹ and in a rainy year 6.0 t ha⁻¹ yield. Thereby they called attention to the result of the weather yield decreasing ability in the crop year [5]. Pintér and Szibrik think the anuak weather the biggest influential factorof the yeald. The largest variability shown by the rain in the crop year [6]. Bocz believes that the performance of the maize determine by the ecology, characteristics of the plant

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and by fertilization [7]. According to [8] the maize is specific productive plant, essential to determine the optimum density because, the corn plant to produce 1 kg of dry material used for 300 liters of water. The missing part of the water stored in the soil cover of the plant. Therefore, it is important to determine the plant density [9]. Less than optimum or higher plant densities, both reduce the yield of the maize [10].

2. Materials and methods

The field research was carried out at Látókép research area of the University of Debrecen on chernozem soil. Soil of the research area is of good agricultural condition, medium hard soil. Water supplies of the soil are favorable. Examined hybrids were P9074, and the SY Octavius. The experiment was set in 76 thousand plants ha⁻¹ plant density. We used three sowing dates. Early sowing date: April 1, Average: April 21, Late sowing: May 5. in 4 replication of each plot. The results were presented in the average of the replications. In both years the fore crop was winter wheat. The experiment was set in one nutrient level. The amount of N was 108 kg ha⁻¹ (in Pétisó). We harvested the plot with a SAMPO plot harvester.

In the 2015 crop year the first half of March was especially cold, wintry weather conditions, however, subsequently be followed by relatively rapid warming. There was low precipitation in March. The dry weather continued in April. April temperature conditions were very similar to the March weather. First half of April with an especially cool weather, the second half was characterized by a slow warming. After May there was close average weather (Table 1).

Table 10) The amount of meteorological parameters in the examined crop years

Months		Apr	May	June	July	Aug	Sept	Oct	Total/ Average
Precipitation (mm)	30 year's average	42.4	58.8	79.5	65.7	60.7	38.0	31.8	376.9
	2015	21.9	52.9	60.5	35.6	84.0	48.9	86.6	390.4
	2016	14.4	69.2	146.3	84.6	71.7	63.4	52.6	502.2
Temperature (°C)	30 year's average	10.7	15.8	18.8	20.3	19.6	15.8	10.3	15.9
	2015	10.1	15.8	19.9	22.9	23.3	17.8	11.2	17.3
	2016	12.5	15.7	20.1	22.9	19.8	17.2	15.2	17.5

Fig. 1. Soil temperature in Debrecen 2015-2016.

In 2015 the soil temperature in the beginning of April was colder than it suitable for planting. In the next year the weather was much hotter at this time. After the middle of April the soil temperature is close the same in both year but in 2016 the end of April the weather cooled down and stay colder than in 2015 duaring the whole germination process (Figure 1).

In this experiment we measure the plants germination dynamics. After sowing we mark two meter long two row wide plots in every parcel and from the beginning of germination we count the plants. We do it every 3 day until the whole parcel germinated. We measured the amount of yield with a special plot harvester - the Sampo Rosenlew 2010 – what measured the weight of the harvested plot and also took a sample from it.

Results and discussion

Fig. 2. Growing dynamics P9074 - SY Octavius (Debrecen 2015)

In the 2015 crop year, it can be observed at the first sowing date (5th April) that due to cold soil temperature the plants very slowly germinated, and slowly began to grow (Figure 2). After the temperature rise the average sowing date (21th April) it is more favorable for the plants as they receive bigger heat and they start germination sooner and grow rapidly. At the third sowing date what was the late sowing (5th May) we examined the most intense germinating, as here, the temperature has exceeded the minimum level for the plants.

In 2015 at the first sowing date the P9074 hybrid has the best germination. This hybrid better tolerate the cold temperature. In the average and sowing the leading position is for SY Octavius but later the P9074 takes the lead. On the late sowing the best germinated hybrid is SY Octavius at the beginning. The P9074 hybrid prefer the warmer weather much more.

Fig. 3. Growing dynamics P9074 - SY Octavius (Debrecen 2016)

In 2016 the plants germinated sooner because in the second examination time we measure 74% germination (Figure 3). It's 20% bigger than in the last year. After this the temperature cooled down, so at the average sowing date (21th April) the plants as they receive normal heat, they start germinating in the same time at the 2015 crop year. The tendency of germinating is close the same as in last year. The third sowing date was the late sowing date (5th May). In this case, we examined the most intense germinating, as here, the temperature has much more exceeded the minimum level for the plants. In the 2016 crop year the first sowing date (1th April) it can be observed (Figure 4) that due to warm soil temperature the plants was germinated 10 day earlier than in last year.

In 2016 cropyear the first sowing best hybrid is still the P9074. This hybrid was the best on the previous year. The weather in 2016 was warmer therefore hybrids take advantage to germinate faster. In the average sowing the best was the SY

Octavius at the beginning but after the P9074 takes the lead. This hybrid was the best in the late sowing date, too. We obtained this hybrid prefer cooler weather much more.

Fig. 4. Growing dynamics average of P9074 - SY Octavius (Debrecen 2015-2016)

Table 11) The amount of yield in 2015-2016 (Debrecen)

2015			2016		
Sowing date	Hybrids	Yield	Sowing date	Hybrids	Yield
		t ha ⁻¹			t ha ⁻¹
Early	P9074	13.42	Early	P9074	18.92
	SY Octavius	12.46		SY Octavius	20.25
Average	P9074	13.65	Average	P9074	19.83
	SY Octavius	13.32		SY Octavius	22.04
Late	P9074	12.78	Late	P9074	18.55
	SY Octavius	13.98		SY Octavius	20.86

After the sowing dates reach the optimal water content we harvested the parcels. We measure the water content of each plot and measure the amount of yield. After we calculate the yield on equal water content what is 14%. In 2015 the P9074 produced the highest yield in the early and average sowing date. In the early it produced 13.42 t ha⁻¹ and in the average it produced 13.65 t ha⁻¹. In this year the SY Octavius produced the top yield 13.98 t ha⁻¹ in the late sowing date (Table 2).

In 2016 the SY Octavius has the highest amount of yield in all the three sowing dates. It produced 20.25 t ha⁻¹ in the early, 20.86 t ha⁻¹ in the late. And produced their top yield in the average sowing 22.04 t ha⁻¹.

Conclusions

The long term experiment was set up at at Látókép research area of the University of Debrecen on chernozem soil. We use two top hybrid .The P9074 (FAO 310) and the SY Octavius (FAO 400) from different genotype. The hybrids was sown in 76 thousand ha⁻¹ plant density. We use three different sowing date. Early, average and late. The early sowing date in the future will have a great role. Because the global warming change the sowing date of some plants. With using earlier sowing, result greater crop safety, because plants can avoid atmospheric drought duaring the summer. Both in dry and rainy crop year the early sowing produce close the same ammount of yield than the average sowing. All in all the average sowing date has the highest amount of yield. The late sowing was the second and the early sowing produced the less yield.

REFERENCES

- [1] Jakab P. Zsoldos M. (2002) *Analyzing different crop year effect in maize fertilization experiment.* Agrártudományi közlemények 38-40.
 - [2] Jakab P. (2002) *The examination of complex fertilization in maize hybrid production.* Agrártudományi közlemények 35-37
 - [3] Bene E; Sárvári M; Futó Z: (2014) *The effect of sowing date on three maize hybrids with different growing seasons on their quantity and some of their quality parameters.* Cropproduction: Volume 63, Issue 4.
 - [4] Berzsenyi Z. Györfly B. (1997) *The effect of the manure to the yield and the yield stability of the maize in monoculture.* Cropproduction: Volume 46, Issue 5.
 - [5] Nagy J. (2006): *The effect of water supply in early (FAO 300-399) maize hybrids yield in production without irrigation.* Cropproduction. 55. 1-2. 103-112.
 - [6] Pintér L.-Szirbik M. (1977) *The applying skills of the maize hybrids.* Cropproduction. 26. 6. 433-442.
 - [7] Bocz E. (1974) *The fertilization some domestic arable crops in Hungary* 65-77
 - [8] Pepó P. (2012) *Reserves in maize production agrotechnic.* Agrofórum Extra 47. 5-11.
 - [9] Szabó Sz. (2012) *The drought of maize and its physiological reactions.* Agronapló 2012/12. 18.
 - [10] Pálovics B. (2006) *The effect of plant densit in maize production.* Agrártudományi közlemények 2006/23 50-51.
-

TWO GROWN HERBS' DRUG YIELD CHANGES UNDER DIFFERENT FERTILIZATION SETTINGS IN SMALL PLOT TRIAL

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Abstract. *While we investigated the summer savory's (*Satureja hortensis* L.) and the marigold's (*Calendula officinalis* L.) nutrient requirements in small-plot trial we measured the drug yield, which we harvested in 2015 and in 2016.*

It was concluded, based on the results, in 2015 the biggest marigold drug yield in the N30P40K60 fertilization setting and in 2016 in the N75P100K150 setting were measured. The savory's yield in 2015 in the N30P40K60, and in 2016 in the N60P80K120 settings were the biggest.

Thanks to the multiple picking the data we got with harvesting of the marigold, we investigated the effect of the different fertilization settings the flower drug's changes over time. The drug crop's change over time could show how many times it is economical to harvest under different fertilization settings.

Keywords: herb, drug, fertilization, marigold, savory

1. Introduction

Many connections had been woven between plants and humankind. The plants and their healing capabilities are here and were in the medicine, meal, science, cosmetology, and in various art forms. In the XXIth century, the phytotherapy in given cases already recognized priority, besides it is getting more and more emphasis in medicine [1].

Herb's cultivation contains different species with different nutrient requirements. The herbs are not undemanding, this statement is incorrect [2]. The cultivation and within that the nutrient requirement of the medicinal plants is a very new re-discovered field in the scientific research. The growers need new, economically and even intensively growable medicine plant species, and modern connecting agrotechnic, to could be compete the world markets [3]. There are many uncertainties which make more difficult determine the nutrient requirements of herbs [4].

According to recent researches, the different fertilization settings has not got significant influence on the marigold's flavonoids [5].

Under our research we analysed the nutrient requirements and fertilizer reactions of herbs, such as the marigold and the summer savory according to the change in the drug yield, as an effect of the different nutrient dosages.

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The marigold (*Calendula officinalis* L., marigold, gold-bloom, Chinese safflower and the summer savory are mediterranean annual plants [6], [7]. For the marigold it's flower (with or without sepal), for the savory, it's the flowering herba gathered as a drug [7], [8].

The marigold is slightly laxative and spasmolytic, but due to it's high E vitamin content it is mainly used for healing of the skin. It is one of the most effective herbs that can be applied to treat lacerations, torn skin wounds and surgical scars [9].

In medicine investigation, there is a stable LGP (lamellar gel phase) emulsion under development with using marigold, which can be an alternative to facilitate the healing of wounds [10].

It could be used for horses' follow-up care of fractures, bruises and sprains externally. For internally used to treat stomach ulcers [11]. The high blood sugar levels mainly promotes the typical complications of diabetes, and leading to arterial stiffness, decreased myocardial compliance and aging. There are researches to prove, the marigold has great antioxidation potential, which could inhibit these two reactions.[12]. The diabetic micro traumas on limbs are constant possibility of infections, and could lead to amputation. The marigold balm could stop the progression of infections and reduced the itching, the redness, the dryness, and the pain, while the risk of allergy to the plant is very low [13].

For the marigold's growing is not recommended use directly manure or high doses of nitrogen fertilizers, because these are increase the vegetative parts' growing against the flowers'. The marigold shape quickly, the harvest of the flowers is stimulates the formation of new ones [14].

In the hungarian national list of species has one savory species, the Budakalászi, since 1959 [15]. The summer savory used in the food industry mainly as a spice for canned foods and liqueurs, or as a dietetian spice, and component of tea blends for blood pressure, inflation, gripes, and sore throat int he traditional medicine [14], [16], [17].

The savory is not demanding for the forecrop. It needs perennial weed free place. Avoid after itself for 2-3 years. It needs medium level of nutrients with more potassium [18]. It is not expedient dispatch the manure directly below, which is otherwise well utilized [19].

2. Materials and methods

The experiment took place in the experiment site of the University of Debrecen, Institute of Crop Sciences. The place's soil is chernozem. Before our research would be planned, in 2014, the regular annual nutrient dosages were spread on the

land. These nutrient supplies necessarily had an impact on the yield of the marigold and the savory.

The rainfall on the experimental area in 2015 from 1st January to 30th September was considerably less (286.2 mm) than the 30 year average (445.8 mm). From January till the end of September the average temperature of each month were higher than the 30 year average, except April. In 2016 the rainfall from 1st January to 31th August was considerably more (574.9 mm) than the 30 year average. From the 1st January to 31th August in 2016, the measured monthly mean temperature was higher than the 30 year average.

The experimental plot size was 8 m². The plots were arranged in 4 replicates in randomized blocks, with 6 different fertilizer treatment levels, in 4 rows with 40 cm row space. In 2015 and 2016, sowing took place on the spot on 7th April and on 4th April, in 1 cm depth in the case of both plants.

The fertilization settings:

- N0P0K0 (Control)
- N15P20K30
- N30P40K60
- N45P60K90
- N60P80K120
- N75P100K150

N%, P₂O₅%, K₂O%

We spread the fertilizer doses manually to the experimental place.

We measured the marigold's drug yield which, in this case, was the quantity of the raw flower with sepal. Gathering was done 6 times manually between 6th July and 18th August 2015 and 7 times in 2016 between 16th June and 1th August. The harvested marigold for the drying has been spread to a single layer, under semi-shade. The drying of the drug took six days average.

We measured the savouries raw drug yield. Gathering was done manually between 12th and 17th August 2015, and between 8th and 10th August 2016.

The drying of the savory herba in 2015 first happened in semi-shade, and it took an average of three weeks. Unfortunately, because of the rainy weather the drug got back wetted and we must make post-drying in drying cabinet 40 °C for 12 hours.

In 2016 because of the rainy weather too we dried the savory yield in drying cabinet 40 °C for 17 hours. We stored the dried marigold and crumbled savory herba drug in paper bags.

3. Results and discussion

Fig. 1. The quantity of the marigold raw drug yield depending on the nutrient supply 2015 (Debrecen, 2015)

Fig. 1. shows the quantity of the marigold raw drug yield depending on the nutrient supply in 2015. The plots with N30P40K60 had the most favourable nutrient setting, followed by the results of the plots with N45P60K90, then that of the control groups.

Fig. 2. The quantity of the marigold raw drug yield depending on the nutrient supply 2016 (Debrecen, 2016)

Fig. 2. shows the quantity of the marigold raw drug yield and the nutrient supplies connection in 2016. In this year the N75P100K150, the N60P80K120 and the N15P20K30 fertilization setting has the biggest effect to the raw drug yield, and the N45P60K90 setting has the weakest effect on the yield.

Fig. 3. The quantity of the summer savory raw drug yield depending on the nutrient supply 2015 (Debrecen, 2015)

On Fig. 3. can be observed the savory raw herba drug yield changes depending on the nutrient supply in 2015. Considering the quantity of the drug crop, the plots with N30P40K60 had the most favourable nutrient setting, followed by the results of the plots with N15P20K30, then that of the N60P80K120 groups. The highest nutrient level (N75P100K150) had the weakest effect on the quantity of the herba drug.

Fig. 4. The quantity of the summer savory raw drug yield depending on the nutrient supply 2016 (Debrecen, 2016)

On Fig. 4. there is the herba drug yield of savory depending on the nutrient supply in 2016. In contrary to the raw yield data of the year 2015, the plots with N60P80K120 had the most favourable nutrient setting, followed by the results of the plots with N15P20K30, then that of the N30P40K60 groups.

Fig. 5. The marigold raw drug yield changing depending on time in 2015 (Debrecen, 2015)

During the marigold's weakly harvest in 2015 all of the plots' yield decreased. Between 21th and 22th July and between 17th and 18th August we measured a weak growth which was the biggest in N30P40K60 fertilizer treatment (Fig. 5.).

Fig. 6. The marigold raw drug yield changing depending on time in 2016 (Debrecen, 2016)

During the also weakly harvest of the marigold plots' the yield firstly increased. We measured the highest yield in the harvest of 28th June. Then the quantity of the yield start to decrease. There were a slight increase again on 18th July, but the yield reduction then continued. Until 11th July the N60P80K120 and the N75P100K150 settings' yields reduced least (Fig. 6.).

4. Conclusions

4.1. Conclusions for the marigold's data

Conclusion (1). As for the drug yield of the marigold, it seems the N30P40K60 level was the ideal nutrient setting in 2015.

Conclusion (2). In 2016 the N75P100K150 nutrient supply was the most effective

Conclusion (3). In our opinion, one of the main reason for the fluctuation of the yield besides the different fertilizer dosages was the very warm and dry weather of the vegetative period in 2015.

Conclusion (4). In our opinion, one of the main reason for the fluctuation of the yield besides the different fertilizer dosages was the fluctuations in rainfall in 2016.

Conclusion (5). The nutrient supply has effect on the biomass production and yield of the crops also in case of herbs.

Conclusion (6). The variance analysis of the drug mass' data did not show significant differences between the plots with the different fertilizer treatments.

Conclusion (7). In our opinion the changes of the temperature and the rainfall are more effective for the marigold's drug yield than the increasing nutrient settings. This phenomenon can influence the changes of the harvests' number, as well as the possible renewal term of the stand.

Conclusion (8). We need more research work to do to clear the complex connections between the quantity and the changes of the marigold drug yield and the effect of the different nutrient settings.

4.2. Conclusions for the summer savory's data

Conclusion (1). As for the herba drug yield of the summer savory in 2015 the N30P40K60 level was the ideal nutrient setting.

Conclusion (2). In 2016 the N15P20K30 fertilizer treatment was the ideal.

Conclusion (3). The three nutrient settings which provided the best results in 2015 and 2016 were the N15P20K30, the N30P40K60, and the N60P80K120.

Conclusion (4). In our opinion, one of the main reasons for the fluctuation of the yield with a given nutrient setting was the very warm and dry weather of the vegetative period in 2015.

Conclusion (5). In our opinion, one of the main reason for the fluctuation of the yield besides the different fertilizer dosages was the fluctuations in rainfall in 2016.

Conclusion (6). The variance analysis of the data of the drug mass did not show significant differences between the plots with different fertilizer treatments.

Conclusion (7). Based on the results, it seems concluded, the savory drug yield depending on the crop land's ecological endowment, and cropping technologies.

Conclusion (8). We need more research work to do to clear the complex connections between the quantity and the changes of the summer savory drug yield and the effect of the different nutrient settings.

REFERENCES

- [1] NAGY G. (1994): *Gyógynövény-történelem, Recept: független egészségpolitikai magazin*, 1994., 5. évf., 10. szám, 22-23. pp.
 - [2] ZÁMBORINÉ N. É. (2010): *Gyógynövények korszerű tápanyag-utánpótlása*, *Agrofórum*, 21. évf., 10. szám, 64-69 pp.
 - [3] ZÁMBORINÉ N. É., RAJHÁRT P., SZABÓ K., ÉS ANTAL T. (2010): *A tápanyag-utánpótlás hatása gyógynövények hozamára és drogminőségére*, *Kertgazdaság*, 42. évf., 3-4. szám, 128-135 pp.
 - [4] VALKOVSZKI N. J. (2011): *Egyéves konyhakömény tápanyagigényének vizsgálata*, *Agrofórum*, 22. évf., 3. szám, 102-104 pp.
 - [5] FERNANDES E. F. A., MELONI F., BORELLA J. C., LOPES N. P. (2013): *Effect of fertilisation and harvest period on polar metabolites of Calendula officinalis*, *Revista Brasileira de Farmacognosia (Brazilian journal of pharmacognosy)*, 23. évf., 731-735 pp.
 - [6] WHO (1999): *Monographs on selected medicinal plants* Voluma 2
 - [7] RÁPÓTI J., és ROMVÁRY V. (1987): *Gyógyító növények*, *Medicina Könyvkiadó*, Budapest
 - [8] DÁNOS B. (2006): *Farmakobotanika, Gyógynövényismeret, Harmadik, bővített, átdolgozott kiadás*, *Semmelweis Kiadó*, Budapest
 - [9] VARRÓ A. B. (2011): *Gyógynövények gyógyhatásai, Növényi gyógyszerek, Hazai gyógynövényeink ismertetése, gyűjtésüknek módja és felhasználásuk a mindennapi életben az egészség szolgálatában*, *Kódexfestő Könyvkereskedés Kft.*, Debrecen, Kinizsi nyomda
 - [10] OKUMA CH., ANDRADE TA., CAETANO GF., FINCI LI., MACIEL NR., TOPAN JF., CEFALI LC., POLIZELLO AC., CARLO T., ROGERIO AP., SPADARO AC., ISAAC VL., FRADE MA., ROCHA-FILHO PA. (2015): *Development of lamellar gel phase emulsion containing marigold oil (Calendula officinalis) as a potential modern wound dressing*, *European Journal of Pharmaceutical Sciences* 71 (2015) 62-72.pp.
 - [11] MARTON ZS. (2005): *Lóherba, Gyógynövények lovaknak*, *Equinter Kiadó*, Budapest
 - [12] AHMAD H., KHAN I., and WAHID A. (2012): *Antiglycation and antioxidation properties of juglans regia and calendula officinalis: possible role in reducing diabetic complications and slowingdown ageing*, *Journal of Traditional Chinese Medicine*, 2012. September 15; 32(3): 1-2.
-

- [13] CIOINAC S. E. (2016): *Use of calendula cream balm to medicate the feet of diabetic patients: Case series, DATeR Dialysis, Hospital Dialysis Center Bentivoglio, AUSL Bologna, Bologna, Italy*, International Journal of Nursing Sciences XXX (2016) I-II.
- [14] BERNÁTH J. (Szerk.) (2000): *Gyógy- és aromanövények*, Mezőgazda Kiadó, Budapest
- [15] NEMZETI ÉLELMISZERLÁNC-BIZTONSÁGI HIVATAL (2014): *Nemzeti fajtajegyzék, Zöldség- és gyógynövények*, Gyógy- és fűszernövények, Budapest, 39-48 pp.
- [16] TAKÁCSNÉ HÁJOS M. (a.) (2004): *Gyógynövények termesztése*, Szaktudás Kiadó Ház, Budapest
- [17] MAKAY B. (1994): *Fűvel-fával gyógyítás kézikönyve*, Kötet Kiadó, Nyíregyháza, 286.p.
- [18] BERNÁTH J. (Szerk.) (2013): *Vadon termő és termesztett gyógynövények*, Gyűjtésük, termesztésük és felhasználásuk, Mezőgazda Kiadó, Budapest
- [19] PEPÓ P. (1992): *Növénytermesztési füzetek 8., Gyógynövények*, Debreceni Agrártudományi Egyetem, Növénytermesztési Tanszék, Debrecen
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WATER USE EFFICIENCY OF MAIZE IN FIELD EXPERIMENTS

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Abstract. *There is little direct in field information about the effects of the abiotic stress factors such as low soil water content on the photosynthesis system of crops. Some recent publications pay attention on this field of research. The water stress has significant effect on the yield and other agronomic parameters of maize. The aim of our work was to get more data about the relations between the water supply and the assimilation parameters. The photosynthetic gas exchange parameters of maize are remarkably improved by nutrient supply in well watered conditions. The water stress through decreased stomatal conductance has significant negative effect on the assimilation parameters of the crops. The obtained results suggest that the water use efficiency of the maize is higher under dry conditions. In well water supply state maize uses up to 330 per cent more water for 1 g CO₂ assimilation.*

Keywords: maize, water use efficiency, abiotic stress

1. Introduction

We can find some articles according to the topic photosynthesis system and the water use efficiency of maize published in the last decades [1, 2, 3, 4, 5]. Shangguan et al. (2000) wrote that the nutrient and water supply has significant effect on the photosynthetic gas exchange of the plant.

The better nitrogen supply results in poorer water use efficiency comparing to the lower nitrogen supply conditions, due to the high rate decreasing in photosynthetic activity [6]. Janda et al. (1998) studied the effect of temperature in the growing period on the net photosynthesis rate of inbred maize lines. They found that at optimal temperature there were no significant differences between the maize lines in the net photosynthesis rate, but after cold treatment the net photosynthesis rate of the lines with lower cold tolerance reduced significantly [7].

Kang et al (2000) did two years study on the effect of water stress on the photosynthesis rate of maize leaf. They stated that the reduced photosynthesis of the water-stressed leaf recovered its previous level three days after irrigation applied [8]. Ben-Asher et al. (2008) studied the transpiration and photosynthetic activity of sweet corn in climate chamber. Their results show that increasing of temperature causes higher transpiration and decreasing in the photosynthesis intensity (with $1 \mu\text{mol m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$ by $1 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ temperature increasing) [9].

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2. Materials and methods

The measurements were carried out between 1999 and 2016 at the Látókép research site of the Debrecen University in small plot (15.4 m²) experiments. The soil of the experimental area is calciferous chernozem. The soil specific plasticity index (KA) was 43; the pH value was nearly neutral (pH_{KCl}=6.46) and it has favourable water regime. The minimal water storing capacity is 808 mm in the 0-200 cm layer. The unavailable water content is 295 mm in the 0-200 cm layer. The amount of disponsible water in saturated state is 513 mm in the 0-200 cm layer of which 342 mm is readily available. The watertable is at 6-8 meters depth.

The set crop rotations: triculture (winter wheat – maize – pea), biculture (winter wheat – maize), monoculture: maize.

Fertilization levels: control: N₀P₀K₀, N₁₂₀P₉₀K₉₀ kg ha⁻¹

Assimilation parameters were measured in the field by the LICOR LI-6400 portable photosynthesis system. It has two infrared gas analyzers to measure CO₂ and H₂O mole fraction in air. The light was controlled in the sample chamber, we used 2000 μmol photon m⁻² s⁻¹ PAR, with 90 % red (630 nm) and 10 % blue (470 nm) light. There is a contact thermometer in the leaf chamber to measure leaf temperature.

We measured light adapted leaves, six times per leaf, in four repetitions. The water use efficiency parameters were calculated from the measured data (WUE g CO₂ kg⁻¹ H₂O) and (1/WUE kg H₂O kg⁻¹ CO₂). We analyzed and evaluated the data of experimental results with the IBM SPSS 22.0 statistical software package. The accuracy of the statistical analysis was given at the level of LSD5% according to the method of Sváb (1981). The results were evaluated with analysis of variance, and Pearson's correlation analysis.

3. Results and discussion

To present the water supply state of maize in the studied years we calculated the potential (PET) and actual evapotranspiration (AET) [10] and their ratio. The higher the ratio, the better the water state of the crop, in this case the maize. 2000, 2002, 2007, 2009, 2012 were very dry years, the PET:AET ratio was very low in these growing seasons (Fig. 1, Fig. 2). On the contrary the water supply in 2004, 2005, 2008 and 2010 was very good to maize (Fig. 3).

According to the growing season's PET:AET ratio we can say the years 1999, 2001, 2006, 2011, 2013, 2014, 2016 were average, but in details there are great differences in the distribution of the rainfall. For example in 2013 the first half of the growing season was favourable regarding to water supply, but from July it was very dry, and the AET:PET ratio was only 27.5% in August, while in 2016 after a

relatively dry spring season the water supply was good to maize These deviations also resulted in differences in yield (Fig. 4, Fig. 5).

We also can see on the figures that in years with high rainfall the potential evapotranspiration is lower caused by the lower temperature and higher air humidity. Maize prefer warm weather, so farmers usually do not harvest very high yields in these years, despite the good water supply of the crop.

Fig. 1. Estimated PET and AET values, PET:AET ratio and the precipitation in maize growing season (Látókép, 1999-2016)

Fig. 2. Estimated PET, AET values and AET/PET ratio in maize growing season (Látókép, 2007)

Fig. 3. Estimated PET, AET values and AET/PET ratio in maize growing season (Látókép, 2010)

Fig. 4. Estimated PET, AET values and AET/PET ratio in maize growing season (Látókép, 2013)

Fig. 5. Estimated PET, AET values and AET/PET ratio in maize growing season (Látókép, 2016)

Table 1) Correlations between the transpiration, the water use efficiency and the measured photosynthesis parameters of maize (r values of Pearson correlation) (Látókép, 04 07 2013)

		Cond	Trmmol	1/WUE	tair-tleaf
Monoculture	Cond(1)	1	0.990	-0.949	0.689
	Trmmol(2)	0.990	1	-0.950	0.599
	1/WUE(3)	-0.949	-0.950	1	-0.638
	tair-tleaf(4)	0.689	0.599	-0.638	1
Biculture	Cond(1)	1	0,971	-0.900	0.761
	Trmmol(2)	0,971	1	-0.935	0.598
	1/WUE(3)	-0.900	-0.935	1	-0.544
	tair-tleaf(4)	0.761	0.598	-0.544	1
Triculture	Cond(1)	1	0.980	-0.948	0.800
	Trmmol(2)	0.980	1	-0.961	0.683
	1/WUE(3)	-0.948	-0.961	1	-0.654
	tair-tleaf(4)	0.800	0.683	-0.654	1

1: stomatal conductance ($\text{mol H}_2\text{O m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$), 2: transpiration ($\text{mmol H}_2\text{O m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$), 3: water use efficiency ($\text{kg H}_2\text{O g}^{-1}\text{CO}_2$), 4: air temperature – leaf temperature ($^{\circ}\text{C}$)

The correlation coefficient values are significant at $P=5\%$ level in every above cases.

We calculated the actual water use efficiency (WUE) of the maize using the measured photosynthesis and transpiration data. The water use efficiency was higher in 2013 ($38.14 \text{ g CO}_2 \text{ kg}^{-1} \text{ H}_2\text{O}$) than that of in wet 2010 ($23.33 \text{ g CO}_2 \text{ kg}^{-1} \text{ H}_2\text{O}$). There were significant differences between the crop rotation varieties, monoculture: $42.09 \text{ g CO}_2 \text{ kg}^{-1} \text{ H}_2\text{O}$, biculture: $35.01 \text{ g CO}_2 \text{ kg}^{-1} \text{ H}_2\text{O}$ and the triculture: $37.31 \text{ g CO}_2 \text{ kg}^{-1} \text{ H}_2\text{O}$ ($\text{LSD}_{5\%}=1.09$). As monoculture means unfavourable water supply comparing to the biculture, this data coincide with results of our previous researches under remarkably different water supply showing that maize use water with much less efficiency under favourable water supplying conditions than in water stress state.

The irrigation had significant effect on the water use efficiency of maize in the experiment. The greatest effect we measured in monoculture (nonirrigated: $46.27 \text{ g CO}_2 \text{ kg}^{-1} \text{ H}_2\text{O}$, irrigated: $37.91 \text{ g CO}_2 \text{ kg}^{-1} \text{ H}_2\text{O}$). The better water supply caused significantly lower efficiency in water use. The difference was lower in the triculture rotation (nonirrigated: $38.84 \text{ g CO}_2 \text{ kg}^{-1} \text{ H}_2\text{O}$, irrigated: $35.62 \text{ g CO}_2 \text{ kg}^{-1} \text{ H}_2\text{O}$) and the lowest difference was in the biculture variation in water use efficiency (nonirrigated: $34.39 \text{ g CO}_2 \text{ kg}^{-1} \text{ H}_2\text{O}$, irrigated: $35.62 \text{ g CO}_2 \text{ kg}^{-1} \text{ H}_2\text{O}$).

Fig. 6. Water use efficiency of maize in different crop rotation variations (Látókép, 2013)

Table 2) Water use efficiency of maize in different cropyears (Látókép, 2007-2013)

Years	WUE (g CO ₂ kg H ₂ O ⁻¹)	per cent (the basis is 2010)
2007	77.82	334
2009	49.04	210
2010	23.33	100
2011	52.88	227
2012	36.19	155
2013	61.52	264

The water use efficiency data of maize show that the lowest efficiency was in 2010, a year with very good water supply. In droughty years like 2009, 2012 and 2013 the efficiency was much better. And the data of very droughty 2007 prove this statement (Table 2). In wet years maize transpires 150-330% more water to one gram CO₂ assimilation than in dry years or in water stress (Fig. 6).

Fig. 7. Water use efficiency of maize in different type cropyears

Conclusions

We found significant, close positive connection between the difference of leaf and air temperature and the water use efficiency of maize. The warmer the leaf comparing to the air, the more the transpired water to assimilate one unit CO₂.

We proved negative connection between the water use efficiency of maize and the soil moisture content in the droughty 2007 year. The higher the moisture content of the soil, the lower the water use efficiency.

In dry conditions maize uses water very effectively, while the good water supply results in lowering efficiency of water use. In better water state maize transpires 150-300% more water to assimilate 1 g CO₂ in wet years, comparing to dry years or water stress state (Fig. 7).

The irrigation had significant effect on the water use efficiency of maize, the greatest effect we measured in monoculture.

REFERENCES

- [1] Raschke, K. *Stomatal responses to pressure changes and interruptions in the water supply of detached leaves of Zea mays L.* Plant Physiology, 45, 415 (1970)
 - [2] Lu, C., Zhang J. *Photosynthetic CO₂ assimilation, chlorophyll fluorescence and photoinhibition as affected by nitrogen deficiency in maize plants.* Plant Science 151 (2) 135 (2000)
 - [3] Hirasawa, T., HSIAO T. C.: *Some characteristics of reduced leaf photosynthesis at midday in maize growing in the field.* Field Crops Research 62 (1) 53
 - [4] Csajbók, J.-Kutasy E. *A transzspiráció és a fotoszintetikus aktivitás összefüggései kukoricában Talaj-víz-növény kapcsolatrendszer a növénytermesztési térben (MTA AK TAKI, Budapest, ISBN: 97896389041-6-4 pp. 151. 2012)*
 - [5] Kutasy, E., Csajbók, J. *Effects of nitrogen supply on the efficiency of photosynthesis of maize* In: C Grignani, M Acutis, L Zavattaro, L Bechini, C Bertora, P Marino Gallina, D Sacco Proceedings of the 16th Nitrogen Workshop: *Connecting different scales of nitrogen use in agriculture* pp 421-422. (2009)
 - [6] Shangguan, Z. P., Shao, M. A., Dyckmans, J. *Nitrogen nutrition and water stress effects on leaf photosynthetic gas exchange and water use efficiency in winter wheat.* Environmental and Experimental Botany 44 141 (2000)
 - [7] Janda, T., Szalai, G., Ducruet, J.-M., Páldi, E. *Changes in photosynthesis in inbred maize lines with different degrees of chilling tolerance grown at optimum and suboptimum temperatures.* Photosynthetica 35 (2): 205 (1998)
-

-
- [8] Kang, S., Shi, W., Zhang, J.: *An improved water-use efficiency for maize grown under regulated deficit irrigation*. Field Crops Research Vol. 67 (3) 207
- [9] Ben-Asher, J, Garcia A. Y, Hoogenboom, G. *Effect of high temperature on photosynthesis and transpiration of sweet corn (Zea mays L. var. rugosa)*, Photosynthetica 46 (4), 595 (2008)
- [10] Szász, G. *A víz a légkörben, a talajban és a növényben. Meteorológia mezőgazdáknek, kertészeknek, erdészeknek. szerk. Szász G.-Tőkei L. (Mezőgazda Kiadó, Budapest p. 111-172, 1997)*
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EFFECT OF FERTILIZER-CONTAINING- MICROORGANISMS ON MAIZE GROWTH AND ROOT LENGTH

Brigitta TÓTH¹

Abstract. *The general objective of this research was deliver and implement viable alternatives to mineral fertilizers by developing strategic combinations of BEs with alternatives to the current practice of mineral fertilizations, such as organic farming, low input agriculture, or the use of fertilizers based on recycling products. In this study, 13 bacterial and fungal isolations were tested as BEs. During this investigation the main plant physiological parameters (relative chlorophyll content, height of plants, root growth, dry and fresh weight) of maize (cv Maxxis) were examined. Maize is well known to be particularly sensitive to low phosphorous (P) availability, as well as to show responsiveness to applications of microbial BEs. The experiment was conducted in pots (2 kg soil) under controlled growth chamber conditions with P as the major limiting nutrient.*

Keywords: crop production, microorganism, phosphorous, plant growth, root length

1. Introduction

Phosphorus (P) is one of the major essential macro-elements required for maximizing crop growth and production. With increasing demand of agricultural production and as the peak in global production will occur in the next decades, phosphorus (P) is receiving more attention as a nonrenewable resource [1]. One unique characteristic of P is its low availability due to slow diffusion and high fixation in soils. All of this means that P can be a major limiting factor for plant growth.

Root-induced chemical and biological changes in the rhizosphere play a vital role in enhancing the bioavailability of soil P [2]. These root-induced changes mainly involve proton release to acidify the rhizosphere, carboxylate exudation to mobilize sparingly available P by chelation and ligand exchange, and secretion of phosphatases or phytases to mobilize P by enzyme-catalyzed hydrolysis [3].

Some soil and rhizosphere microorganisms can also enhance plant P acquisition by directly increasing solubilization of P to plants, or by indirect hormone-induced stimulation of plant growth [4]. P-solubilizing microorganisms account for approximately 1% to 50% in P solubilization potential [5].

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They may mobilize soil P by the acidification of soil, the release of enzymes (such as phosphatases and phytases), or the production of carboxylates such as gluconate, citrate, and oxalate [6].

In this study, 13 different bacterial and fungal inoculants (so called bio-effectors: BEs) were tested on the basic plant physiological parameters which are the followings: plant height, shoot,- root fresh and dry weight total root length and fractional root length based on root diameter.

2. Material and Methods

The experimental plant was *Zea mays* L. cv. Maxxis (R. A. G. T. Saaten Deutschland GmbH). The experiment was conducted in pots (2 kg soil) under controlled environmental conditions. The seedlings were grown for 30 days in a greenhouse. A low P organic farming soil free of postharvest residues was obtained from the plough depth (top 20 cm) in Kleinhohenheim (research station of Hohenheim University, Stuttgart, Germany) (clay loam pH 6.8, 20 mg CAL-P/kg soil). The soil was moisture until 60 % WHC, water losses were replaced after gravimetric determination (every other day, later on every day). The following basal fertilization was applied: N was applied at the rate 100 mg N kg⁻¹ (Ca(NO₃)₂) in all treatments. There were two non-inoculated controls; one was without added P (Contr.) and the other with added 150 mg P kg⁻¹ (Ca(H₂PO₄)₂) (Contr.+P).

13 bacterial and fungal isolations were tested as BEs. Table 1 shows the applied bacterial and fungal inoculants.

Height of plants was measured on the 9th and 30th days after sowing with folding rule. The dry weight was measured by thermogravimetric method. The samples were dried for three days at 65 °C. Measurement of the root samples was performed with WinRhizo Pro (Regent Instrument, Quebec, Canada), an interactive scanner-based image analysis system. The experiment was arranged in completely randomized design, and the data were analyzed in Sigma Plot version 12.0 version.

Table 1) List of the name of applied products, the treatments short name and the contents of the applied BEs

Name of product	Tr. Short name	BEs	Beneficial effects
Trichoderma-WG	T-WG	<i>Trichoderma harzianum</i>	P-solubilization
OmG-08	T-OmG	<i>Trichoderma harzianum</i>	root growth, P-solubilization
Vitalin T50	T. Vit.T50	<i>Trichoderma harzianum</i>	root growth, P-solubilization
Trianium-P	T-Tria-P	<i>Trichoderma harzianum</i> T22	resistance to diseases and drought stress
Biological Fertilizer DC	P.B.F.-DC	<i>Penicillium sp.</i> PK 112	root and shoot growth stimulation, P-solubilization
Proradix WG	Ps. Pro.WG	<i>Pseudomonas sp.</i> DSMZ 13134	root growth stimulation, resistance to biotic and abiotic stress, mycorrhization, P-solubilization, pathogen suppression
Rhizovital 42	B.am-Rvt	<i>Bacillus amyloliquefaciens</i> FZB42	Root growth stimulation, P solubilization, yield, tolerance biotic (soil borne disease) and abiotic stress
Bacillus simplex R41	Bs.R41	<i>Bacillus amyloliquefaciens</i>	Root growth stimulation at temperatures below 12 °C, yield
Bacillus antrophaeus	B.atr	<i>Bacillus antrophaeus</i>	
<i>Bacillus spec.</i> ,	B. spec	<i>Bacillus spec</i>	
Phylazonit	Phylazo.	<i>Azotobacter chroococcum</i> <i>Bacillus megaterium</i>	P-solubilization
Bactofil	Bacto.	<i>Azospirillum brasilens</i> <i>Azotobacter vinelandii</i> <i>Bacillus megaterium</i> <i>Bacillus polymyxa</i> <i>Pseudomonas fluorescens</i>	
Meganit	Mega.	<i>Sterptomyces albus</i> <i>Azotobacter chroococcum</i> <i>Azospirillum ssp</i> <i>Bacillus megaterium</i> <i>Bacillus subtilis</i>	P-solubilization

3. Results and Discussions

The height of plants was measured on the 9th and 30th days after sowing (DAS). Among all treatments at 9 DAS, there was no difference in plant height between treatments (results are not shown). Among all treatments at 30 DAS, there was no

significant increase in plant height with the inoculation of any bio-effector in comparison to the corresponding control treatment without added P. Among all treatments at 30 DAS, only the non-inoculated control with added P (Contr.+P) was taller than the non-inoculated control without added P (Contr.). Inoculation with *Bacillus spec.* resulted in smaller plant height compared to the control without added P (results are not shown). At the end of the experiment, the dry weight of roots and shoots were measured. The results can be seen in Table 1. The non-inoculated control with added P (Contr.+P) showed significantly higher shoot fresh weight compared to all other treatments. The shoot fresh weight of control with P-fertilization was approx. 22 % higher than the fresh weight of P-deficient value (Contr.). There was no significant difference among other treatment. There was no difference in shoot dry weight among the other treatments.

Wu et al. [7] observed moderate increment in plant biomass due to the increase of nutrients either in chemical or organic form.

The fertilizer effect of plant growth was more pronounced after inoculation of AMF and its combination with beneficial bacteria. The results suggested that the dual inoculation of beneficial bacteria and AM fungi could compensate the nutrient deficiency in soils of maize.

Table 2) Shoot and root fresh and dry weight of maize (g plant^{-1}) inoculated with different bio-effectors (BEs) on 30 day after sowing (DAS). Difference letters show significant difference between treatments (One Way ANOVA, Tukey-test, ^a $p < 0.05$, ^b $p < 0.01$)

Treatments	Shoot FW	Shoot DW	Root FW	Root DW
Contr.	15.864± 0.924 ^b	1.557± 0.137	18.940± 1.429	0.783± 0.063
T-WG	14.356± 0.652 ^b	1.417± 0.056	19.288± 1.201	0.798± 0.047
T-OmG-08	14.276± 0.876 ^b	1.416± 0.095	21.146± 3.438	0.654± 0.115
T-Vit. T50	14.630± 1.225 ^b	1.474± 0.151	20.210± 4.463	0.712± 0.079
T-Tria-P	14.212± 1.569 ^b	1.365± 0.127	17.482± 2.102	0.699± 0.084
P.B.F.-DC	14.958± 0.356 ^b	1.487± 0.048	17.918± 1.444	0.754± 0.041
Ps.-ProWG	15.334± 1.615 ^b	1.558± 0.142	17.748± 1.764	0.853± 0.076
B.am-Rvt	14.868± 1.484 ^b	1.526± 0.161	18.380± 0.763	0.853± 0.067
Bs-R41	15.034± 0.946 ^b	1.508± 0.123	18.168± 2.663	0.799± 0.098
B.atr	16.014± 0.890 ^b	1.622± 0.122	17.458± 2.299	0.819± 0.089
B.spec	14.878± 0.828 ^b	1.527± 0.069	16.280± 1.370	0.792± 0.065
Phylazo	15.254± 0.786 ^b	1.541± 0.115	16.200± 2.278	0.842± 0.052
Bacto.	14.366± 0.786 ^b	1.445± 0.082	16.220± 2.278	0.763± 0.042
Mega.	14.830± 1.112 ^b	1.508± 0.137	16.540± 1.674	0.810± 0.096
Contr.+P	20.342± 1.173 ^a	2.144± 0.117	15.740± 1.673	0.780± 0.081

Root growth and development are sensitive for early P uptake by plants since P is relatively unavailable and immobile in many soils [8]. Root growth depends on the P status of the plant. P deficiency leads to higher root:shoot ratio [9]. Anghinoni and Barber [11] observed increased root length and dry weight on 12-d-old maize when P-deficiency increased between 1 and 6 days. On the other hand, Khamis et al. [12] did not observe an effect of P deficiency on maize root biomass. There are many reports of P fertilization increasing root length and biomass on a wide range of plants (e.g. maize, wheat, bean, cucumber) under different experimental conditions (hydroponic, - soil experiments) [13]. Root architecture refers to the complexity of root system spatial configurations that arise in response to soil conditions [14]. Soil P limitations is a primary effector of root architecture and is known to impact all aspects of root growth and development [15]. Williamson et al. [15] found that growth under P-deficient conditions resulted in a redistribution of root growth from the primary root to lateral roots. Reduced primary root elongation under low P conditions was accompanied by increased lateral root density and elongation. The abundant development of lateral roots associated with P-deficiency induced alterations in root architecture in almost invariable accompanied by increased root hair density and length. Phosphorus helps in development of meristematic tissue, in stimulation of early root growth.

Using the WinRHIZO digital image analysis system allowed for a categorization of the root system length, according to diameter class. Roselem et al. [13] observed that maize with higher efficiency in the acquisition and use of nutrients showed a larger proportion of thin roots. Schenck and Barber [16] suggested that the formation of thinner and longer roots is a mechanism that plants use to increase the nutrient absorption.

Figure 1. shows the total root length of 30-d-old maize treated with different BEs. The total root length was 133.6 - 241.5 m plant⁻¹. The longest root length was measured at T.-Vit.T50 treatment.

This value is higher with approx. 11 % compared to non-inoculated control without additional P-fertilization. There was no significant difference between two non-inoculated treatments. The total root length was significantly shorter at T.-WG compared to both of non-inoculated controls.

Plants are able to respond to P starvation by changing their root architecture, including root morphology, topology, and distribution patterns. Increases in root/shoot ratio, root branching, root elongation, root topsoil foraging, and root hairs are commonly observed in P-deficient plants, while the formation of specialized roots such as cluster roots occurs in a limited number of species [17].

P deficiency has been shown to reduce growth of primary roots and enhance length and density of root hairs and lateral roots in many plant species [17]. The P-efficient genotypes of common bean (*Phaseolus vulgaris*) have more shallow roots in the topsoil where there are relatively high contents of P resources [18]. Some plant species, including white lupin (*Lupinus albus*), can develop cluster roots with dense and determinative lateral roots, which are covered by large numbers of root hairs [19].

Fig. 1. Total root length of maize (m plant⁻¹) inoculated with different BEs on 30 DAS. Different letters show significant difference between treatments (One Way ANOVA, Tukey-test, $p < 0.05$)

Therefore, root architecture plays an important role in maximizing P acquisition because root systems with higher surface area are able to explore a given volume of soil more effectively [19]. The distribution of root length based on diameter is very similar in all treatments (Figure 2). The longest roots diameter class belongs to <0.2 mm. Approx. 82-88 % of total root length belong to the <0.4 mm diameter group.

According to Clarkson and Hanson [19] a root system with a large number of smaller diameter roots is more effective in the absorption of nutrients. Costa et al. [20] observed that the biggest contribution for the total root length came from roots with diameter classes between 0.2 and 0.4 mm.

Pallant et al. [21] reported that 70 % of the roots belongs to the very thin roots classes (<0.5 mm). The biggest distribution to the length of roots with a diameter smaller than <0.5 mm has been believed to be a strategy that the plant uses, in low P availability conditions.

Fig. 2. Distribution of roots according to diameter class (<0.2 mm; 0.2-0.4 mm; 0.4-0.6 mm; 0.6-0.8 mm; >0.8 mm) in maize inoculated with different bio-effectors.

Conclusions

There was no observed significant difference between the two non-inoculated controls in some measured parameters. The shoot fresh and dry weight was higher in the non-inoculated control with additional P-fertilization. But, the root dry and fresh weight was not different under P-deficient and P-sufficient supply. Even though, the P-deficiency should theoretically affect root length, there was no significant difference between the P-deficient (Contr.) and P-sufficient (Cont.+P) control. An explanation could be that the roots tried to darned additional soil to uptake sufficient phosphorus which resulted in a longer root length. The advantages of bacterial and fungal inoculations are not questionable in agriculture, even thought our experiment showed no significant differences. A possible explanation for this is the soil used contained adequate nutrients for the plants, resulting in little differences between two controls. The good availability of nutrients, including phosphorus, could shadow the effect of microorganisms.

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Abbreviations

Bacto: Bactofil, B.am-Rvt: Rhizovital WG, B.atr: Bacillus antrophaeus, B. spec: Bacillus spec., Bs.R41: Bacillus simplex R41, BEs: bioeffectors, Contr: negative control (-P), Contr.+P: positive control (+P), DAS: day after sowing, DW: dry weight, FW: fresh weight, Mega: Meganit, P.B.F.-DC: Biological Fertilizer DC, Phylazo: Phylazonit, Ps. Pro. WG: Proradix WG, T-OmG: OmG-08, T.Vit. T50: Vitalon T50, T-Tria-P: Trianum-P, T-WG: Trichoderma-WG

REFERENCES

- [1] D. Cordell, J. O. Drangert, S. White, *Glob Environ Change* 19, 29-305 (2009)
- [2] P. Hinsinger, *Bioavailability of soil inorganic P in the rhizosphere affected by root-induced chemical changes: a review*. *Plant Soil* **237**, 173-195 (2001)
- [3] G. Neumann and V. Römheld V. (2002). *Plant Roots, The Hidden Half*, (Marcel Dekker, Inc. New York) p. 617-649 (2002)
- [4] A. E. Richardson, J. M. Barea A. M. McNeil, C. Prigent-Combaret, *Acquisition of phosphorus and nitrogen in the rhizosphere and plant growth promotion by microorganisms*. (2009). *Plant Soil* **321**, 305-339 (2009)
- [5] Y. P. Chen, P. D. Rekha, A. B. Arunshen, W. A. Lai, C. C. Young, *Phosphate solubilizing bacteria from subtropical soil and their tricalcium phosphate solubilizing abilities* (2006). *Appl Soil Ecol* **34**, 33-41 (2006)
- [6] D. L. Jones, E. Oburger (2011). *Phosphorus in Action*. (Springer, New York, pp. 169-198 (2011)
- [7] S. C. Wu, Z. H. Cao, Z. G. Li, K. C. Cheung, M. H. Wong, *Effects of biofertilizer containing N-fixers, P and K solubilizers and AM fungi on maize growth: a greenhouse trial*. *Geoderma* 125, 155-166 (2005)
- [8] S. A. Barber, *Soil nutrient bioavailability: a mechanistic approach*. New York, Wiley-Inter Science (1984)
- [9] W. J. Horst, M. Abdon, F. Wiesler, (1996). *Zeitschrift für Pflanzernaehrung und Bodenkunde* **159**, 155-161 (1996)
- [10] I. Anghinoni and S. A. Barber S. A. *Phosphorus Influx and Growth Characteristics of Corn Roots as Influenced by Phosphorus Supply*. *Agronomy Journal* **72**, 685-688 (1980)
- [11] S. Khamis, S. Chaillou, T. Lamaze, *CO₂ Assimilation and Partitioning of Carbon in Maize Plants Deprived of Orthophosphate*. *Journal of Experimental Botany* **41**, 1619-1625 (1990)
- [12] C. A. Roselem, J. S. Assis, A. D. Santiago, *Root growth and mineral nutrition of corn hybrids as affected by phosphorus and lime*. *Communications in Soil Science and Plant Analysis* 25, 2491-2499 (1994)

- [13] J. P. Lynch and K. M. Brown, *Topsoil foraging-an architectural adaptation of plants to low phosphorus availability*. Plant and Soil **237**, 225-237 (2001)
 - [14] L. C. Willianson, S. P. Ribrioux, A. H. Fitter, H. M. *Phosphate availability regulates root system architecture in Arabidopsis*. Leyser, Plant Physiology **126**, 875-882 (2001)
 - [15] N. K. Schenk and S. A. Barber, *Potassium and phosphorus uptake by corn genotypes grown in the field as influenced by root characteristics*. Plant and Soil **54**, 65-76 (1980)
 - [16] J. López-Bucio, A. Cruz-Ramirez, L. Herrera – Estralla, *The role of nutrient availability in regulating root architecture*. Curr Opin Plant Biol **6**, 280-287 (2003)
 - [17] H. Lambers, M. W. Shane, M. D. Cramer, S. J. Pearse, E. J. Veneklaas, *Root Structure and Functioning for Efficient Acquisition of Phosphorus: Matching Morphological and Physiological Traits*. Ann Bot **98**, 693-713 (2006)
 - [18] J. P. Lynch and K. M. Brown K. M. *The Ecophysiology of Plant-Phosphorus Interactions*. (Springer, Dordrecht, The Netherlands, pp. 83-116) (2008)
 - [19] D. T. Clarkson and J. B. Hanson, *The Mineral Nutrition of Higher Plants*. Annual Review of Plant Physiology **3**, 239-298 (1980)
 - [20] C. Costa, L. M. Dwyer, X. Zhou, P. Dutilleul, C. Hamel, L. M. Reid, D. L. Smith, *Root Morphology of Contrasting Maize Genotypes*. Agronomy Journal **94** 96-101 (2002)
 - [21] E. Pallant, R. A. Holmgren, G. E. Schuler, K. L. McCracken, B. Drbal, *Using a fine root extraction device to quantify small diameter corn roots (≥ 0.025 mm) in field soils*. Plant and Soil **153**, 273-279 (1993)
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THE ROLE OF PHOTOSYNTHESIS IN CHOOSING OPTIMAL AGRO-TECHNICAL FACTORS OF AUTUMN CANOLA PRODUCTION

Éva VINCZE¹,

Abstract. *We measure plant physiological parameters in Hybridrock winter oilseed rape hybrid: relative chlorophyll content (SPAD) measurements at seven different date (25.03; 01.04; 11.04; 26.04; 06.05; 24.05; 09.06.2016) in our experiment. The experiment has been set up in the University of Debrecen Látóképi Experimental Station in three different sowing times (I 28.08.2015, II. 12.09.2015 and III. 23.09.2015), three different plant density 200, 350 and 500 thousand ha⁻¹, four replication of the same nutrient supply with using a line spacing of 45 cm. In the experiment the fore crop was winter wheat. The highest yield in the early sowing time was 5475 kg ha⁻¹ (high plant density); the average sowing time was 4485 kg ha⁻¹ (medium plant density) and the late sowing time 4104 kg ha⁻¹ (high plant density). We concluded that the photosynthetic capacity of rape is significantly influenced by the sowing time. On the basis of the Pearson correlation analysis there was significant negative correlation between the sowing time and yield of the hybrid.*

Keywords: winter oilseed rape, yield, LAI, SPAD, PHC

1. Introduction

Oilseed rape is the third most important cultivated oil plant all over the world while second in Hungary after sunflower. Its cultivation area has been increasing since 1990; currently it varies between 200 and 250 thousand ha. Among the technological elements, the appropriate nutrient supply and the optimal sowing time are of especial importance in the oilseed rape production [2]. The optimal selection of the sowing time of oilseed rape is very important for the germination, the development of homogenous stocks and over-wintering. In their experiments, Risnoveanu and Buzdugan [4] found the interval between 5 and 10 September as the optimal sowing time. In the studies of Sharafizadeh et al. [5] the sowing time significantly influenced the yield of oilseed rape. The growth status can be controlled the optimal seeding time and in addition plant density. Péti and Tihany [3] between sowing date and plant density $r = 0.3$ to 0.45 correlation was found. In the domestic research, we can found only limited amounts of experimental data in connection with the nutrient supply and sowing time of oilseed rape [1].

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2. Materials and methods

Our experiments were set up on calcareous chernozem soil in the Hajdúság, 15 km from Debrecen at the Látókép Plant Production Research Site of the University of Debrecen. The soil of the experiment is characterized by favorable physical, chemical and biological traits. The humus content of the calcareous chernozem soil of the experiment is 2.76%, its AL extractable P₂O₅ content is 133 mg kg⁻¹, its AL extractable K₂O value is 240 mg kg⁻¹. The soil has favorable water management conditions. The soil saturated up to the field water capacity can store 578 mm water in the 0-2 m layer, 50% of which is disposable water. The experiment design was set as split-plot, plot areas were 36 m² in four replications and we used Hybridrock hybrid. Three different sowing times (early sowing date: August 28, average: September 12, late: September 23.) were sown in the experimental year (2015). Three different plant densities were set in this year: 200, 350 and 500 thousand plants ha⁻¹. Uniform nutrient supply and a row spacing of 45 cm were applied. Winter wheat was used as pre-crop. We harvested the experimental plots with a SAMPO plot combine harvester.

In the crop year 2015/2016 altogether 694.6 mm precipitation fell during the vegetation of rapeseed (1.08.2015. - 30.06.2016.). This amount was about one and a half times higher than the several years' average value (Table 1.). The significant amount of precipitation in August (84 mm) was higher than the several years' average value (60.7 mm), which enabled the execution of soil preparation works in a rather good quality. September and October were really wet. This was favourable from the aspect of uniform emergence and adequate early development of rapeseed populations. Vegetative development of rapeseed populations was favoured by the weather conditions of autumn months. An amount of precipitation that fell in October (86.6 mm) was higher than the several years' average value (30.8 mm), and the monthly average temperature value (10.0 °C) was similar to the several years' average value (10.3 °C). Measured average temperature at the experimental field was higher in November (5.3 °C) than the average value (4.5 °C). Due to the combined effect of the mentioned factors, just as the optimal applied agrotechnical management rapeseed populations started winter in favourable development stage. Monthly temperature average values were higher than the several years' average values – except for October and May.

Table 12) Amount of precipitation (mm) and temperature (°C) values during rapeseed vegetation period (Debrecen)

Months		VIII.	IX.	X.	XI.	XII.	I.	II.	III.	IV.	V.	VI.	Total/ Average
Precipitation (mm)	2015/2016	84	49	87	43	13	59	79	51	15	69	146	694,6
	30 year's average	60,7	38	31	45	44	37	30	34	42	59	79,5	499,6
Temperature (°C)	2015/2016	23,3	18	10	5,3	2,2	-2,3	5,5	6,4	13	16	20,1	10,6
	30 year's average	19,6	16	10	4,5	-0,2	-3	0,2	5	11	16	18,7	8,9

For the statistical evaluation of the experiment, we used SPSS 13.0 for Windows and Microsoft Excel 2010 programs. The statistical evaluation, the bifactorial variance analysis and correlation analysis were done according to Sváb [6], with regression equations. In the correlation analysis, we determined the following types of correlations according to the r values: $r < 0.4$: loose, $0.4-0.7$: medium, $0.7-0.9$: tight, >0.9 : strong.

3. Results and discussion

The photosynthetic capacity (Ph.C.) is calculated by the formula bellow using the max. SPAD values, max. leaf area (LAI) values and max. yield:

$$Ph.C. = \left(\frac{Yield_{max}}{LAI_{max}} * \frac{Yield_{max}}{SPAD_{max}} \right) / 1000$$

The Ph.C. calculation was done with the average of the hybrid at three sowing time and with all three plant density (Table 2.). Based on the results we concluded that the photosynthetic capacity of rape is significantly influenced by the sowing time. The early sowing time (122, 107, 103) had a significantly higher Ph.C. value than the average sowing time (87, 69, 65) and the late sowing time (77, 47, 59). Yield of the low, medium and high plant density plots was 5160 kg ha^{-1} , 5415 kg ha^{-1} , 5475 kg ha^{-1} ; 4389 kg ha^{-1} , 4485 kg ha^{-1} , 4387 kg ha^{-1} and 4044 kg ha^{-1} , 3408 kg ha^{-1} , 4104 kg ha^{-1} in the early, average and late sowing date.

Table 13) Effect of sowing time and plant density on the photosynthetic capacity of rape (Debrecen, 2016)

Sowing time:	Plant density: (th ha ⁻¹)	Yield (kg ha ⁻¹):	SPAD max:	Date: (d/m)	LAI max:	Date: (d/m)	Ph.C.:
Early (August 28.)	200	5160	55,24	06.05	3,95	06.05	122
	350	5415	63,27	06.05	4,34	06.05	107
	500	5475	63,6	04.26	4,58	04.26	103
Average (September 12.)	200	4389	65,63	04.26	3,37	04.26	87
	350	4485	67,79	04.26	4,31	04.26	69
	500	4387	60,1	04.26	4,92	04.26	65
Late (September 23.)	200	4044	59,5	06.05	3,57	04.26	77
	350	3408	62,97	04.26	3,95	04.26	47
	500	4104	63,04	04.26	4,51	04.26	59

During the correlation measurement (Table 3.), we concluded that there was tight negative correlation ($r=-0,942$) between the sowing time and the yield. There was tight negative correlation ($r=-0,754$) between the sowing time and LAI max value. The tight positive correlation ($r=0,796$) between the yield and LAI max value as well as the medium positive correlation ($r=0,681$) between the photosynthetic activity and yield confirmed that the efficiency of photosynthesis and the size of leaf area have a crucial influence on the yield of rape.

Table 14) Correlation measurement between sowing time and plant density, photosynthetic capacity and yield using the Pearson Correlation (Debrecen, 2016)

	Sowing time	Plant density	Yield	SPAD max	LAI max	Ph.C.
Sowing time	1	0	-,942**	-0,191	-,754*	-0,646
Plant density	0	1	0,078	0,047	0,372	-0,252
Yield	-,942**	0,078	1	0,173	,796*	,681*

** Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

* Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

On the basis of the Pearson correlation analysis (Table 4.) there was significant negative correlation ($r=-0,849$) between the sowing time and yield of the hybrid. Medium negative correlation ($r=-0,602$; $-0,401$) can be noted between 06/05, 24/05, 04.17 at the measurement dates between the sowing time and leaf area index values. With one measurement date medium positive ($r=0,411$) and one measurement date ($r=0,355$) there was loose positive correlation between the sowing time and chlorophyll content values (Table 5.). With two measurement

dates (11/04, 26/04) the results showed tight positive ($r=0,742, 0,782$) and one measurement date (09/06) medium positive correlation (0,480). between the plant density and leaf area index values. There was medium positive correlation ($r=0,626$) at the measurement date of 06/05 and medium positive correlation ($r=0,347$) at 24/05 between the yield and the leaf area index values. Findings showed that there was medium and loose positive correlation ($r=-0,411, 0,355$) between the sowing time and chlorophyll content values at the first two measurement dates. Between the yield and chlorophyll content values there was medium ($r=0,481$) and loose ($r=0,382$) negative correlation at the dates of 25/03, 01/04.

Table 15) Correlation between the analyzed parameters (Debrecen, 2016)

Parameters	Sowing time	Plant density	Yield	LAI measurement dates (2016)						
				25/03	01/04	11/04	26/04	06/05	24/05	09/06
Sowing time	1	0	-,849**	-0,114	-0,095	-0,082	0,004	-0,602**	-,401*	-0,082
Plant density	0	1	0,07	0,236	0,241	,742**	,782**	0,3	0,269	,480**
Yield	-,849**	0,07	1	0,109	0,085	0,046	-0,041	0,626**	0,347*	0,098

** Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

* Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

Table 16) Correlation between the analyzed parameters (Debrecen, 2016)

Parameters	Sowing time	Plant density	Yield	SPAD measurement dates (2016)						
				25/03	01/04	11/04	26/04	06/05	24/05	09/06
Sowing time	1	0	-,849**	,411*	,355*	0,132	-0,024	0,094	0,076	0,028
Plant density	0	1	0,07	0,152	0,158	0,222	0,233	0,151	0,194	-0,097
Yield	-,849**	0,07	1	-,481**	-,382*	-0,108	0,008	-0,129	-0,117	-0,007

** Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

* Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

Conclusions

Based on the results we concluded that the photosynthetic capacity of rape is significantly influenced by the sowing time. The early sowing time had a significantly higher Ph.C. value than the average sowing time and the late sowing time. Yield of the low, medium and high plant density plots was 5160 kg ha^{-1} , 5415 kg ha^{-1} , 5475 kg ha^{-1} ; 4389 kg ha^{-1} , 4485 kg ha^{-1} , 4387 kg ha^{-1} and 4044 kg ha^{-1} , 3408 kg ha^{-1} , 4104 kg ha^{-1} in the early, average and late sowing date. During the correlation measurement, we concluded that there was tight negative correlation between the sowing time and the yield as well as between the sowing time and LAI max value. The tight positive correlation between the yield and LAI max value as well as the medium positive correlation between the photosynthetic

activity and yield confirmed that the efficiency of photosynthesis and the size of leaf area have a crucial influence on the yield of rape. On the basis of the Pearson correlation analysis there was significant negative correlation ($r=-0,849$) between the sowing time and yield of the hybrid. Medium negative correlation can be noted between the sowing time and leaf area index values. Medium positive and loose positive correlation was between the sowing time and chlorophyll content values. The results showed tight positive and medium positive correlation between the plant density and leaf area index values. There was medium positive correlation and medium positive correlation between the yield and the leaf area index values. Findings showed that there was medium and loose positive correlation between the sowing time and chlorophyll content values. Between the yield and chlorophyll content values there was medium and loose negative correlation.

REFERENCES

- [1] Pepó P., 2012, *Kockázatok a repcetermesztésben (Agronomy risks in oilseed rape production)*, Agrofórum, 23, 8, 12-20.
 - [2] Pepó P.-Vincze É. (2015): *Fertilization and sowing time as the environmental risk factors in winter oilseed rape (Brassica napus var. napus f. biennis L.) production*. Analele Universității din Oradea, Fascicula Protecția Mediului, Vol. XXV, 2015, Anul 20, 61-68; ISSN 1224-6255
 - [3] Péti L.-né, Tihanyi F.: 1978. *A repce termésátlagát befolyásoló tényezők vizsgálata regressziószámításokkal*. Gazdálkodás. Gazdálkodás 1978. 22 (12), 25-28.
 - [4] Risnoveanu L., Buzdugan L., 2011, *Some aspects the influence of sowing time of winter oilseed rape production in the conditions north-east Baragan*, Lucrari Stiintifice, Universitatea de Stiinte Agricole Si Medicina Veterinara „Ion Ionescu de la Brad” Iasi, Seria Agronomie, 54, 1, 163-169
 - [5] Sharafizadeh, M., Gholizadeh, M. R. E., Aryannia, N., Razaz, M. (2012): *Effect of planting date and planting pattern on quality and quantity of canola hybrid seed (Hayola 401)*. Adv. Environ. Biol., 6, 2184–2189.
 - [6] Sváb J. (1981) *Biometriai módszerek a kutatásban*. Mezőgazdasági Kiadó. 171-179.
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THE EFFECT OF USING ZEOLITE ON SOME CHARACTERISTICS OF SANDY SOIL AND ON THE AMOUNT OF THE TEST PLANT BIOMASS

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Abstract. *Different doses (5; 10, 15; 20 t ha⁻¹) of zeolite were studied on humous sand soil, on some soil physical, chemical, microbial characteristics and on the biomass of a test plant ((Lolium perenne L.). The zeolite can have a positive impact on properties of weak soil fertility and can exert advantageous influence with more complex changes of soil characteristics. In terms of efficiency, to use the 15 and 20 t ha⁻¹ doses can be recommended. The use of zeolite as soil natural amendment can safely inserted into a sustainable land use system.*

Keywords: zeolite, humous sand, soil characteristics, plant biomass

1. Introduction

The zeolite mineral association is one of the most used and researched clay minerals which can significantly contribute to the preservation of soil fertility [1, 2].

Zeolites are aluminium-silicates, the two most important of their components the clinoptilolite- and mordenite- tectosilicates. By properties zeolites are applied in agriculture on field of the horticulture and landscape architecture, communal waste- [3, 4] as well as in the field of water management [5]. As a fertilizer, it has an advantageous effect on soil pH (it reduces the soil acidity) and the availability of microelements [6]. It enhances water uptake by plants and the water management of soils [7]. In agriculture are used as amendments of soil improvement, as well as component in gardening soil mixtures, and excipient in compost productions [8]. The zeolites are applied to seedlings, rooting and intensive horticulture [9]. They have a positive effect on nutrient-supplying system, and development of plants [10].

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Due to these reasons above experiments were carried out with zeolite, and we studied the effect of zeolite on some soil characteristics on humous, acidic sand soil, and how it influences the amount of test plant biomass.

2. Material and methods

The experiment was set up in the greenhouse of Institute of Agricultural Chemistry and Soil Science. We examined the effect of increased dose of zeolite on some physical, chemical properties and some microbial features of an sandy soil and on the biomass of a test plant was measured in controlled conditions.

The soil type of experiment was: humous sand soil type of Pallag. The pH of the cultivated layers was weakly acidic ($\text{pH}_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}$ 6.52) and low in humus ($\text{Hu}\%=1.6\%$).

The zeolite treatments were set up in year 2014 in three kg, bottom perforated pots. Zeolite treatments are shown in the Table 1.

Table 1) Treatments and the applied doses of the pot experiment (Debrecen, Hungary, 2014)

Number of treatments	Treatments	Doses (t ha^{-1})
0	Control	0
1	Small-dose	5
2	Middle-dose	10
3	Middle-large dose	15
4	Large dose	20

Water content of treatments was kept on the same level, which is 70% of the maximum water-holding capacity. The pots were watered in every day to the same mass. Basic treatments 50 mg nitrogen – as $\text{Ca}(\text{NO}_3)_2$ solution – and 50 mg P_2O_5 and 50 mg K_2O as potassium dihydrogen orthophosphate and potassium sulphate solution were given to every pot.

Among the soil physical parameters the soil moisture content [11], the water holding – and permeability capacity were measured [12]. Among the chemical parameters the pH in suspension of distilled water and M KCl [$\text{pH}_{(\text{H}_2\text{O})}$; $\text{pH}_{(\text{KCl})}$] [13], to concern to the soil nutrient content the nitrate nitrogen-, the ammonium lactate-acetate soluble phosphate and potassium content of soil were determined [14]. Among the microbiological parameters the total countable numbers of bacteria (in meat soup agar), the number of microscopic fungi (in peptone glucose agar) was measured by plate dilution method [15]. The soil respiration [16], the activities of phosphatase [17], dehydrogenase enzyme [18] were determined.

As test plant the perennial rye grass (*Lolium perenne L.*) was used, cutted in twice a year. Plant biomass was given in g pot^{-1} dry mass basis.

By statistical analysis F-test analysis of variance was performed at $p=5\%$ level. The applied method was the Duncan – test. We labeled the distinctnesses between

the treatments with the little letters of the alphabet in the tables. Statistical calculations by SPSS 13.0 for Windows and Microsoft Office Excel programs were carried out.

3. Results

The soil physical properties will be shown firstly, followed by the results of pH and available nutrient content and the microbiological parameters, finally the biomass quantity of the perennial ryegrass as test plant.

Among the physical soil properties (Table 2.) the moisture content changed between 17.71 and 19.18% due to the controlled circumstances, it proved satisfactory in the pot experiment.

Based on our results, along the one year application of increasing zeolite doses did not influence on the water holding capacity and the water permeability of soil significantly. But it can be stated that the water holding capacity slightly increased in the soil, at the same time the water permeability decreased in all treatments compared to the control.

Table 2) The effect of zeolite on some soil water management properties (Debrecen, Hungary, 2014)

Number of treatments	Moisture content (%)	Water holding capacity (%)	Water permeability (ml 10 sec ⁻¹)
0	17.71 a	17.00 a	63.93 a
1	18.07 a	17.70 a	52.67 a
2	18.80 a	17.48 a	56.33 a
3	17.88 a	17.57 a	61.27 a
4	19.18 a	18.06 a	58.40 a

The soil pH – measured in distilled water - changed (Table 3.) favourably in some treatments. The treatment of 10 and 20 t ha⁻¹-the soil pH increased, so positive change was caused in the pH. The soil pH in KCl-suspension increased in all treatments and in the treatment of the 5 t ha⁻¹ dose the effect of zeolite was significantly positive.

Table 3) The effect of zeolite on some chemical properties of soil (Debrecen, Hungary, 2014)

Number of treatment	pH _(H₂O)	pH _(KCl)	Nitrate-N (mg 1000 g ⁻¹)	AL-P ₂ O ₅ (mg 1000 g ⁻¹)	AL-K ₂ O (mg 1000 g ⁻¹)
0	6.52 a	5.29 a	6.18 a	267.58 a	266.25 a
1	6.61 a	5.43 b	5.65 a	271.05 a	294.77 a
2	6.85 b	5.39 ab	6.88 a	273.43 a	281.11 a
3	6.55 a	5.30 a	10.13 b	331.2 b	301.76 a
4	6.68 ab	5.38 ab	10.22 b	317.63 b	372.04 b

The available nutrient content of the sandy soil (Table 3.) proved to be well stocked. The treatments of the zeolite doses usually increased the nitrate-N content, the AL-soluble phosphorus content and the AL-soluble potassium content in soil. The treatments in the 15 és 20 t ha⁻¹ doses of zeolite the increase were experience significant positively, except for potassium content the treatments in 15 t ha⁻¹.

Influence of zeolite treatments soil microbiological parameters varying degrees changed (Table 4.). The number of total bacteria increased significantly in the treatments of 5, 10, 15 t ha⁻¹, also the activity of phosphatase enzyme in the 15 and 20 t ha⁻¹ treatments.

Also slightly increased the number of microscopic fungi and activity of dehydrogenase enzyme in all treatments. Among the effect of different doses there was no difference. The soil respiration also increased slightly in the applied 15 and 20 t ha⁻¹ zeolite doses, but it can not be proved statistically.

Table 4) The effect of zeolite on some microbial properties of soil (Debrecen, Hungary, 2014)

No. of treatment	Total number of bacteria (*10 ⁶ g ⁻¹ soil)	Microscopic fungi (*10 ³ g ⁻¹ soil)	Soil respiration (CO ₂ mg 100 g ⁻¹ 10 days)	Phosphatase enzyme (mg P ₂ O ₅ 100g ⁻¹ 2h ⁻¹)	Dehydrogenase enzyme (INTF µg g ⁻¹ 2h ⁻¹)
0	4.67 a	50.47 a	5.89 a	2.38 a	33.00 a
1	5.54 ab	58.70 a	5.96 a	2.51 a	33.73 a
2	6.86 b	64.13 a	5.67 a	1.99 a	37.80 a
3	5.64 ab	65.47 a	6.09 a	4.08 b	36.53 a
4	5.22 a	55.95 a	6.21 a	5.95 c	36.53 a

Fig. 1. The effect of zeolite on the biomass of the test plant – perennial ryegrass (*Lolium perenne*, L.) (Debrecen, Hungary, 2014)

In the season, the total quantity of ryegrass was determined on the basis of the sum of two cuttings (Figure 1.). The results showed differences between the control and the treatments.

The grass mass increased even in the treatment of 5 t ha⁻¹ dose, but the largest increase was measured in the pots treated by 20 t ha⁻¹ zeolite. The biomass of the test plant in both treatments was increased significantly, its quantity was larger by 5-14%, than it was in the control pots.

4. Conclusion

The water holding capacity slightly - not significantly - increased, at the same time the water permeability decreased in all zeolite treated soil compared to the control.

The soil acidity decreased by the effect of zeolite, the soil nitrate-N and available phosphorus content increased significantly in the 15; 20 t ha⁻¹ doses of zeolite. The AL-soluble potassium also increased in the large dose of treatment.

Among the microbiological properties of soil the total number of bacteria was the most sensitive parameter and the activity of phosphatase enzyme increased significantly in the 15; 20 t ha⁻¹ treatments. Lower effect of zeolite was measured on the quantity change of microscopic fungi and dehydrogenase activity. The values of soil respiration did not change significantly in the treatments.

Based on the one-year results the total plant biomass quantity of ryegrass test plant was more by 5-14%, than it was in the control pots.

The zeolite as a natural material safely fits into the sustainable land use system, the largest, 20 t ha⁻¹ dose of zeolite can be recommended as the most efficient dose on sand soil.

REFERENCES

- [1] Kátai, J., Tállai, M., Sándor, Zs., Zsuposné, O. Á., *Effect of Bentonite and Zeolite on some characteristics of acidic sandy soil and on the biomass of a testplant*. Agrokémia és Talajtan. Special Issue (ed. Gy. Várallyay) Akadémiai Kiadó. 165-174 p. (2010).
- [2] Kátai, J., Zsuposné, O. Á., Tállai, M., *Application of Zeolite in the sustainable land use. Article Book*. (Ed. Evgeny Shein) International Soil Science Congress on "Soil Science in International Year of Soils 2015" 10.19. - 10.23. 2015. Sochi, Russia. 191-194. (2015).
- [3] Madjid, D., Babak E. B., Hossein K., *Using zeolitic adsorbents to cleanup special wastewater streams*. A rev. Microporous and Mesoporous Materials. Vol. **214**, 224. (2015).

- [4] Zhitong, Y., Daidai, W., Jie, L., Weihong, W., Hongting, Z., Junhong, T., *Recycling of typical difficult-to-treat e-waste: Synthesize zeolites from waste cathode-ray-tube funnel glass*. Journal of Hazardous Materials. Vol. **324**, Part B. 673. (2017).
- [5] Moradzadeh, M., Hadi Moazed, H., Sayyad, G., Mohammadreza Khaledian, M., *Transport of nitrate and ammonium ions in a sandy loam soil treated with potassium zeolite – Evaluating equilibrium and non-equilibrium equations*. Acta Ecologica Sinica, Vol. **34**, Iss. 6, 342. (2014).
- [6] Bernardi, A. C. D., De Souza, G. B., Polidoro, J. C., Paiva, P. R. P., Monte, M. B. D. M., *Yield, Quality Components, and Nitrogen Levels of Silage Corn Fertilized with Urea and Zeolite*. Comm. in Soil Sci. and Plant Anal. Akad. Kiadó, Bp. 42 (**11**): 1266. (2011).
- [7] Ippolito, J. A., Tarkalson, D. D., Lehrs, G. A., *Zeolite Soil App. Method Affects Inorganic Nitrogen, Moisture, and Corn Growth*. Soil Sci. Vol: **176**. Iss: 3. 136. (2011).
- [8] Lateef, A., Nazir, R., Jamil, Alam, S., Shah, R., Naeem, Khan, M., Saleem, M., *Synthesis and characterization of zeolite based nano-composite: An environment friendly slow release fertilizer*. Microporous and Mesoporous materials. Vol. **232**. 174. (2016).
- [9] Azadeh, M., Akbar, S., Mohammad, Z., Kassae, M. F., *Synthetic nanozeolite/nanohydroxyapatite as a phosphorus fertilizer for German chamomile (Matricaria chamomilla L.)*. Industrial Crops and Products. Vol. **95**. 444. (2017).
- [10] Mahmoodabadi, M. R., *Experimental Study on the Effects of Natural Zeolite on Lead Toxicity Growth, Nodulation, and Chemical Composition of Soybean*. Communications in Soil Science and Plant Analysis. Vol: **41**. Iss: 16. 1896. (2010).
- [11] Klimes-Szmik A., *A talajok fizikai tulajdonságainak vizsgálata*. In: *Talaj- és trágyavizsgáló módszerek (Sz: Ballenegger R. & Di Gléria J.)* Mezőg. Kiadó. 83. (1962).
- [12] Vér F., *A talaj szerkezetének és vízgazdálkodásának vizsgálata, eredeti szerkezetű talajmintán, Vér-féle szerkezeti mintavevő csövekben*. Mg. Kiadó. 37. (1961).
- [13] Filep Gy. *Talajvizsgálat. Egy. jegyzet*. Debrecen, 32., 68.; 96., 105. (1995).
- [14] Egner, H., Riehm, H., Domingo, W. R., *Untersuchungen über die chemische Bodenanalyse als Grundlage für die Beurteilung des Nährstoffzustandes der Böden. II. K.* LandbrHöghsk. Ann. **26**. 199. (1960).
- [15] Szegi J. *Talajmikrobiológiai vizsg. módszerek*. Mg. Kiadó, Bp. 250. (1979).
- [16] Witkamp, M., *Decomposition of leaf litter in relation to environment microflora and microbial respiration*. Ecology, **47**. 194. (1966).
- [17] Krámer, M., Erdei, G., *Primenyeniye metoda opregyeleniya akgyivnosztyi foszfatazui v agrohimicheskikh issledovaniyah*. Pochvovedeniye. (**9**) 99. (1959).
- [18] Schinner, F., Öhlinger, R., Kandeler, E., Margesin, R., *Methods in soil biology*. 93. (Springer-Verlag, Berlin. 1996).
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CHANGES IN GREEN WEIGHT PRODUCTION AND IN SOIL NUTRIENT SUPPLYING CAPACITY IN CASE OF ORGANIC AND NPK FERTILIZED ONION CULTIVATIONS

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Abstract. *In our comparative greenhouse experiment we examined the effect of EM-1 microbial yield enhancing vaccine, an organic cow manure and an NPK fertilizer on the nutrient supplying capacity of the soil. The test plant was onion (*Allium cepa* L.) and the applied soil was humic sandy soil. The wet and dry matter production and the element content of plant samples were also determined, from which the element uptake was calculated. We also determined the amount of readily available nutrients in the soils of several treatments. The 0.01M CaCl₂ soluble K, Mg, Mn, NO₃⁻-N, NH₄⁺-N, organic-N, total-N contents, pH of soil, and the AL soluble P₂O₅, K₂O, Ca, Mg of soil also were determined. The increasing effect of NPK fertilizer on the yield was greater than that of organic manure and EM-1 + straw. The green mass production of NPK fertilized plants were withdrawn from most of the soil nutrient. In the growing season the soil pH reduced as an effect of NPK fertilizers, which can cause problems in further cultivations. Organic fertilization had a positive effect on the mineralization of nutrients in the soil.*

Keywords: onion, fertilization, mineralization

1. Introduction

The main task of today's agriculture is to ensure sufficient and appropriate quality food and to generate industrial raw material. Nutrients uptaken by yield is replaced mainly by fertilizers in addition to organic fertilizers which improper use or overdose can be harmful to the environment [1]. The application of high doses of fertilizers can cause soil acidification [2, 3, 4, 5].

Soil pH has a direct or indirect effect on the life of plants, on the quantity and quality of their yields. Its direct effect prevails on the dissolution of nutrients and their uptake. The indirect effect of soil pH is the influence of the life of soil microbes which modify the mobilization of nutrients.

Today, it is important for farmers to decrease or eliminate the environmental load and the use of chemicals. From this concern environment-friendly organic farming methods evolved out in our country and throughout the developed world,

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which retain and even improve soil fertility without the use of chemical products [6, 7, 8, 9]. It maintains soil structure and the balance of soil organisms. The increase of organic matter in soil reduces the leaching of mineral nutrients.

The organic farming has very strict rules. Organic plants can not be treated with synthetic chemicals (fertilizers, pesticides). The nutrient supply is provided by organic manure, green manure and bacterial products, and biological pest control can only be used [10, 11].

The question can be raised whether plants are able to uptake the required amount of nutrients in all developmental stages in organic production. Thus in our paper we compared the crop yields and the nutrient supply capacity of soils from organic cultivation versus integrated cultivation

2. Material and Methods

A pot experiment was carried out in spring 2015 at the University of Debrecen in Hungary. The test plant was onion (*Allium cepa* L.) The main physico-chemical characteristics of the soil are shown in Table 1.

Table 1) The characteristics of humic sandy soil from Pállag

Humusz %	1.4
pH (CaCl ₂)	5.84
CaCl ₂ -os NO ₃ ⁻ /N (mg kg ⁻¹)	6.15
CaCl ₂ -os NH ₄ ⁺ /N (mg/kg)	1.91
CaCl ₂ -os szerves N (mg/kg)	7.55
CaCl ₂ -os összes N (mg/kg)	15.6
CaCl ₂ -os K (mg/kg)	159
CaCl ₂ -os Mg (mg/kg)	9.65
CaCl ₂ -os Mn (mg/kg)	11.75
AL-P ₂ O ₅ (mg/kg)	274
AL-K ₂ O (mg/kg)	286.6
AL-Ca (mg/kg)	1185
AL-Mg (mg/kg)	117

Based on the data the soil nutrient supply is the following: moderate for nitrogen, good for potassium, and high for phosphorus. [12, 1]

During the experiment, 60 pots were used, we filled the pots with 2.5 kg soil and sown 4 onions per pots. 15 pots got (NPK) fertilizer application, another 15 pots treated with organic cattle manure (BIO.1.), and again 15 pots with wheat straw and yield enhancing vaccine (EM-1) (BIO.2.), 5 pots got no treatment (control). The applied treatments are shown in Table 2.

Table 2) Applied treatments

Treatments	Nutrient dose (g/pot)
NPK	0.25 g N 0.15 g P ₂ O ₅ 0.27 g K ₂ O
BIO.1.	0.25 g N 0.15 g P ₂ O ₅ 0.27 g K ₂ O
BIO.2.	0.25 g N 0.11 g P ₂ O ₅ 0.6 g K ₂ O
CONTROL	-

Nitrogen and phosphorus are added to the soil as ammonium dihydrogen phosphate and ammonium nitrate solution and potassium was added as potassium chloride solution. We tried to apply the same amount of nutrients by BIO.1. treatment with mature cattle manure and by BIO.2. treatment with wheat straw. The breakdown of straw was enhanced by the EM-1. vaccine. EM-1. is a microbial yield enhancing vaccine that contains useful and effective microorganisms in high concentration and in high spectrum of bacteria species. It contains micro and actinomycetes and various symbiotic bacteria in nearly equal proportions. So it enhances N fixation and P exploration.

Onion sets were planted.

Soils were kept at constant moisture by daily irrigation at 60% of field water capacity.

The onion was harvested as green onions. Soil and plants samples were collected at this time.

For determining P and K contents, first homogenized plant samples (0.5 g each sample) were digested with cc. 5 cm³ H₂SO₄ and 5 cm³ H₂O₂ in a heating block digester, at 220 °C until full digestion. Then phosphorus was quantified by colorimetrically with phosphomolybdovanadate method using a spectrophotometer. [13] Potassium content was determined by flame atom emission spectrophotometry. For determining Ca, Mg and Mn contents, homogenized plant samples (0.5 g each sample) were digested with cc. 10 cm³ HNO₃ until full digestion. Amount of Ca, Mg and Mn were determined by atomic absorption spectrophotometry using a Varian SpectrAA-10 Plus spectrophotometer.

The total nitrogen content of plants was measured by dry combustion method [14].

Concentrations of water soluble nitrogen forms were measured in 0.01 M CaCl₂ extracts after 2 h shaking with 1:10 soil:solution ratio [15]. NO₃⁻, NH₄⁺ and total N was determined by Contiflo device, the organic-N concentration was calculated as the difference between total nitrogen and inorganic nitrogen (NO₃⁻+NH₄⁺) as described by Houba et al. [16]. The pH of the 0.01 M CaCl₂ extract was measured with glass-calomel combination electrode (Radelkis OP-0808P digital pH meter), and Mg and Mn contents were determined by atomic absorption spectrophotometer (Varian AA10 Plus).

Phosphorus content of the AL extract [17] was measured with UV-VIS spectrophotometer [17], while the amount of K, Ca and Mg was measured with flamephotometer (Unicam SP90B) and by atomic absorption spectrophotometer.

Significant differences were examined by One way Anova test using the statistical package of Microsoft Excel.

3. Results and Discussion

3.1. The yield results

Table 3 shows the wet mass of onion in case of the different treatments. It can be seen that the yield increased in all treatments compared to the control. The yield increasing effect of fertilizers was higher than that of organic manure and the EM-1 + straw application. The NPK fertilization increased the yield mass significantly compared to the control treatment as well as to the BIO.1., BIO.2. treatment, while the yield increasing effect of BIO.1. and BIO.2. treatments can not be proven statistically.

Table 3) Wet matter content and the amount of nutrients extracted from the biomass plant

QUANTITY	CONTROL	NPK	BIO.1.	BIO.2.
Wet weight (g)	193.1	342.7	210.9	197.3
LSD _{5%}	70.10			
N (mg)	571.2	1013	623.9	592.3
LSD _{5%}	205.5			
P (mg)	101.5	108,9	77.08	83.13
LSD _{5%}	14.71			
K (mg)	652.9	887,2	590.8	620.7
LSD _{5%}	132.6			
Ca (mg)	184.6	315,8	191.8	187.8
LSD _{5%}	62.65			
Mg (mg)	43.95	77.73	46.93	44.82
LSD _{5%}	15.97			
Mn (mg)	29.42	44.19	30.27	30.12
LSD _{5%}	6.99			

Discernible, to produce higher green mass the plants took more nutrients from the soil up. The fertilized plants were withdrawn from most of the fertilising element from the soil. The NPK - control treatments between quantities (excluding P), the difference is statistically justified. The BIO.1. and BIO.2. treatments plant tendency more nitrogen, calcium, magnesium and manganese were withdrawn from the soil than in the control plants.

3.2. The results of 0.01 M CaCl₂ soil extracts

From the data of Table 4 it can be concluded that the different treatments changed the soil pH variously.

At the beginning of the experiment the soil pH was 5.84 and in case of control and BIO.2. treatments it decreased slightly, while the NPK fertilization acidified the soil significantly. The application of organic manure (BIO.1. treatment) increased soil pH, it became more favorable to the end of the experiment. The effect of NPK and BIO.1. treatments on soil pH were statistically justifiable compared to the control by the end of the season.

At the end of the vegetation period the 0.01 M CaCl₂ soluble total N contents of soil show large differences in the treatments (Table 4). At the beginning of the growing season the amount of added nitrogen was the same for all treatments, but the added N forms were different. By NPK treatment the amount of yield was higher than that of the other two treatments and the control, therefore the plant withdrew more nitrogen from the soil here. Based on our results however we can conclude that the most 0.01 M CaCl₂ soluble total nitrogen content remained in case of this treatment. This result can be explained by the fact that most of the N forms of BIO.1. and BIO.2. treatments was not directly available for the plants thus it was in 0.01 M CaCl₂ soluble form nor at the beginning neither at the end of the experiment. Our results show that the EM-1 vaccine contributed to the degradation of straw in soil, since 0.01 M CaCl₂ soluble total N content of the BIO.2. treatment was greater than that of the BIO.1. treatment and the control.

The method of nutrient supply also affects the amount of 0.01 M CaCl₂ soluble nitrogen forms. In case of NPK treatment the largest amount of nitrogen is in nitrate- ion, while at the BIO.1., BIO.2. treatments and control the dominant N forms were organic forms and ammonium ion.

Comparing the soil 0.01 M CaCl₂ soluble K contents it can be stated that by the end of the growing season, the K contents reduced in all treatments compared to the initial K contents although this element was replaced. We found no significant difference between the K content of control and the treatments. The different fertilization treatments resulted differences in soil 0.01 M CaCl₂ soluble K contents as well.

Table 4) The pH and N - K- Mg - Mn -concentrations (0.01M CaCl₂ extraction) in the soils with different fertilizers

0.01M CaCl₂ extraction	CONTROL	NPK	BIO.1.	BIO.2.
pH	5.17	5.6	6.11	5.63
LSD _{5%}	0.37			
N (mg kg⁻¹)	4.612	52.62	5.142	10.15
LSD _{5%}	23.71			
NO₃⁻/N (mg kg⁻¹)	0.101	44.23	0.312	0.101
LSD _{5%}	21.62			
NH₄⁺/N (mg kg⁻¹)	1.372	4.471	1.262	4.031
LSD _{5%}	1.551			
organic N (mg kg⁻¹)	3.233	3.922	3.588	6.122
LSD _{5%}	1.377			
K (mg kg⁻¹)	107.1	154.7	144.1	124.6
LSD _{5%}	20.68			
Mg (mg kg⁻¹)	9.051	8.702	9.603	9.164
LSD _{5%}	0.367			
Mn (mg kg⁻¹)	8.601	14.31	5.401	6.421
LSD _{5%}	3.901			

Among the measured nutrients we did not add magnesium and manganese to the soil with the fertilizer (NPK) treatments, but organic cattle manure (BIO.1.) and straw (BIO.2.) contained the former two elements. Our results also support this. The results of the experiment showed that the soil CaCl₂ soluble Mg content in the organic treatments (BIO.1.-2.) hardly reduced by the end of the growing season (Table 4. The lowest Mg concentration was measured by NPK fertilization. The initial concentration (9.65 mg kg⁻¹) decreased by almost 10%. This result also shows that the integrated production mode should take care of the Mg nutrient replacement as well.

For Mn it can be stated that although the NPK fertilized plants removed the most Mn from the soil yet at the end of the experiment, the easily available Mn content was the greatest in case of these treatments. The high Mn content that was more than at the beginning of the experiment (11.75 mg kg⁻¹), can be explained by the acidification of soil. Our result is statistically justified.

3.3. The results of AL soil extracts

Table 5 shows the AL soluble phosphorus content of the soils at the various treatments. It can be seen that the soil P content increased compared to initial state (274 mg kg⁻¹) except for the control.

P reserve was remained at the end of the growing season from the different nutrient supplying methods. Compared to the control it is statistically justified.

The soils treated with NPK fertilizer contained less AL- P_2O_5 than the soils of BIO.1. and BIO. 2. treatments, which can be explained by the higher yield. The difference between BIO.1 and BIO.2. treatments, which was not statistically justified, can be explained by the fact that straw contains proportionately less P.

Table 5) The P_2O_5 -, K_2O -, Ca – and Mg -concentrations (AL extraction) in the soils with different fertilizers

AL extraction	CONTROL	NPK	BIO.1.	BIO.2.
P_2O_5 (mg kg ⁻¹)	262.4	285.3	292.2	286.6
LSD _{5%}	12.87			
K_2O (mg kg ⁻¹)	239.7	303.0	291.3	251.1
LSD _{5%}	30.02			
Ca (mg kg ⁻¹)	964.1	968.7	1127	1320
LSD _{5%}	164.7			
Mg (mg kg ⁻¹)	111.1	116.3	133.3	115.6
LSD _{5%}	9.567			

The AL soluble potassium content (Table 5) of the soils at the various treatments. According to it, the AL soluble K contents increased significantly at the end of the growing season compared to the initial K content (286.6 mg kg⁻¹) for NPK treatment and organic cattle manure treatment (BIO. 1.). The AL-soluble potassium content increased parallel with the 0.01 M $CaCl_2$ soluble K content. The AL-soluble Ca content of soils due to the decreased production (exception:BIO.2). In the control and NPK treatments the change large. In the BIO.1. treatment of the decline is smaller.The straw treatment plants (BIO.2.) less amounts of calcium were withdrawn from the soil, such as NPK and BIO.1. treatment plants. Straw also contains calcium, the EM-1 helped the Ca into the soil. Of soil the BIO. 2. treatment more quantities contained than other treatments.The effect is statistically justified.

The AL-soluble Mg content of soils due to the decreased production (exception: BIO.1.).

Conclusions

Based on our results the yield increasing effect of NPK fertilizer on the yield was greater than that of organic manure and EM-1. + straw. In the applied fertilizers the nutrients are present in readily available form, while in mature organic fertilizer and wheat straw the nutrients can be only utilized after transformation by soil microorganisms. Thus on the basis of our experimental results it can be concluded that organic manures and stalks must be applied sooner, than fertilizers. To produce higher green mass the plants took more nutrients from the soil up.

The NPK - control treatments between quantities (excluding P), the difference is statistically justified.

In the growing season the soil pH reduced as an effect of NPK fertilizers, which can cause problems in further cultivations. In case of organic treatments (BIO.1. és BIO.2.) the soil pH increased slightly so that the soil properties in the next growing season became more favorable. The way of nutrient supply influences the amount of 0.01M CaCl₂ soluble total nitrogen, the quality and quantity of nitrogen forms. Contrary to NPK treatment in case of BIO.1. and BIO.2. treatments even at the end of the experiment most of the N forms was not in 0.01 M CaCl₂ soluble form, that is readily available for plants. Our results show that the EM-1 vaccine contributed to the degradation of straw in soil. The different fertilization treatments resulted in differences in soil 0.01 M CaCl₂ soluble K concentrations as well. At the end of the growing season the soil CaCl₂-soluble Mg content for organic treatments (BIO.1.-BIO. 2.) declined only slightly, whereas for NPK fertilizer the decline was nearly 10%. This result also shows that the integrated production mode should take care of the Mg nutrient replacement as well. By the end of the experiment the 0.01 M CaCl₂-soluble Mn content of the soils increased in spite of the increased plant uptake, which can be explained by the acidifying effect of fertilizers. In case of a soil with poor pH buffering capacity the long term use of NPK fertilizers can cause Mn dissolution to such an extent which can be toxic for plants. This problem does not arise by organic fertilized soils.

The 0.01 M CaCl₂ soluble nutrient contents of the soil are proportional to the AL soluble nutrients. The AL soluble phosphorus content of the soils at the various treatments increased compared to initial state. The AL soluble K contents increased significantly at the end of the growing season compared to the initial K content. The AL-soluble potassium content increased parallel with the 0.01 M CaCl₂ soluble K content. The AL-soluble Ca and Mg content of soils the end of the growing season due to the decreased.

REFERENCES

- [1] Loch J., Nosticzius Á., *Agrokémia és növényvédelmi kémia*, Mezőgazda Kiadó, Budapest, Magyarország, 1992.
 - [2] Chander H., Abrol I. P., *Effect of three nitrogenous fertilizers on the solution composition of a saline sodic soil*. Communications in Soil Science and Plant Analysis, **3**, **1**. 51-56, 1972.
 - [3] Felizardo B. C., Benson N. R., Cheng H. H., *Nitrogen, salinity, and acidity distribution in an irrigated orchard soil as affected by placement of nitrogen fertilizers*. Soil Science Society of America. Proceedings, **36**. 803-808, 1972
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-
- [4] Nagy P. T., *A trágyázás hatása a 0,01 M kalcium-kloridban oldható nitrogén-formák mennyiségének változására*. Agrártudományi Közlemények **10**. 166-170, 2003.
- [5] Nagy P.T., Lazányi J.; Loch J., *Comparative analysis of chemical and biological soil examination to determine the plant available N content of soil in the Nyírlugos long term field experiments*. Joint International Conference on Long-term Experiments, Agricultural Research and Natural Resources. 226-233, 2007.
- [6] Shen D. G., *Microbial diversity and application of microbial products for agricultural purposes in China*. Agriculture Ecosystems & Environment **62**. 237-245, 1997.
- [7] Zsuposné Á. O., *Changes of biological activity in different soil types*. Cereal Research Communications, **35**. **2**. 861-864, 2007.
- [8] Mäder P., Fliessbach A., Dubois D., Gunst L., Fried P. M., Niggli U., *Soil fertility and biodiversity in organic farming*. Science. **296**. 5573, 2002. <http://orgprints.org/5514>
- [9] Gabriel D., Roschewitz I., Tschardt T., Thies C., *Beta diversity at different spatial scales. Plant communities in organic and conventional agriculture*. Ecological Applications. **16**. S. 2011–2021, 2006.
- [10] Wyss E., *Gebärfreudige Blattläuse halten Bioforscher auf Trab*. Tätigkeitsbericht Forschungsinstitut für biologischen Landbau, CH-Frick. S. 12, 2004.
- [11] Wu, S. C.; Cao, Z. H.; Li, Z. G.; Cheung, K. C.; Wong, M. H., *Effects of biofertilizer containing N-fixer, P and K solubilizers and AM fungi on maize growth: a greenhouse trial 2005*. Geoderma, **125**, 1-2, 155-166, 2005.
- [12] Buzás I., Fekete A., *Műtrágyázási irányelvek és üzemi számítási módszer*. MÉM NAK. Budapest, 1979
- [13] Tahmm F.-né, Krámer M., Sarkadi J., *Növények és trágya-anyagok foszfortartalmának meghatározása ammonium-molibdovanadátos módszerrel*. Agrokémia és Talajtan, **17**, 145-156, 1968.
- [14] Nagy P.T., *Égetéses elven működő elemvizsgáló alkalmazhatósága talaj- és növényvizsgálatokban*. Agrokémia és Talajtan, **49**. 3-4, 521-534, 2000.
- [15] Jászberényi I., Loch J., Sarkadi J., *Experiences with 0.01 M CaCl₂ as an extraction reagent for use as a soil testing procedure in Hungary*. Communications in Soil Science and Plant Analysis, **25**. 1771–1777, 1994.
- [16] Houba V.J.G., Novozamsky I., Temminghoff E., *Soil and plant analysis. Part 5A. Soil analysis procedures extraction with 0.01 M CaCl₂* – Wageningen Agricultural University Wageningen 12-22, 1994.
- [17] Egner H., Riehm H., Domingo W.R., *Untersuchungen über die chemische Bodenanalyse als Grundlage für die Beurteilung des Nährstoffzustandes der Böden*. Kungl. Lantbrukshögsk. Ann., Uppsala, **26**. 199-215, 1960.
- [18] Buzás I., *A talajok fizikai-kémiai és kémiai vizsgálati módszerei*. Mezőgazdasági Kiadó, Budapest, Magyarország, 1988.
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EFFECT OF MOLYBDENUM TREATMENTS ON GROWTH AND MOLYBDENUM UPTAKE OF GREEN PEA

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Abstract. *The main aim of the present study was to examine whether increasing molybdenum (Mo) concentration affects on the growth and Mo uptake of green pea plants (*Pisum sativum* L.) in pot experiment. In addition it was determined how much percent of the soil's total Mo content can be utilized for plants (soluble element content). In this experiment three types of soil were applied (calcareous chernozem soil, carbonate humus sandy soil, humus sandy soil) and Mo was used in form of sodium molybdate dissolved in distilled water.*

In this study we have found that there is a close connection between the acidity of different types of soil and the Lakanen-Erviö's soluble Mo concentration. According to our results 30 mg kg⁻¹ Mo treatment affected positively on growth of plants in case of calcareous chernozem and acidic humus sandy soil however, in the case of carbonate humus sandy soil this Mo-treatment caused significant reduction in plant growth. Furthermore we observed, molybdenum concentration in green peas were significantly elevated with increasing the concentration of Mo treatment in comparison with control.

Keywords: molybdenum, green pea, soil, dry weight

1. Introduction

Molybdenum is one of the seven microelements which is essential for the plants. Its relevance of plant physiology primarily lies in the fact that it is a necessary metal component of enzymes participating in nitrogen-metabolism [1]. On the one hand, it has a decisive role in the nitrogen supply of Fabaceae as the co-factor of the nitrogenase enzyme, on the other hand, it has an essential role in the process of nitrate reduction, since the presence of molybdenum is essential in order that the nitrate reductase could function optimally [2-3].

Absorption of Mo by plants occurs in the form of molybdate ion. Whenever molybdate anion enters into the roots, it stays biologically inactive until it is joined by a pterin compound which is called molybdenum cofactor (Moco) [4-5].

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The availability of molybdenum for plant growth strongly depends on the soil pH. In acidic soils which has less than 5.5 pH, molybdenum availability goes down when anion adsorption to soil oxides goes up. On the other hand, in alkaline soils, molybdenum are more soluble and is accessible to plants especially when it is in its anion form as MoO_4^- [6-7].

The objective of our study was to examine whether molybdenum treatments affects the dry mass and molybdenum concentration of green pea plants (*Pisum sativum* L.) in pot experiment. In addition it was determined how much percent of the soil's total molybdenum content can be utilized for plants (soluble molybdenum content).

2. Materials and methods

Pot experiment was carried out in the Greenhouse of Institute of Agricultural Chemistry and Soil Science in University of Debrecen, in the spring of 2015. In this experiment green pea (*Pisum sativum* L.) was chosen as test plant since its molybdenum need is significant and it is one of the vegetables grown in the largest area in Hungary.

Three types of soil were applied in this experiment:

- 1.) calcareous chernozem soil (pH=6.58) – Faculty of Agricultural and Food Sciences and Environmental Management at University of Debrecen, Látókép Experimental Station of Plant Production
- 2.) carbonate humus sandy soil (pH=7.14) – University of Debrecen, Pallag Experimental Station of Horticulture
- 3.) acidic humus sandy soil (pH=5.09) – College of Nyíregyháza, Ferenctanya Educational Farm

Molybdenum was added to the soil in the form sodium molybdate ($\text{Na}_2\text{MoO}_4 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$) dissolved in distilled water. In the case of calcareous chernozem soil (Látókép) we applied 0, 3, 30, 90 és 270 mg kg^{-1} molybdenum treatments, in the case of carbonate humus sandy soil (Pallag) and the acidic humus sandy soil (Nyíregyháza) the applied treatments included the following: 0, 30 and 270 mg kg^{-1} . We did not add molybdenum to the control soil.

Element analysis of plant samples was carried out with inductively coupled plasma optical emission spectrometry (ICP-OES) and inductively coupled plasma mass spectrometry (ICP-MS) [8]. Wet digestion with nitric acid and hydrogen peroxide was applied during sample preparation of these plants [9]. The elemental analysis of soil samples can be divided to two main components which are the following: 1. The determination of the total element content of the samples with atmospheric wet digestion using concentrated nitric acid and hydrogen peroxide [10]. 2. The determination of the samples' soluble element content easily available for plants using the extraction tool by Lakanen-Erviö [11]. Afterwards, we measured the element

content of the appropriately prepared samples using the abovementioned ICP-OES equipment.

For the statistical analysis One-Way analysis of variance (ANOVA) and Duncan's test were used. The significance was evaluated at the $P < 0.05$ level. The statistical analyses were carried out using SPSS v.22.0 software.

3. Results

During our results of soil analysis it was established that due to the Mo-treatments with increasing concentration, the total molybdenum content of the soil and Lakanen-Erviö soluble molybdenum content that can be utilized by the plants showed a significant increase but difference was found in the soluble Mo concentration of different types of soils (Table 1). In the case of the soil of Nyíregyháza (sour humus sand) with the smallest pH value (pH=5.09) 26-29%, in the case of the soil of Látókép (calcareous chernozem) (pH=6.58) 44-56%, while in the case of the soil of Pallag (carbonate humus sand) with the largest pH value (pH=7.14) 62-67% of the total molybdenum was available to the plants.

Table 1) Total molybdenum and Lakanen-Erviö soluble molybdenum content (mg kg^{-1}) of soil of Látókép, Pallag and Nyíregyháza

Mo-treatment (mg kg^{-1})	Total Mo (mg kg^{-1}) (A)	Lakanen-Erviö soluble Mo (mg kg^{-1}) (B)	B/A
Látókép (pH=6.58)			
0	<LOD	0.069 ± 0.010^a	-
3	2.96 ± 0.05^a	1.67 ± 0.06^a	0.564
30	27.3 ± 4.2^b	12.1 ± 0.2^b	0.443
90	87.2 ± 2.2^c	43.2 ± 1.0^c	0.495
270	265 ± 5^d	141 ± 12^d	0.532
Pallag (pH=7.14)			
0	<LOD	0.080 ± 0.022^a	-
30	27.4 ± 2.5^a	18.4 ± 0.4^b	0.672
270	272 ± 2^b	169 ± 9^c	0.621
Nyíregyháza (pH=5.09)			
0	<LOD	0.036 ± 0.006^a	-
30	30.2 ± 1.0^a	8.74 ± 0.20^b	0.289
270	281 ± 4^b	74.3 ± 2.0^c	0.264

The values with different alphabetical index are significantly ($P < 0.05$) different within the individual columns. Abbreviations: LOD=limit of detection. $n=3 \pm \text{s.e.}$

The results of our research on dry weight of green pea plants are summarized in Tables 2-4. The results showed that the growth of the green peas treated with molybdenum is considerably determined by the type and acidity of the used soil. In case of Látókép and Nyíregyháza soil, the 30 mg kg^{-1} Mo-treatment increased significantly the dry matter product of the plant in most cases, but the 270 mg kg^{-1} Mo-treatment hindered the

growth of peas. However, in the case of green peas cultivated in the soil of Pallag the Mo-treatment did not caused an increase in any dry mass product which as we see it is the consequence of the extra-high molybdenum accumulation arising from the soil's nearly neutral pH value. In addition, it was found that the application of the 270 mg kg⁻¹ Mo-dose not only hindered the growth of peas but also led to the destruction of plants.

Table 2) Dry weight (g plant⁻¹) of individual plant's part of green pea plants grown in the calcareous chernozem soil of Látókép in case of different molybdenum treatments (0, 3, 30, 90, 270 mg kg⁻¹)

Mo-treat. (mg kg ⁻¹)	Dry weight (g plant ⁻¹) of green pea plant grown in soil of Látókép				
	Leaf	Stem	Root	Pod	Seed
0	0.4640±0.1238 ^a	0.3829±0.0759 ^a	0.0687±0.0023 ^{ab}	0.2326±0.0697 ^a	0.2092±0.0190 ^a
3	0.5022±0.0776 ^a	0.3948±0.0513 ^a	0.0806±0.0064 ^{bc}	0.2489±0.0306 ^a	0.2123±0.0505 ^a
30	0.7956±0.0993 ^b	0.7475±0.1335 ^b	0.0898±0.0108 ^c	0.3259±0.0373 ^a	0.2333±0.0557 ^a
90	0.5193±0.1411 ^a	0.5490±0.2454 ^{ab}	0.0519±0.0137 ^a	0.2501±0.0563 ^a	0.1895±0.0595 ^a
270	0.3787±0.0861 ^a	0.3118±0.1202 ^a	0.0537±0.0172 ^a	0.2370±0.0453 ^a	0.1737±0.0430 ^a

The values with different alphabetical index are significantly (P<0.05) different within the individual columns. n=3±s.e.

Table 3) Dry weight (g plant⁻¹) of individual plant's part of green pea plants grown in the carbonate humus sandy soil of Pallag in case of different molybdenum treatments (0, 30, 270 mg kg⁻¹)

Mo-treat. (mg kg ⁻¹)	Dry weight (g plant ⁻¹) of green pea plant grown in soil of Pallag				
	Leaf	Stem	Root	Pod	Seed
0	0.3290±0.6436 ^a	0.4526±0.1084 ^a	0.0613±0.0074 ^a	0.3077±0.0126 ^a	0.2263±0.0334 ^a
30	0.2121±0.7021 ^b	0.2373±0.0935 ^b	0.0396±0.0137 ^b	0.2363±0.0344 ^b	0.1487±0.0238 ^b
270	-	-	-	-	-

The values with different alphabetical index are significantly (P<0.05) different within the individual columns. n=3±s.e.

Table 4) Dry weight (g plant⁻¹) of individual plant's part of green pea plants grown in in acidic sandy soil soil of Pallag in case of different molybdenum treatments (0, 30, 270 mg kg⁻¹)

Mo-treat. (mg kg ⁻¹)	Dry weight (g plant ⁻¹) of green pea plant grown in soil of Nyíregyháza				
	Leaf	Stem	Root	Pod	Seed
0	0.1938±0.0030 ^a	0.2202±0.0543 ^a	0.0409±0.0096 ^a	0.1968±0.0038 ^a	0.2343±0.0769 ^a
30	0.2440±0.0185 ^b	0.3218±0.0421 ^b	0.0587±0.0042 ^b	0.2451±0.0128 ^b	0.2706±0.0285 ^a
270	0.1961±0.0289 ^a	0.2194±0.0261 ^a	0.0480±0.0113 ^{ab}	0.2067±0.0099 ^{ab}	0.2384±0.0500 ^a

The values with different alphabetical index are significantly (P<0.05) different within the individual columns. n=3±s.e.

In Tables 5-7. changes of Mo concentration in individual plant's part of green pea plants depending on Mo treatments that has been shown. This results showed that the Mo-treatments increased the Mo accumulation of peas and the effect of treatment was verifiable in all parts of the pea plants. We couldn't only observed a significant increase in the vegetative organs between the control and the 3 mg kg⁻¹ treatments. In addition, the results of green peas cultivated in different types of soil affirm the fact

that the capability to uptake Mo is primarily determined by the soil's acidity. Since the only utilizable Mo form for the plants is the molybdate anion (MoO_4^{2-}) which is available depending on pH and can be absorbed in a much larger quantity from alkaline soils. Accordingly, during this experiment we established that the treated plants accumulated the largest amount of molybdenum from the soil with the largest pH value (Pallag; pH=7.14), while the smallest amount from the Nyíregyháza soil with the smallest pH value (pH=5.09), the results show a close conjunction with the Lakanen-Erviö's soluble Mo contents.

Table 5) Mo concentration (mg kg^{-1}) of individual plant's part of green pea plants grown in the calcareous chernozem soil of Látókép in case of different molybdenum treatments (0, 3, 30, 90, 270 mg kg^{-1})

Mo-treat. (mg kg^{-1})	Mo concentration (mg kg^{-1}) of green pea plant grown in soil of Látókép				
	Leaf	Stem	Root	Pod	Seed
0	2.85±0.10 ^a	4.01±0.42 ^a	10.0±0.9 ^a	2.61±0.14 ^a	4.82±0.52 ^a
3	7.21±1.73 ^a	12.0±0.1 ^a	11.0±0.3 ^a	15.5±4.0 ^b	5.62±0.38 ^a
30	119±3 ^b	187±15 ^b	337±40 ^b	48.3±5.9 ^c	42.6±1 ^b
90	483±33 ^c	431±17 ^c	964±27 ^c	134±7 ^d	131±3 ^c
270	1050±41 ^d	822±2 ^d	1322±132 ^d	165±9 ^c	200±6 ^d

The values with different alphabetical index are significantly ($P<0.05$) different within the individual columns. $n=3\pm s.e.$

Table 6) Mo concentration (mg kg^{-1}) of individual plant's part of green pea plants grown in the carbonate humus sandy soil of Pallag in case of different molybdenum treatments (0, 30, 270 mg kg^{-1})

Mo-treat. (mg kg^{-1})	Mo concentration (mg kg^{-1}) of green pea plant grown in soil of Pallag				
	Leaf	Stem	Root	Pod	Seed
0	2.39±0.02 ^a	6.45±0.21 ^a	34.5±4.9 ^a	8.47±2.45 ^a	5.19±0.54 ^a
30	1886±85 ^b	1183±57 ^b	3473±146 ^b	305±5 ^b	253±6 ^b
270	-	-	-	-	-

The values with different alphabetical index are significantly ($P<0.05$) different within the individual columns. $n=3\pm s.e.$

Table 7) Mo concentration (mg kg^{-1}) of individual plant's part of green pea plants grown in in acidic sandy soil of Nyíregyháza in case of different molybdenum treatments (0, 30, 270 mg kg^{-1})

Mo-treat. (mg kg^{-1})	Mo concentration (mg kg^{-1}) of green pea plant grown in soil of Nyíregyháza				
	Leaf	Stem	Root	Pod	Seed
0	1.79±0.04 ^a	3.15±0.38 ^a	5.61±0.58 ^a	1.93±0.19 ^a	6.25±0.96 ^a
30	61.3±1.2 ^b	74.8±4.5 ^b	294±2 ^b	26.1±6.2 ^b	32.5±0.1 ^b
270	711±13 ^c	449±20 ^c	2558±23 ^c	140±7 ^c	170±5 ^c

The values with different alphabetical index are significantly ($P<0.05$) different within the individual columns. $n=3\pm s.e.$

Conclusion

In this study we have found that there is a close connection between the acidity of different types of soil and the Lakanen-Erviö's soluble molybdenum concentration.

According to our results 30 mg kg⁻¹ Mo treatment affected positively on growth of plants in case of calcareous chernozem and acidic humus sandy soil however, higher content reduced the dry mass of green pea. In the case of carbonate humus sandy soil 30 mg kg⁻¹ Mo treatment caused significant reduction in plant growth and application of the 270 mg kg⁻¹ Mo led to the destruction of plants.

In addition, we observed that molybdenum concentration in green peas were significantly elevated with increasing the concentration of molybdenum treatment in comparison with control.

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REFERENCES

- [1] R. L. Hamlin, *Molybdenum* In: A.V. Barker, D. J. Belbeam (eds.) *Handbook of Plant Nutrition* (Taylor and Francis Group, New York, USA, 2007).
 - [2] I. Yaneva et al., *J. Pant. Physiol.* **149**, 211-216 (1996).
 - [3] M. Anke and M. Seifert, *Acta Biol. Hung.* **58**, 3, 311-324 (2007).
 - [4] R. R. Mendel and T. Kruse, *Biochim. Biophys. Acta.* 1568-1579 (2012).
 - [5] F. Bittner, *Front. Plant. Sci.* **5**, 28 (2014).
 - [6] B. N. Kaiser et al., *Ann. Bot.* **96**, 745-754. (2005).
 - [7] K. J. Reddy et al. *Chemistry and mineralogy of molybdenum in soils*. In: U. C. Gupta (ed.) *Molybdenum in agriculture*, (Cambridge University Press, Cambridge, United Kingdom, 1997).
 - [8] B. Kovács et al., *Comm. Soil Sci. Plant. Anal.* **29**, 11-14. 2035-2054 (1998).
 - [9] B. Kovács et al., *Comm. Soil Sci. Plant. Anal.* **27**, 5-8. 1177-1198 (1996).
 - [10] B. Kovács et al., *Comm. Soil Sci. Plant. Anal.* **31**. 11-14. 1949-1963 (2000).
 - [11] MSZ 21470-50. *Környezetvédelmi talajvizsgálatok. Az összes és az oldható toxikuselem-, a nehézfém- és a króm (VI) tartalom meghatározása* (Magyar Szabványügyi Testület, Budapest, Hungary, 2006).
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EFFECTS OF ORGANIC FERTILIZERS ON THE GROWTH AND NUTRIENT UPTAKE OF CUCUMBER (*CUCUMIS SATIVUS* L.) SEEDLINGS

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Abstract. *Pot experiment was conducted to compare the effects of organic fertilizers on growth, phosphorus and potassium uptake of cucumber. The study was conducted on humic sandy soil with treatments of 1: control; 2:horse manure with straw (30t/ha); 3:horse manure with sawdust (30t/ha); 4: cattle manure (30t/ha); 5: food waste compost (30t/ha); 6-9 organic fertilizers with 60t/ha. The effects of fertilizers were investigated after a month and 5 further months incubation period. Fresh weights of cucumber seedlings were not greatly influenced by manures and compost, but phosphorus and potassium uptake were significantly enhanced. Horse manure with straw, food waste compost and cattle manure proved to be effective and horse manure with sawdust was the least effective organic fertilizer in terms of growth of cucumber seedlings and nutrient supply ability.*

Keywords: organic fertilizers, cucumber seedlings, nutrient

1. Introduction

Use of organic manure is one of the oldest methods of soil cultivation [1]. Manure may help in the improvement of soil structure, the physico-chemical, microbiological properties of soil, may improve the quantity and quality of the yield, through increasing microbial activity and plant nutrients of soils [2, 3]. Organic fertilizers besides containing high level of organic matter also contain macro- and micronutrients [4, 5].

In recent years the application of organic fertilizers has received great attention in sustainable agriculture [6]. They might have been major components of organic farming, which offer an economically and ecologically attractive means of reducing external inputs and improving internal resources [7, 8]. Different kinds of organic amendments including farmyard manure [9], composts [10] have been

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applied to enhance both crop yield and soil quality all over the world. The expression of “solid manure” means when farmed animals are kept on bedding material which is collected together with all excreta. Farmed animals might be a variety of animals like pig, horse, cattle, etc. Quality and composition of manures from various domestic animals are mostly significantly different. These are also influenced by bedding materials and composting process of organic manures as well.

The stalls of horses are bedded to absorb urine, moisture, and gases and to increase the comfort, health, and well-being of horses [11]. Bedding materials may be recycled book paper, sawdust and straw. Straw and sawdust are the most common materials used as main or extra bedding [12]. Bedding has effects on the volume and quality of manure. The management and composting of horse manure can be improved by choosing bedding material. Differences have been found in the process of composting horse manure bedding with sawdust or straw [13, 14]. The horse manure with different bedding materials using as organic fertilizer may have different effect on the soil properties and on the yield.

Food waste is large component of the waste stream in Hungary. Restaurants, food factories and canteens of schools produce million tons of commercial organic waste that may be composted. This compost may represent one of the alternatives for achieving the goal of ensuring integrated and sustainable waste management [15, 16]. Food waste compost is generally higher in nutrient values and lower in other contamination than most types of composts, thus making it more valuable in the market [17, 18].

The main goal of this study was to investigate the effects of organic manures with different origin (horse, cattle), various bedding materials (straw, sawdust) and diverse doses (30t/ha, 60t/ha) and the impact of food waste compost on the growth and nutrient uptake of cucumber seedlings.

2. Materials and method

The pot experiment was performed on humic sandy soil with cucumber seeds. The examined organic fertilizers were cattle and horse manures. Horse manure was produced with different bedding materials, namely straw and sawdust. The effects of manures were compared to the effect of food waste compost. Compost was obtained from restaurant food residuals. Food residuals were mixed with wood waste and were composted for 90 days. Organic amendments were mixed with humic sandy soil at two different doses, 30t/ha and 60t/ha. The 150g soil-manure mixture were put into pots. The main properties of soil were: pH(CaCl₂): 6.01; K_A:26 (Soil plasticity index according to Arany, described [19]; Hu %: 1.3; AL-P₂O₅:274mg/kg; AL-K₂O: 286 mg/kg. The treatments were the follow: 1: control; 2: horse manure with straw, 30t/ha; 3: horse manure with sawdust, 30t/ha; 4:

cattle manure, 30t/ha; 5: food waste compost, 30t/ha; 6: horse manure with straw, 60t/ha; 7: horse manure with sawdust, 60t/ha; 8: cattle manure, 60t/ha; 9: food waste compost, 60t/ha.

Organic fertilizers with different doses were mixed with the soil thoroughly one month before starting the experiment. The main characteristics of different organic fertilizers are described in Table 1.

Table 1) Characteristics of organic fertilizers applied

	N%	C%	C/N	AL-P ₂ O ₅ mg/kg	AL-K ₂ O g/100g
horse manure with straw	3.87	31.90	8.24	820	4.030
horse manure with sawdust	0.980	11.64	11.88	730	0.939
cattle manure	2.31	27.22	11.79	670	1.359
food waste compost	0.841	13.65	16.22	714	0.673

Ion exchanged water was added to all pots to keep the soil at constant moisture (60% of the water-holding capacity) using daily weighing. Soil-manure mixture had been incubated at room temperature and constant moisture for four weeks. After four weeks incubation period pot experiment was started. Ten seeds of cucumber “Rajnai fűrtös” were sown in all pots. The seedlings had been grown for eight days after sowing. After the first germination experiment all pots had been incubated again at room temperature and constant moisture for five further months (totally six-month incubation) in order to organic matter could be able to mineralise. After incubation period the germination experiment were repeated again as the same way as the first experiment.

Fresh weights and after drying at 60 °C, dry weights of leaves per pots were determined in both germination experiments. Leaves after drying were digested by H₂SO₄-H₂O₂ methods and phosphorus and potassium were measured. P was measured by colorimetrically using the molybdenum blue colorimetric method, potassium was quantified by flame emission spectrophotometry. The P and K uptake of plant per pot were counted from data of fresh weights and P and K contents of seedlings.

Analysis of variance was carried out on the data by SPSS statistics 1.3 program in order to provide a statistical comparison between the treatment means. The mean differences among treatments were analyzed through Tukey post hoc test. Significant differences (P < 0.05) between treatments in figures are indicated by different letters.

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Growth of cucumber seedlings response to soil-fertility treatments

Germination experiments were taken after a month and after five further months after fertilizers applications. The changes of fresh weights of seedling of cucumber in the first and second germination experiments are presented in Figure 1.

*Significant differences ($P < 0.05$) between treatments are indicated by different letters

Fig. 1. Means of fresh weights of seedling in the first and second germination experiments (g/pot)

Fresh weights of seedling ranged between 2.48-4.2 g/pot after one month of organic fertilizers application. Although there were no significant differences between values of different organic manure treatments compared to control, it is worth to mention that the value of horse manure with sawdust in 30t/ha dose tended to be a little bit lower and the other horse manure with straw tended to be a little bit higher than the control. The higher doses (60t/ha) of fertilizers did not alter the weights of cucumber compared to lower ones.

After cutting cucumber plants, all pots were incubated for five further months and the germination experiment was repeated. In that case the weights of seedlings were higher and ranged between 2.53-5.5 g/pot. All fertilizers except for horse manure with sawdust in 30t/ha dose, slightly increased the growth of seedlings. Horse manure with sawdust caused a small decrease in values compared to control and other treatments. Organic fertilizers in 60t/ha dose did not cause further change in weights compared to values with 30t/ha.

3.2. Phosphorus and potassium uptake of cucumber seedlings

The values of phosphorus uptake of cucumber seedlings as a function of different treatments in first and second germination experiments are presented in *Fig. 2*.

*Significant differences ($P < 0.05$) between treatments are indicated by different letters

Fig. 2. Means of phosphorus uptake of seedlings in first and second germination experiments (mg/pot)

Phosphorus uptake of plants varied between 0.97-1.46 mg/pot in the first germination experiment. Among fertilizers with 30t/ha dose the highest value (1.45 mg/pot) was resulted by horse manure with straw and the lowest one (0.97mg/pot) caused by food waste compost. The 60t/ha dose of horse manures did not alter the P uptake of plant compared to values of lower dose. The higher dose of cattle manure and food waste compost significantly increased the P uptake of cucumber compared to values of 30t/ha dose of fertilizers.

As a result of five-month incubation period the phosphorus supply ability of fertilizers increased. The P uptake of seedling increased in all treatments except for in the treatment of horse manure with sawdust (30t/ha). The highest P uptake (1.98 mg/pot) of plant was measured in the treatment of food waste compost (30t/ha). 60t/ha dose of compost did not increased further the P uptake of plant. The lowest value appeared in treatment with horse manure with sawdust, but the 60t/ha dose of this fertilizer significantly increased the P uptake compared to control. Cattle manure with 30t/ha dose also significantly increased P uptake of plant compared to control, and the higher dose further increased this value.

Potassium uptake of cucumber plants as a function of different treatments in the first and second germination experiments are presented in Fig. 3.

*Significant differences ($P < 0.05$) between treatments are indicated by different letters

Fig. 3. Means of potassium uptake of seedlings in first and second germination experiments (mg/pot)

The potassium uptake of plants varied between 3.21-6.16 mg/pot in the first germination experiment. Among fertilizers with 30t/ha dose the highest value was resulted by horse manure with straw (5.96 mg/pot) followed by value of cattle manure (5.06 mg/pot). 60t/ha dose of these fertilizers did not enhance further the potassium uptake of plants.

After five months further incubation period the potassium supply ability of organic fertilizers increased except for horse manure with sawdust and ranged between 2.45-8.48 mg/pot. Highest K uptake of plants was measured in treatments of horse manure with straw and food waste compost. The 60t/ha dose of horse manure with straw further increased the values, but compost did not caused further change. Cattle manure with 30t/ha dose also significantly increased K uptake of plant compared to control, and higher dose further increased this value.

Conclusions

Organic fertilizers did not cause significant effect on growth of cucumber seedling at the beginning of the growth, only small changes were detected in values. Horse manure with straw, cattle manure and compost in 30t/ha dose tended to enhance growth while horse manure with sawdust caused slightly reduced weights. 60t/ha

dose of fertilizers did not influence growth values compared to values of lower dose.

Organic fertilizers increased phosphorus and potassium uptake of seedling. After a month of fertilizers application horse manure with straw supplied the highest amount of phosphorus and potassium compared to control and other treatments. After five months further incubation period the P and K uptake of plants increased except for in the treatment of horse manure with sawdust where the phosphorus uptake of plants decreased. After longer incubation period of fertilizer-soil mixture the highest nutrient uptake were resulted in treatments of food waste compost and horse manure with straw, followed by value of cattle manure. 60t/ha dose of these fertilizers further increased nutrient uptake in most cases.

Favourable effect of horse manure with straw, cattle manure and food waste compost with 30t/ha dose was justified, but positive effects of horse manure with sawdust could not be proved.

REFERENCES

- [1] Jongtae, L, *Effect of application methods of organic fertilizer on growth, soil chemical properties and microbial densities in organic bulb onion production*. Scientia Horticulturae, **124**. 3. 299-305. (2010).
 - [2] Clark, M.S., Horwath, W. R., Shennan, C., Scattle, K. M., *Changes in soil chemical properties resulting from organic and low-input farming practices*. Agron J. **90**. 662–671. (1998).
 - [3] Liebig, M. A., Doran, J.W., *Impact of organic production practices on soil quality indicators*. J. Environ. Qual. **28**. 1601–1609. (1999).
 - [4] Cayuela, M.L., Sinicco, T. Mondini C., *Mineralization dynamics and biochemical properties during initial decomposition of plant and animal residues in soil*. Appl. Soil Ecol., **41**. 118–127. (2008).
 - [5] Alabadan, B. A., Adeoye, P. A. and Folorunso, E. A., *Effects of different poultry wastes on physical, chemical and biological properties of soil*. Caspian J. Environ. Sci., **7**: 31-35. (2009).
 - [6] Irshad, M., Yamamoto, S., Eneji, A. E., Endo, T., Honna, T., *Urea and manure effect on growth and mineral contents of maize under saline conditions*. Journal of Plant Nutrition, **25**. 1. 189-200. (2002).
 - [7] Saxena, A. K., Tilak, K. V. B. R., *Interaction among beneficial soil microorganisms*. Indian J. Microbiol., **34**, 91–106. (1994).
 - [8] Pathak, D. V., Khurana, A. L., Singh, S., *Biofertilizers for enhancement of crop productivity – a review*. Agric. Rev., **18**. 155–166. (1997).
-

-
- [9] Hati, K. M., Mandal, K. G., Misra, A. K., Ghosh, P. K., Bandyopadhyay, K. K., *Effects of inorganic fertilizer and farmyard manure on soil physical properties, root distribution, and water-use efficiency of soybean in Vertisols of central India*. Bioresource Technology, **97**. 16. 2182–2188. (2008).
- [10] Sharpley, A., Moyer, B., *Phosphorus forms in manure and compost and their release during simulated rainfall*. Journal of environmental quality. **29**. 5. 1462-1469. (2000).
- [11] Saastamoinen, M., Särkijärvi, S., Hyypä, S., *Reducing Respiratory Health Risks to Horses and Workers: A Comparison of Two Bedding Materials*. Animals 5, 965-977. (2015).
- [12] Breum N.O., Nielsen B.H., Lyngbye M., and Midtgard U. *Dustiness of chopped straw as affected by lignosulfonate as a dust suppressant*. Ann Agric Environ Med, **6**(2): 133-140. (1999).
- [13] Fleming, K., Hessel, E. F., van de Weghe, H. F. A., Orof, Dr. Ir., *Evaluation of Factors Influencing the Generation of Ammonia in Different Bedding Materials Used for Horse Keeping*, Journal of Equine Veterinary Science, **28**. 4. 223–231. (2008).
- [14] Airaksinen, S.; Heinonen-Tanski, H.; Heiskanen, M. *Quality of different bedding materials and their influence on the compostability of horse manure*. J. Equine Vet. Sci., 21, 125–130. (2001).
- [15] Elherradi, E., Soudi, B., Chiang, C., Elkceimi, K., *Evaluation of nitrogen fertilizing value of composted household solid waste under greenhouse conditions*. Agronomy for sustainable development **25**. (2). 169-175. (2005).
- [16] Cegarra, J., Albuquerque, A., González, J., Tortosa, G., D. Chaw, D. *Effects of the forced ventilation on composting of a solid olive-mill by-product (“alperujo”) managed by mechanical turning*, Waste Manage. 26. 1377–1383. (2006).
- [17] Roberts, P., Edwards-Jones, G., Jones, D.L. *In-vessel cocomposting of green waste with biosolids and paper waste*, Compost Science and Utilization. **15**. 272–282. (2007).
- [18] Chang, J. I., Tin-En, Hsu. *Effects of compositions on food waste composting*. Bioresource Technology, **99**. 17. 256-278. (2008).
- [19] Buzás, I. *Talaj - és agrokémiai vizsgálati módszerkönyv 1*. INDA 4231 Kiadó, Budapest. (1993).
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EFFECT OF DIFFERENT ARSENIC-TREATMENTS ON THE DRY WEIGHT OF VEGETATIVE PLANT PARTS OF GREEN PEA IN THE DIFFERENT PHENOPHASE OF THE PLANT DEVELOPMENT

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Abstract. *The objective of our study was to investigate the effect of arsenate and arsenite on dry weight of root, stem and leaves of green pea in the four different growth phases (four-node condition, the beginning of flowering, green ripening, and complete maturity) of the plant development. As a results of our experiment shows, in some cases there were significant differences beetwen the effect of As(III)- and As(V)-treatmnets. Based on the data, in the case of the all phenophase, As(III)-treatments has a negatvive effect on the dry mass of vegetative plant parts. According to the results, in the case of the first phenopase the 3 mg kg⁻¹ As(V)-treatments, in the case of the further phenophase the 3 and 10 mg kg⁻¹ As(V)-treatment increased, but the higher concentration of As(V) decreased the dry mass of leaves and stem. However, the dry weigth of root was sightly increased in the first and second phenophase of the plant development as a result of the 3 mg kg⁻¹ As(V)-treatmnet, the dry mass of root was negatively effected by the As(V)-treatments.*

Keywords: arsenite, arsenate, green pea, dry weight, pot experiment

1. Introduction

Arsenic (As) is a toxic element that is found naturally in soils all over the world [1]. Most environmental arsenic problems are the result in mining activities, use of arsenical herbicides and insecticides, irrigation with arsenic contaminated groundwater and some other agricultural and anthropogenic factors [2, 3, 4, 5]. The pollution of soil and groundwater with arsenic is a serious environmental problem all over the world [4, 6]. Arsenic is non-essential moreover toxic to

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plants [5, 7]. The phytotoxicity of arsenic depends on the form of the arsenic speciation and just only secondarily depends on the total concentration [8]. Inorganic arsenic forms are usually more toxic to plants, than organic compounds [9]. Arsenic in soil mostly found as inorganic form, namely arsenate [As(V)] and arsenite [As(III)]. Both are easily taken up by the cells of the plant root [10, 11]. Excessive uptake of arsenic by plants have led to physiological changes [12, 13]. Arsenic could inhibit the normal growth of the plants with toxicity symptoms such as morphological changes [14, 15] reduction of the plants productivity [16, 17] and loss of biomass [18].

The objective of this study was to investigate the physiological response of green peas to different As-treatments, evaluated by the parameters of dry mass of shoot, root, leaves, peas and pods in the four different phase of plant development.

2. Materials and methods

The pot experiment was carried out in calcareous chernozem soil was collected from the Látókép Experimental Station of the University of Debrecen. The parameters of the experimental soil were published previously by Kovács et al. (2015) [19]. 11 kg soil was weighed into each pot. The soil was air dried, sieved and additional NPK fertilization was applied (Table 1).

Table 1) Doses of NPK-fertilizer was applied in the greenhouse experiment

Doses of NPK-fertilizer			
N	P	K	
NH ₄ NO ₃ (g pot ⁻¹)	KH ₂ PO ₄ (g pot ⁻¹)	KH ₂ PO ₄ (g pot ⁻¹)	K ₂ SO ₄ (g pot ⁻¹)
0.568	0.229	0.079	0.148

Arsenic was applied in the form of arsenite (NaAsO₂) and arsenate (KH₂AsO₄), separately in seven different levels respectively as follows: 0 (control), 1, 3, 10, 30, 90 and 270 mg kg⁻¹. The NPK fertilizer and the arsenate as well as arsenite was supplemented to the soil as an aqueous solution.

Green pea (*Pisum sativum* L.) was chosen for our research to study the effect of different arsenic treatments on the dry weight of plant since it is one of the vegetables grown in the largest area in Hungary. Twenty-five seeds were planted in each pots and after the germination the number of the plants was slowed to sixteen. The study was conducted in randomized complete block design with three replications. Pots were weighed daily and the water losses were refilled by applications of de-ionized water. Plants samples (four plant in each phenophase) were collected in the four different phase of the plant development (four-node condition, the beginning of flowering, green ripening, and complete maturity). The roots of the plants were washed to eliminate the soil by distilled water. The

dry weights were recorded after drying the root, stem, leaves, peas and pods at 65°C until a constant weight was achieved.

All data obtained from experiment were subjected to one-way analysis of variance (ANOVA) and Duncan's test at 0.05 significance level to compare populations and arsenic treatments, used by SPSS statistics software version 22.0. Independent Sample T-test was used to determine the statistically significant differences at 0.05, 0.01 and 0.001 significance levels between the effect of arsenate and arsenite at the same level.

3. Results

3.1. Effect of As(III)- and As(V)-treatments on the dry weight of green pea in the first phenophase of the plant development

The effect of As(III)- and As(V)-treatments on the dry weight of individual plant's part of green pea plants which were in four-node condition is demonstrate in the Table 3.

Table 2) Dry weight (g plant⁻¹) of individual plant's part of green pea plants which were in four-node condition grown in the calcareous chernozem soil of Látókép depending on arsenic-treatments (0, 3, 10, 30, 90, 270 mg kg⁻¹)

As-treatments (mg kg ⁻¹)	Dry weight (g plant ⁻¹)			
	Leaves	Stem	Root	
As(III)	0	0.162±0.042 ^a	0.123±0.039 ^a	0.0223±0.0055 ^a
	3	0.135±0.01 ^b	0.0817±0.0087 ^b	0.0210±0.0046 ^a
	10	0.123±0.01 ^b	0.0813±0.0069 ^b	0.0178±0.0058 ^a
	30	0.117±0.007 ^b	0.0785±0.0053 ^b	0.0176±0.0059 ^a
	90	0.114±0.013 ^b	0.0711±0.0083 ^b	0.0107±0.0007 ^b
	270	0.0198±0.0056 ^c	0.0207±0.0058 ^c	0.0101±0.0034 ^b
As(V)	0	0.162±0.042 ^a	0.123±0.039 ^{ab}	0.0223±0.0055 ^a
	3	0.175±0.026 ^{a*}	0.151±0.051 ^{b*}	0.0312±0.0069 ^{b*}
	10	0.160±0.038 ^{a*}	0.111±0.014 ^{ab}	0.0215±0.0048 ^a
	30	0.121±0.028 ^b	0.0837±0.0154 ^a	0.0181±0.0051 ^a
	90	0.109±0.024 ^b	0.0740±0.0119 ^{ac}	0.0164±0.0016 ^{a*}
	270	0.0215±0.0052 ^c	0.0287±0.0071 ^c	0.0157±0.0053 ^a

Means followed by the same letter within columns, separately in the case of As(III) and As(V), were not significantly different according to Duncan's multiple range test ($P \leq 0.05$). Means followed by * ($p < 0.05$), ** ($p < 0.01$), *** ($p < 0.001$) within columns were significantly different between the effect of As(III) and As(V) at the same level according to independent sample T-test.

This values show that increasing amount of As(III)-treatment resulted statistically lower dry weight of the leaves and stem of experimental plants. Based on the data,

in the case of the root the 90 and 270 mg kg⁻¹ As(III)-treatments also significantly reduced the dry weight.

According to the data the 3 mg kg⁻¹ As(V)-treatment statistically increased the dry weight of root. When the plants were treated with more than 10 mg kg⁻¹ As(V), the dry weight of leaves were reduced, moreover the dry biomass of stem was also reduced when the plants were treated with 270 mg kg⁻¹ As(V). Nevertheless, the 3 mg kg⁻¹ As(V)-treatment significantly increased the dry mass of stem and root.

3.2. Effect of As(III)- and As(V)-treatments on the dry weight of green pea in the second phenophase of the plant development

As a result of our experiments shows, the treatments of green pea with As(III) had a negative effect on the dry mass of stem. The dry weight of root and leaves were also reduced when the plants were treated with at least 30 mg kg⁻¹ As(III).

In addition it was observed that the dry mass of root, stem and leaves were decreased when the plants were treated with 90 and 270 mg kg⁻¹ As(V). Nevertheless, the 10 mg kg⁻¹ As(V)-treatment increased the dry mass of leaves (Table 3).

Table 3) Dry weight (g plant⁻¹) of individual plant's part of green pea plants which were in the beginning of flowering grown in the calcareous chernozem soil of Látókép depending on arsenic-treatments (0, 3, 10, 30, 90, 270 mg kg⁻¹)

As-treatments (mg kg ⁻¹)	Dry weight (g plant ⁻¹)			
	Leaves	Stem	Root	
As(III)	0	0.192±0.048 ^a	0.255±0.085 ^a	0.0304±0.0077 ^a
	3	0.165±0.014 ^{ab}	0.170±0.027 ^b	0.0287±0.0095 ^a
	10	0.145±0.046 ^{ab}	0.156±0.037 ^b	0.0255±0.0053 ^{ab}
	30	0.133±0.041 ^b	0.141±0.036 ^b	0.0200±0.0059 ^{bc}
	90	0.128±0.030 ^b	0.126±0.037 ^b	0.0159±0.0051 ^c
	270	0.0298±0.0106 ^c	0.0238±0.0046 ^c	0.0130±0.0044 ^c
As(V)	0	0.192±0.048 ^a	0.255±0.085 ^a	0.0304±0.0077 ^a
	3	0.218±0.06 ^a	0.266±0.07 ^a	0.0335±0.0068 ^a
	10	0.311±0.078 ^{b**}	0.345±0.081 ^{a**}	0.0299±0.0079 ^{ab}
	30	0.208±0.056 ^{a*}	0.276±0.07 ^a	0.0267±0.0077 ^{abc}
	90	0.112±0.039 ^c	0.122±0.025 ^b	0.0202±0.0069 ^{bc}
	270	0.0294±0.0098 ^d	0.0323±0.0079 ^c	0.0189±0.0057 ^c

Means followed by the same letter within columns, separately in the case of As(III) and As(V), were not significantly different according to Duncan's multiple range test ($P \leq 0.05$). Means followed by * ($p < 0.05$), ** ($p < 0.01$), *** ($p < 0.001$) within columns were significantly different between the effect of As(III) and As(V) at the same level according to independent sample T-test.

3.3. Effect of As(III)- and As(V)-treatments on the dry weight of green pea in the third phenophase of the plant development

In the case of the third phase of the plant development, dry weight of each plant part were decreased when the plant were exposed to 90 and 270 mg kg⁻¹ As(V)-treatments. Nevertheless, the 30 mg kg⁻¹ As(V)-treatments significantly increased the dry weight of leaves and stem.

In the case if the leaves similar tendency was observed when the plants were treated with As(III). The 90 and 270 mg kg⁻¹ As(III)-treatment significantly decreased the dry weight of leaves. The dry mass of root was not vary significantly under the As(III)-stress, however the biomass of stem was negatively affected by all As(III)-treatments (Table 4.).

Table 4) Dry weight (g plant⁻¹) of individual plant's part of green pea plants which were in green ripening grown in the calcareous chernozem soil of Látókép depending on arsenic-treatments (0, 3, 10, 30, 90, 270 mg kg⁻¹)

As-treatments (mg kg ⁻¹)	Dry weight (g plant ⁻¹)			
	Leaves	Stem	Root	
As(III)	0	0.226±0.072 ^a	0.299±0.087 ^a	0.0463±0.0127 ^{ab}
	3	0.176±0.038 ^{ab}	0.194±0.066 ^b	0.0460±0.0149 ^b
	10	0.174±0.049 ^{ab}	0.192±0.061 ^b	0.0394±0.0087 ^{ab}
	30	0.173±0.059 ^{ab}	0.185±0.041 ^b	0.0341±0.0033 ^{ab}
	90	0.159±0.046 ^b	0.176±0.057 ^b	0.0323±0.0104 ^{ab}
	270	0.0379±0.0126 ^c	0.0270±0.0074 ^c	0.0293±0.0061 ^b
As(V)	0	0.226±0.072 ^a	0.299±0.087 ^a	0.0463±0.0127 ^a
	3	0.240±0.078 ^a	0.306±0.068 ^{a*}	0.0455±0.0035 ^a
	10	0.356±0.049 ^{b**}	0.391±0.113 ^{b**}	0.0452±0.0067 ^a
	30	0.248±0.055 ^{a*}	0.299±0.046 ^{a***}	0.0415±0.0105 ^{ab}
	90	0.116±0.028 ^c	0.133±0.028 ^c	0.0300±0.0071 ^{bc}
	270	0.0340±0.0106 ^c	0.0399±0.0124 ^{d*}	0.0238±0.0072 ^c

Means followed by the same letter within columns, separately in the case of As(III) and As(V), were not significantly different according to Duncan's multiple range test ($P \leq 0.05$). Means followed by * ($p < 0.05$), ** ($p < 0.01$), *** ($p < 0.001$) within columns were significantly different between the effect of As(III) and As(V) at the same level according to independent sample T-test.

3.4. Effect of As(III)- and As(V)-treatments on the dry weight of green pea in the fourth phenophase of the plant development

The effect of As(III)- and As(V)-treatments was also evident on the vegetative plant's part of green pea. The As(V)-treatments caused a similar tendency in the dry weight of leaves, stem and root as previously mentioned in the case of the third phenophase of the plant development. The 90 and 270 mg kg⁻¹ As(V)-

treatments decreased the dry mass of the vegetative plant parts, however the 10 mg kg⁻¹ As(V)-treatment increased the dry weight of leaves and stem. In the case of the leaves the dry mass was also positively affected by the 3 mg kg⁻¹ As(III)-treatment. As in the case of the third phenophase of the plant development, the highest As(III)-treatment (270 mg kg⁻¹) also significantly decreased the dry weight of the vegetative parts of the green pea, moreover the 90 mg kg⁻¹ As(III)-treatment also decreased the dry mass of the root compared to the control as demonstrated in the Table 5.

Table 5 Dry weight (g plant⁻¹) of vegetative plant's part of green pea plants which were in complete maturity grown in the calcareous chernozem soil of Látókép depending on arsenic-treatments (0, 3, 10, 30, 90, 270 mg kg⁻¹)

As-treatments (mg kg ⁻¹)	Dry weight (g plant ⁻¹)		
	Leaves	Stem	Root
0	0.24±0.061 ^{ab}	0.305±0.064 ^{ab}	0.0607±0.0119 ^a
3	0.368±0.072 ^c	0.374±0.129 ^b	0.0565±0.0194 ^{ab}
10	0.301±0.039 ^{bc}	0.322±0.036 ^{ab}	0.0527±0.0110 ^{ab}
30	0.238±0.074 ^{ab}	0.263±0.032 ^{ab}	0.0450±0.0150 ^{ab}
90	0.197±0.059 ^a	0.209±0.028 ^a	0.0430±0.0120 ^b
270	0.0554±0.0182 ^d	0.065±0.0107 ^c	0.0249±0.0081 ^c
0	0.24±0.061 ^a	0.305±0.064 ^a	0.0607±0.0119 ^a
3	0.246±0.056 ^{a*}	0.316±0.085 ^a	0.0505±0.0097 ^{ab}
10	0.379±0.052 ^{b*}	0.465±0.108 ^{b*}	0.0471±0.0092 ^{bc}
30	0.262±0.037 ^a	0.307±0.048 ^a	0.0463±0.0119 ^{bc}
90	0.127±0.036 ^c	0.153±0.043 ^c	0.0342±0.0074 ^c
270	0.0435±0.0119 ^d	0.0525±0.0154 ^d	0.0341±0.0089 ^c

Means followed by the same letter within columns, separately in the case of As(III) and As(V), were not significantly different according to Duncan's multiple range test ($P \leq 0.05$). Means followed by * ($p < 0.05$), ** ($p < 0.01$), *** ($p < 0.001$) within columns were significantly different between the effect of As(III) and As(V) at the same level according to independent sample T-test.

Conclusion

This study provides important information concerning the relationship between the levels of As in the soil and its impact on dry weight of the of individual plant's part of green pea plants.

According to the results, in the case of the all phenophase As(III)-treatments has a negative impact on the dry weight of the vegetative plant's parts, however is statistically not supportable in all cases. Based on the data in the case of the first phenophase the lower concentration of As(V)-treatment (3 mg kg⁻¹) increased, but the higher As(V)-treatments (10, 30, 90 and 270 mg kg⁻¹) inhibited the dry mass accumulation, however is statistically also not supportable in all cases. In the case of the second, third and fourth phenophase of the plant development, increasing

tendency was observed in the dry weight of leaves and stem until the 10 mg kg⁻¹ As(V)-treatment, nevertheless decreasing tendency was observed in the case of the higher As(V)-treatments (30, 90 and 270 mg kg⁻¹). However, in the case of the first phenophase as a result of the 3 mg kg⁻¹ As(V)-treatment the dry weight of root was slightly increased and in the second phase also was slightly increased. Nevertheless, the dry mass of root was negatively affected by the As(V)-treatments in case of the other treatments and other phenophase of the green pea development. As a results of our experiment shows in some cases there were significant differences between the effect of As(III)- and As(V)-treatments. Some authors reported that the arsenic is toxic, for plant, however at very low concentration As(V) may be beneficial for plants [11, 18]. Our study confirms that the low concentration of As(V) has a positive effect on the dry biomass of plants. The reason of that is the next: As(V) chemically similar to the phosphate, which element is necessary to the plant growth. As(V) is able to replace the phosphate on the surface of the minerals in the soil, which mechanism increased the plant-available amount of phosphate.

REFERENCES

- [1] P. L. Smedley and D. G. Kinniburgh, *A review of the source, behavior and distribution of arsenic in natural waters*, Appl. Geochem. **17**, 517 (2002).
 - [2] P. N. Williams et al., *Variation in arsenic speciation and concentration in paddy rice related to dietary exposure*, Environ. Sci. Technol. **41**, 6854 (2007).
 - [3] Y. G. Zhu et al., *Exposure to inorganic arsenic from rice: a global health issue?*, Environ. Pollut. **154**, 169 (2008).
 - [4] N. Stoeva et al., *Physiological response of maize to arsenic contamination*, Biol. Plant. **47**, 449 (2004).
 - [5] F. J. Zhao et al., *Arsenic uptake and metabolism in plants*, New Phytol. **181**, 777 (2009).
 - [6] J. M. Shaofen Wang and C. Wai, *Arsenic in Drinking Water - A Global Environmental Problem*, J. Chem. Educ. **81**, 207 (2004).
 - [7] D. J. Kim et al., *Arsenate tolerance mechanism of *Oenothera odorata* from a mine population involves the induction of phytochelatins in roots*, Chemosphere. **75**, 505 (2009).
 - [8] A. A. Meharg and J. Hartley-Whitaker, *Arsenic uptake and metabolism in arsenic resistant and nonresistant plant species*, New Phytol. **154**, 29 (2002).
 - [9] C. I. Ullrich-Eberius et al., *Evaluation of arsenate - and vanadate-associated changes of electrical membrane potential and phosphate transport in *Lemna gibba* G1*, J. Exp. Bot. **40**, 119 (1989).
-

- [10] P. M. Finnegan and W. Chen, *Arsenic Toxicity: The effects on plant metabolism*. Front Physiol. 3, 182 (2012).
 - [11] J. Y. Xu et al., *Arsenic in garden soils and vegetable crops in Cornwall, England: implications for human health*, Environ Pollut. 194, 105 (2014).
 - [12] B. R. Wells and J. T. Gilmor, *Sterility in rice cultivars as influenced by MSMA rate and water management*, Agron. J. 69, 451 (1977).
 - [13] S. E. Smith et al., *Arsenic uptake and toxicity in plants: integrating mycorrhizal influences*, Plant Soil. 327, 1 (2010).
 - [14] N. S. Mokgalaka-Matlala et al., *Toxicity of Arsenic (III) and (V) on plant growth, element uptake, and total amyolytic activity of Mesquite (Prosopis juliflora x P. velutina)*, Int. J. Phytoremediat. 10, 47 (2008).
 - [15] C. Tu and L. Q. Ma, *Effects of arsenic concentrations and forms on arsenic uptake by the hyperaccumulator ladder brake*, J. Environ. Qual. 31, 641 (2002).
 - [16] M. R. Shaibur et al., *Critical toxicity of arsenic and elemental composition of arsenic-induced chlorosis in hydroponic Sorghum*, Water Air Soil Pollut. 191, 279 (2008).
 - [17] S. Srivastava et al., *Comparative biochemical and transcriptional profiling of two contrasting varieties of Brassica juncea L. in response to arsenic exposure reveals mechanisms of stress perception and tolerance*, J. Exp. Bot. 60, 3419 (2009).
 - [18] A. A. Carbonell-Barrachina et al., *The influence of arsenite concentration on arsenic accumulation in tomato and bean plants*, Sci. Hortic. 71, 167 (1997).
 - [19] B. Kovács et al., *Effect of molybdenum treatment on molybdenum concentration and nitrate reduction in maize seedlings*, Plant Physiol. Biochem. **96**, 38 (2015).
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PHYSIOLOGICAL DETECTION OF WATER AND NITROGEN DEPRIVATION

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Abstract. *Water and nitrogen are crucial environmental factors, which are modifiable by farmers and main in controlling plant growth and development. The supply of nitrogen is crucial for vegetative growth and the role of nitrogen in agricultural production is intimately connected with photosynthesis. Photosynthetic rate correlates closely with leaf nitrogen content and water status of plants. The main goal of this research was to investigate some physiological parameters of barley genotypes under nitrogen and water deprivation conditions at anthesis growth stage. Dry weight of plants was determined with thermo-gravimetric method. Relative chlorophyll content as SPAD unit measurement was applied to follow the relative chlorophyll contents of leaves. The water status of plants was established by measuring relative water content (RWC) of leaves. Chlorophyll fluorescence induction method was used to examine potential photochemical activity (Fv/Fm). Based on the measured parameters, genotypes showed differences. Some parameters are useful for choosing more photosynthetically active barley genotypes in the double-haploid populations to be used in breeding barley lines with increased productivity under relatively low nitrogen and water supply.*

Keywords: nitrogen, drought, barley, SPAD, Fv/Fm

1. Introduction

Water and nitrogen (N) are the main limiting factors in agricultural production in most parts of the world. During its life cycle, a plant may be subjected to a water deficit, a N deficit or a combination of both, thus co-limiting [1] its productivity.

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The interaction between carbon and nitrogen assimilation and their efficiency are key importance for plant production. Applying optimal nitrogen amount at total genetic potential, more carbon assimilation per unit nitrogen would increase biomass. The supply of nitrogen is crucial for leaf growth and the role of nitrogen in agricultural production is intimately connected with photosynthesis. Photosynthetic rate correlates closely with leaf nitrogen content in several plants. At the same time low photosynthetic potential per gram of leaf does not directly cause the slow growth of nitrogen deficient plants. The effect of water deficit on N nutrition has been the subject of considerable research at plants [2, 3, 4]. The main effect of water restriction is certainly a reduction in N demand due to the marked sensitivity of leaf area expansion [5]. Investigations are mainly focused on measuring the intensity and products of dark reaction of the photosynthetic pathway. Less result have about light reaction affected by genotypic and nitrogen supply variations, mainly under stress conditions. The physiological or genetic mechanisms that underlie such natural variation in species or cultivars are largely untapped resources that may provide not only valuable information on the capacity and performance of different cultivars under different environmental conditions but also an invaluable genetic resource that can be used to improve yield [6, 7]. Based on Pepó [8] results the dry weight production was mainly influenced by environmental factors and modified by fertilizers and genotypes. Measuring parameters, which are useful for characterizing plant condition is a good tool for getting information about stress plasticity of plants under non-optimal conditions.

2. Materials and Methods

Two barley (*Hordeum vulgare* L.) – Vlamingh (VLA) and Buloke (BUL) – genotypes from the double haploid population were investigated under two different nitrogen supply (optimal and $\frac{1}{4}$ amount of optimal) and under optimal and 50% soil water capacity (*Tab 1*) from tillering stage till anthesis. All of the presented results were measured in anthesis (GS 69) stage. Plants were grown on real soil from Katanning (Australia) (2kg topsoil and 2kg subsoil) in columns. 3 columns per treatment and 3 plants per columns were set up. Experiments were established in glasshouse of University of Western Australia. All of the measurements were taken on flag leaves of plants. Dry weight of plants (spike, stem, leaves, root) was determined with thermo-gravimetric method. Relative chlorophyll contents (SPAD unit) were measured by SPAD 502 relative chlorophyll meter (Minolta, Japan). Chlorophyll fluorescence parameter, as potential photochemical activity (Fv/Fm) was detected by PAM-2000 chlorophyll fluorometer (Walz, Germany) as described by Schreiber *et al.* (1986) [9]. Fv/Fm was measured early in the morning and at noon as well. Relative water content

(RWC) measurement of leaves was made by Barrs *et al.* (1962) [10] method at noon.

Table 1) Symbols of different treatment

VLAMING=VLA	BULOKE=BUL
¼ Nitrogen + 50% Water = VLA00	¼ Nitrogen + 50% Water = BUL00
¼ Nitrogen + optimal Water = VLA0W	¼ Nitrogen + optimal Water = BUL0W
optimal Nitrogen + 50% Water = VLAN0	optimal Nitrogen + 50% Water = BULN0
optimal Nitrogen + optimal Water = VLANW	optimal Nitrogen + optimal Water = BULNW

3. Results and Discussion

The main goal of this research was to investigate some physiological parameters of barley genotypes under two nitrogen contents and water deprivation conditions. It is widely accepted that improved information on the factors controlling the acquisition and utilization of N by crops will help to identify the constraints to developing more effective strategies of N fertilization. Nitrogen nutrition and water supply has significant effects on dry weight of two barley genotypes were compared under two different nitrogen and water supply conditions. Water deprivation means higher strain than nitrogen lack with genotype difference (*Fig 1*).

Fig 1) Values of dry weight (g plant⁻¹) of barley genotypes under different N and water supply conditions, n=3±s.e.

The 50% water deprivation after the tillering stage does not caused serous drought problem for plants (*Tab 2*), but Fv/Fm values were sensitive mainly for ¼ nitrogen supply condition at noon. (*Fig 2*). The chlorophyll fluorescence induction method was used for examining Fv/Fm as one of the most reliable chlorophyll fluorescence parameters for characterising genotypic differences in photochemical activity under various nitrogen and water supplies.

Table 2) Values of relative water content (RWC) (%) in the case of two barley genotypes (VLAMINGH=VLA and BULOKE=BLU) under optimal nitrogen (N) and water (W) supply and deprivation (0), n=3, \pm s.e.

%	1/4N+0W	1/4N+optimalW	optimalN+0W	optimalN+optimalW
VLA	81.8 \pm 0.3	88.1 \pm 0.9	73.8 \pm 5.2	84.2 \pm 2.1
BUL	81.9 \pm 0.7	91.1 \pm 0.3	79.5 \pm 0.8	86.6 \pm 2.1

Fig 2) Values of potential photochemical activity (Fv/Fm) of barley genotypes under different nitrogen and water supply conditions, n=9, \pm s.e.

BULOKE genotype was more tolerant for water or nitrogen deprivation respectively, than VLAMINGH, but deprivation of both caused higher reduction in Fv/Fm, than in VLAMINGH.

Nondestructive analysis of relative chlorophyll content with chlorophyll meters, for example the SPAD-502, provide a simple, quick, and nondestructive method for estimating leaf chlorophyll content [11].

The relative chlorophyll content values show (Fig 3) differences by the effect of nitrogen and water in both barley genotypes.

Fig 3) Values of relative chlorophyll content (SPAD value) of barley genotypes under different nitrogen and water supply conditions $n=15 \pm s.e.$ Significant differences $p < 0.05^*$; $p < 0.001^{***}$ between water treatment and $p < 0.001^c$ between nitrogen treatment

Nitrogen lack was more serious in VLAMINGH genotype, SPAD values declined with 25% compared to have nitrogen. In case of BULOKE genotypes this differences were lower.

Conclusions

Water deprivation means higher strain than nitrogen lack with genotype difference based on dry weight value.

The optimal photochemical activity (Fv/Fm) values were sensitive for the investigated two environmental factors, and genotype differences were established in tolerance.

Relative chlorophyll content was more sensitive for nitrogen supply, than water deprivation with genotypes differences as well.

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REFERENCES

- [1] O.V. Sadras, *A quantitative top-down view of interactions between stresses: theory and analysis of nitrogen-water co-limitation in Mediterranean agro-ecosystems* Aust. J. Agr. Res. **56**, 1151 (2005).
 - [2] J.A. Morgan, *Interaction of water supply and N in wheat*. Plant Phys. **76**, 112 (1984).
 - [3] D.W. Lawlor, G. Cornic, *Photosynthetic carbon assimilation and associated metabolism in relation to water deficits in higher plants*. Plant Cell Environ. **25**, 275 (2002).
 - [4] V. Gonzales-Dugo, J.L. Durand *et al.*, *Short-term response of the nitrogen nutrition status of tall fescue and Italian ryegrass swards under water deficit*. Aust. J. Agr. Res. **56**, 1269 (2005).
 - [5] V. Gonzales-Dugo, J.L. Durand, F. Gastal, *Water deficit and nitrogen nutrition of crops. A review*. Agron. Sustain. Dev. **30**, 529 (2010)
 - [6] T. Lawson, D.M. Kramer, C.A. Raines, *Improving yield by exploiting mechanisms underlying natural variation of photosynthesis*, Curr. Op. in Biotech. **23**, 215 (2012)
 - [7] S.M. Diever, T. Lawson, P.J. Andralojc, C.A. Raines, M.A.J. Parry, *Natural variation in photosynthetic capacity, growth, and yield in 64 field-grown wheat genotypes*. J. Exp. Bot. **65**, 4959 (2014)
 - [8] P. Pepó, *Szárazanyag - és levélterület - dinamikai vizsgálatok őszi búza állományokban*. Növénytermelés. **54**, 65 (2005).
 - [9] U. Schreiber, U. Schliwa, W. Bilger, *Continuous recording of photochemical and non-photochemical chlorophyll fluorescence quenching with a new type of modulation fluorometer*. Phot. Res. **10**, 51 (1986).
 - [10] H.D. Barrs, P.E. Weatherley, *A re-examination of the relative turgidity technique for estimating water deficits in leaves*. Aust. J. Biol. Sci. **24**, 519 (1962).
 - [11] Q. Ling, W. Huang, P. Jarvis, *Use of a SPAD-502 meter to measure leaf chlorophyll concentration in Arabidopsis thaliana*. Phot. Research, **107**, 209 (2011).
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MAIZE (*ZEA MAYS L.*) IMPROVEMENT STUDIES

Pál PEPÓ¹

Abstract. *Plant regeneration via tissue culture is becoming increasingly more common in monocots such as maize (*Zea mays L.*). Pollen (gametophytic) selection for resistance to aflatoxin in maize can greatly facilitate recurrent selection and the screening of germplasm for resistance at much less cost and in a shorter time than field testing. In vivo and in vitro techniques have been integrated in maize breeding programmes to obtain desirable agronomic attributes, and enhance the genes responsible for them and speed up the breeding process. The efficiency of anther and tissue cultures in maize and wheat has reached the stage where they can be used in breeding programmes to some extent and many new cultivars produced by genetic manipulation have now reached the market.*

Keywords: *Zea mays L.*, callus induction, aflatoxin, grain yield

1. Introduction

The regeneration of plants from tissue cultures was first reported in maize (*Zea mays L.*) by Green and Philips [6], who utilised immature embryos as the tissue source. Using the same tissue system, Springer et al. [19] demonstrated that plant regeneration took place by means of organogenesis.

Rice et al. [17] found that plant regeneration could also occur by somatic embryogenesis. Both types of regeneration arise from hard, white or yellow callus, which can be clearly distinguished from the granular, greyish-yellow, translucent callus that is incapable of plant regeneration. The regeneration of maize from cell and tissue cultures has been limited to a few specific genotype and medium combinations (Green and Philips, [6]; Hodges et al., [7]; Kamo et al., [8]. Medium improvements boosted the average regeneration, but genotypic differences remained (Duncan et al.,) [3]. Studies on the genotype component can be used to predict probabilities for a desired response level and to describe in more detail the nature of the tissue culture response (Tomes and Smith) [21].

Mycotoxins, in general, reportedly contaminate about one-quarter of the world's yearly food and feed crops. The effects of mycotoxin consumption on animal health range from decreased growth rates and reproductive efficiency to mortality. In addition, there is increasing concern about the effects of aflatoxin on human health, as aflatoxins have been linked to liver cancer. The occurrence of aflatoxin in food is viewed as a potential threat to the food supply. It has been deemed

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necessary to develop efficient methods that will prevent aflatoxin contamination in crops. Host-plant resistance is the most logical and useful method of control (Dickson et al. [2], Kang et al., [5]).

Thus far, only a few studies on the inheritance of resistance have been conducted (Widstrom et al., [23]; Gardner et al., [4]; Darrah et al., [1]; Gorman and Kang, [9]; Pepó and Szabó, [16]; Tóth and Bódi, [22]). Progress in elucidating genetic mechanisms and identifying sources of resistance to aflatoxin has been slow, primarily because genotype evaluation in the field (sporophytic selection) is laborious, expensive and time-consuming. Selection at the pollen level (male gametophytic selection) to screen for resistance to aflatoxin did not receive much attention until recently. The gametophytic generation has appropriately been called 'the forgotten generation'.

A total of 60-70 % of structural genes controlling traits in the sporophytic generation (plant) are expressed in the gametophytic generation (pollen) (Mulcahy, [11]; Mulcahy and Mulcahy, [12]; Ottaviano et al., [14]; Tanksley et al., [20]; Smith, [18]). This genetic overlap between the sporophytic and gametophytic generations offers a tremendous potential for modifying the sporophyte by applying selection pressure on the gametophyte. A maize plant produces 2 to 5 million pollen grains that can be subjected to selection. Selection pressure applied to pollen produced by a genetically homogeneous, heterozygous plant is expected to produce genetic changes in the sporophytic population (Ottaviano and Mulcahy, [14]).

Intergenic somatic hybridization was performed between albino maize (*Zea mays* L.) protoplasts and mesophyll protoplasts of wheat (*Triticum aestivum* L.) by means of PEG treatments. None of the parental protoplasts were able to produce green plants without fusion (Mórocz et al., [10]).

2. Materials and methods

Two maize populations developed in the Louisiana State University maize breeding program, viz. (Mo17 x B73) x Yellow Creole and (Mo17 x B 73) x (L331 x Yellow Creole), hereafter referred to as population L91 R and population L331, respectively, were evaluated for their in vitro culturability and regeneration potential. The S0, S1 and S2 generations were subjected to tissue culturing using the following procedure. The seeds were surface-sterilised for 10 min in 0.2% aqueous mercurous chloride solution, rinsed overnight under running tap water and re-sterilised for 5 min in 0.2% aqueous mercurous chloride solution, followed by several water rinses. Twenty-five kernels of each generation were germinated. Aseptic seedlings were grown on a 1% agar-solidified medium containing the inorganic constituents of Murashige and Skoog [13]: 3% sucrose, 26.7 µM glycine, 4.1 µM nicotinic acid, 2.4 µM pyridoxine-HCl and 0.3 µM thiamine-HCl.

N6 medium was used with 100 μmol Fe-EDTA concentration to initiate anther culture. Saccharose concentration 10% supplemented with activated charcoal was applied to induce calli in maize.

The radicles were aseptically separated from the plumules at the scutellar node and the explants were cut into five pieces each 23 mm long. These explants and intact, mature embryos were plated on MS medium. The pH was adjusted to 5.8 before autoclaving. Incubation was done at 26 °C with a 16/8 h photoperiod.

The 2,4-D concentration was 2.5 mg/L-1. After callus induction, meristematic segments were discarded; the remainder were transferred to the above culture medium for callus proliferation. To induce further differentiation, the calli were subcultured on MS medium supplemented with different concentrations of 2,4-D and zeatin. Regenerated plantlets were transferred to hormone-free medium for root development.

Anthers with mid-uninucleate microspores were cold-treated at 8-10 °C for 14 days and heat-preincubated in the dark at 27 ± 2 °C for 7 days. To increase the frequency of embryoids the medium was supplemented with activated charcoal and 0.1 mg L-1 TIBA. The embryoids were further cultured on N6 and M9 media to induce differentiation.

In the breeding programme, diallels were obtained by crossing four maize inbred lines (P2, P34, P50 and P61). The general and specific combining abilities for callus weight and grain yield were estimated using a full diallel system according to a modified version of Griffing's 1 method.

3. Results

It can be seen from Table 1 that the callus induction frequency for the two populations ranged from 4.7 to 60.9%. The highest frequency of callus formation was exhibited by radicle tissue and the lowest by the embryo. In both populations, the callus induction frequency decreased as the level of homozygosity increased, which suggested that callus induction was controlled primarily by dominant gene action.

Table 1) Callus induction and regeneration for populations L331 and L91R

Explant	Inbred stage	Callus induction		Regeneration	
		L331	L91R	L331	L91R
Radicle	S ₀	60.9	41.1	4.75	1.51
	S ₁	58.0	32.0	4.45	0.0
	S ₂	<u>56.0</u>	<u>23.9</u>	<u>0.0</u>	<u>0.0</u>
	Mean	58.3	33.4	2.70	0.59
Plumule (P)	S ₀	41.9	30.1	9.94	3.05
	S ₁	39.0	23.9	6.65	1.26
	S ₂	<u>38.9</u>	<u>19.0</u>	<u>4.43</u>	<u>0.0</u>
	Mean	40.0	25.1	6.95	1.65
Embryo (E)	S ₀	40.0	9.8	5.00	2.17
	S ₁	38.2	7.2	2.06	1.20
	S ₂	35.8	4.7	1.05	0.0
	Mean	38.0	7.5	2.75	1.25
Mean: R+P+E	S ₀	50.9	33.3	7.03	2.26
		(601/1181)	(228/1016)	(83/1181)	(23/1016)
	S ₁	47.9	26.1	4.79	0.67
		(590/1232)	(233/893)	(59/1232)	(6/893)
	S ₂	46.9	19.9	3.92	0.0
		(577/1230)	(134/673)	(25/1230)	(0/673)

The explants had different plant regeneration percentages in both populations. The maximum number of plants was regenerated from plumules in the L331 population. No plant regeneration was noted in the S₂ generation of the L91R population. The results suggested that plant regeneration would be increasingly more difficult in the inbred generations and that prior to embarking on a tissue culture-based breeding programme, responsive genotypes should be identified.

Microscopic investigations were carried out to investigate the effect of *Aspergillus flavus* spores and the aflatoxin B₁ on in vitro pollen germination and it was demonstrated that both inhibited pollen germination (Table 2).

Table 2) Mean percentage germination of pollen grains from the F₂ of the single cross (Mp 313 E x SC 212 M)

Treatment	Mean pollen grain germination (%)
Control	71.5 a*
<i>Aspergillus parasiticus</i> spores	44.2 b
Aflatoxin B ₁ (400 ppm)	42.4 b
<i>Aspergillus flavus</i> spores	23.7 c

- Means followed by the same letter are not significantly different at the 5% level of probability according to Duncan's New Multiple Range Test.

The callus induction and yielding ability of four maize inbred lines (P2, P34, P50 and P61) were compared in a diallel system. The general and specific combining

abilities for callus weight and grain yield were estimated (Tables 3, 4, 5 and 6) using a full diallel system according to a modified version of Griffing's 1 method.

Table 3) Values of general combining ability (GCA) for callus weight

Inbred lines	GCA [g]
P 2	0.1110
P 34	-0.0840
P 50	-0.7545
*P 61	0.7180

* Registered maize line

Table 4) Values of general combining ability (GCA) for grain yield

Inbred lines	GCA [t/ha]
P 2	-0.384
P 34	-0.093
P 50	-0.073
*P 61 (3)	0.550

* Registered maize line

Table 5) Results of callus induction in diallel analysis (SCA = specific combining ability (g), RE = Effect of reciprocal (g))

Female lines	Male lines			
	P 2	P 34	P 50	P61
P 2	-4.438 (SCA)	1.858 (SCA)	1.719 (SCA)	0.861 (SCA)
P 34	-2.250 (RE)	-2.988 (SCA)	0.024 (SCA)	1.106 (SCA)
P 50	-2.080 (RE)	-0.500 (RE)	-5.825 (SCA)	4.083 (SCA)
P 61	-1.995 (RE)	-0.955 (RE)	-0.720 (RE)	-6.050 (SCA)

(SCA = specific combining ability (g), RE = Effect of reciprocal (g))

*LSD_{5%} = 0,237

R² = 0,898

Table 6) Results of grain yield in diallel analysis

Female lines	Male lines.			
	P 2	P 34	P 50	P61
P 2	-5.333 (SCA)	2.406 (SCA)	1.137 (SCA)	1.789 (SCA)
P 34	-0.455 (RE)	-4.436 (SCA)	0.657 (SCA)	1.373 (SCA)
P 50	-1.108 (RE)	0.109 (RE)	-4.059 (SCA)	2.265 (SCA)
P 61	-1.114 (RE)	-0.260 (RE)	-1.361 (RE)	-5.426 (SCA)

(SCA = specific combining ability (t/ha), RE = Effect of reciprocal (t/ha))

*LSD_{5%} (3) = 0,312 R² = 0,887

3. Conclusions

A wide variety of diploid and double haploid lines produced in vitro are increasingly used in practical breeding programme.

Anther culture and tissue culture techniques were employed to develop lines with resistance to aflatoxins and herbicides, and with other desirable agronomic traits such as fast dry-down rate, better stalk and seed quality, and weevil resistance. As seen in Figure 2, a complex maize breeding programme was developed to obtain desirable agronomic attributes, enhance the genes responsible for them and speed up the breeding process. Depending on the nature of the source material, e.g. synthetics, F1 or open-pollinated varieties, and the breeding aims, one or more haploid (pollen) or diploid (tissue) steps were included and the F1 hybrids or selfed progenies in later generations served as the source material for haploidization or tissue culture. One haploid step followed by selection in the greenhouse/field or a diploid step after selection at the cell/plant level during the first androgenetic generations (A1) or diploid progenies (D1) and two subsequent selfed generations (A2, A3, D2, D3) proved to be the most efficient procedure, if characters from related varieties were to be combined. To make this genetic manipulation system more efficient, it was combined it with several backcrosses.

A combination of conventional and new genetic recombination methods (in vivo and in vitro genetic manipulation) may result in the development of cereal varieties and hybrids that are better able to meet production demands. The efficiency of anther and tissue cultures in most cereals such as maize has reached the stage where it can be used in breeding programmes to some extent and many new cultivars produced using this system have now reached the market.

REFERENCES

- [1] Darrah, L. L., Lillehoj, E.B., Zuber, M. S., Scott, G. E., Thompson, D., West, D. R., Widstrom, N. W., Fortnum B., A.: *Inheritance of aflatoxin B1 levels in maize kernels under modified natural inoculation with Aspergillus flavus*. Crop Sci. 27, 869-872. (1987)
 - [2] Dickson, J. I., Dronovalli, S., Pepo, P., Kondapi, N., Kang, M.S.: *Effect of MSMA on in vitro corn pollen germination*. Southern Branch of American Society of Agronomy, Lexington, Kentucky. Agronomy Abstracts, 45-46. (1992)
 - [3] Duncan, D. R., Williams, E. M., Zehr, B. E., Widholm. J. M.: *The production of callus capable of plant regeneration from immature embryos of numerous Zea mays genotypes*. Planta 165, 322-332. (1985)
 - [4] Gardner, C.A. C., Darrah, L. L., Zuber, M. S., Wallin, J.R.: *Genetic control of aflatoxin production in maize*. Plant Dis. 71, 426-429. (1987)
-

-
- [5] Kang, M.S.: *Preharvest aflatoxin contamination in maize: Resistance and genetics*. Plant Breeding, 107, 1-10. (1991)
- [6] D Green, C. E., Philips, R. L.: *Plant regeneration from tissue culture of maize*. Crop. Sci., 15, 417-421. (1975)
- [7] Hodges, T. K., K.K. Kamo, R. M. Becwar, S. Schroll.: *Regeneration of maize*. In: *Biotechnology in Plant Science: Relevance to Agriculture in the Nineteen Eighties*. Zaitlin, M., Day, P., Hollaender, A. (eds.), Academic Press, Orlando, Florida: pp.15-33.P. (1985)
- [8] Kamo, K. K., Becwar M. R., Hodges, T. K.: *Regeneration of Zea mays L. from embryogenic callus*. Bot. Gaz. 146, 327-334. (1985)
- [9] Gorman, D. P.Kang, M.S., Pepó, P., Dronovalli, S., Dickson, J. I., Kondapi, .N.: *Corn breeding and genetic investigations*, Report of Projects for 1991., Dept. of Agronomy, LSU. 71-78. (1992)
- [10] Mórocz S., Dudits D., Golovkin M. V., Ábrahám M., Bottka S., Fehér A.: *Production of transgenic maize plants by direct DNA uptake into embryogenic protoplasts*. Plant Science, 90, 41-52. (1993)
- [11] Mulcahy, D. L.: *Correlation between gametophytic and sporophytic characteristics in Zea mays L*. Science, 171, 1155-1156. (1971)
- [12] Mulcahy, D. L., Mulcahy., G. B.: *The effects of pollen competition*. Am. Scientist 75, 44-50. (1987)
- [13] Murashige T., Skoog F.: *A revised media for rapid growth and bioassays with tobacco tissue culture*. Physiol Plant 15, 473-479. (1962)
- [14] Ottaviano, E., Sari-Gorla, M., Mulcahy D. L.: *Pollen tube growth rates in Zea mays: Implications for genetic improvement of crops*. Science 210, 437-438. (1980)
- [15] Ottaviano, E., Mulcahy, D. L.: *Genetics of angiosperm pollen*. In: Scandalios, J. G. (ed.) *Advances in Genetics*, Academic Pres, Inc., CA, pp.1-64. (1989)
- [16] Pepó, P., E. Szabó.: *RAPD markerek öröklődése kukoricában (Zea mays L.) (Inheritance of RAPD markers in maize (Zea mays L.))*. IV. Növ.nem. Tudományos Napok, MTA, Abstract, 122. (1998)
- [17] Rice, T. B., R. K. Reid, P. N. Gordon.: *Morphogenesis in field crops*. pp. 262-277. Hughes, K. W., Henke, R., Constantin, M. (eds.), *Propagation of Higher Plants through Tissue Culture*. National Technical Information Service, U. S. Department of Commerce, Springfield, VA., USA. (1978)
- [18] Smith, G. A.: *Sporophytic screening and gametophytic verification of phytotoxin tolerance in sugarbeet (Beta vulgaris L.)*. pp. 83-88. In Mulcahy, D. L., Mulcahy, G. B. and Ottaviano, E. (eds.) *Biotechnology and Ecology of Pollen* Springer-Verlag, New York. (1986)
-

-
- [19] Springer, W. D., Green, E. C., Kohn, A. K.: *A histological examination of tissue culture initiation from immature embryos of maize*. Protoplasma 101, 269-281. (1979)
- [20] Tanksley, S. D., Zamir, D., Rick, C. M.: *Evidence for extensive overlap of sporophytic and gametophytic gene expression in Lycopersicon esculentum*. Science 213, 453-455. (1981)
- [21] Tomes, D. T., Smith, O. S.: *The effect of parental genotype on initiation of embryogenic callus from elite maize (Zea mays L.) germplasm*. Theor. Appl. Gen. 50, 505-509. (1985)
- [22] Tóth, Sz., Bódi, Z.: *Indukált mutációval létrehozott kukoricagénbank a nemesítési alapanyagbázis növelésért. (Gene Bank Developed by Induced Mutation for Selection)* Acta Agraria Debreceniensis. 19, 45-49. (2006)
- [23] Widstrom, N. W., Wilson, D. M., McMillian, W. W.: *Ear resistance of maize inbreds to field aflatoxin contamination*. Crop Sci. 24, 1155-1157. (1984)
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ASSESSMENT OF GRAIN SORGHUM (*SORGHUM BICOLOR* (L.) MOENCH) HYBRID COMBINATIONS

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Abstract. Grain sorghum is a very prospective plant in Europe and the potential role of this crop can be enhanced by sorghum. In this study eleven sorghum hybrids were evaluated. During this experiment some morphological parameters, starch- and protein contents were assessed. Starch contents were carried out by using polarimetric method while Kjeldahl method of nitrogen content was used to determine the protein content. Based on the measured data, heterosis values were calculated and ANOVA was applied in order to determine the potential differences appeared among the hybrids. From the viewpoint of the investigated aspects significant differences were found. Parameters of the investigated morphological parameters differed in a large scale, while in the case of the starch content Hybrid 6 obtained the highest values with a remarkable 26.19% heterosis value. Protein contents ranged from 10.59% to 14.25%. The highest value for protein content was obtained by Hybrid 2 with 12.59% value of heterosis.

Keywords: grain sorghum, threshing %, starch content, protein content, plant breeding

1. Introduction

Sorghum is produced for a diversity of uses, but this crop is mostly grown for forage in Europe. It is a very prospective crop in Hungary due to its great tolerance against drought and unfavorable soil conditions, which are actual problems in the Hungarian agriculture [1, 2]. Thus growing and breeding of sorghum can be an adequate method to decrease risks caused by drought. In the field of sorghum breeding the most widespread conventional breeding method is hybridization.

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Heterosis in sorghum can be manifested in improved performance of several characteristics. In a case study the manifestation of heterosis among 19 sorghum hybrids was reported appearing in the yields and plant height [3]. In another case 84% increase of grain yield had been reported as compared to the parents in the United States of America [4] while in Kenya the mean hybrid superiority over mid-parent values was 54% for grain yield and 35% for above-ground biomass [5]. Other research works also studied the manifestation of heterosis on grain sorghum and reported an increased yield of the hybrid compared to the parent lines as well [6, 7] moreover, in some cases the percentage of the increase was 238% [8].

Primer proteins are essential in the field of human nutrition and animal husbandry, therefore a respectful attention focused on the investigation of this parameter [9]. Some studies mention negative heterosis values for protein content in the case of grain sorghum [10, 11] therefore more attention should be focused on this parameter. Remarkable starch- and protein content enhancement can be obtained by crossing inbred lines resulting significant differences among the hybrid combinations from the viewpoint of these parameters [11]. Based on a Hungarian research work notable outbreeding enhancements were reported in the case of sorghum hybrid combinations from the point of view of starch- and protein content [12]. The starch contents of the single cross hybrids varied between 48.37% and 62.63% while the protein content ranged between 9.43–17.7%.

In this study eleven hybrid combinations were evaluated by the viewpoints of some morphological parameters, starch- and protein content in order to reflect the impacts of the hybridization.

2. Materials and methods

The field experiment was fixed on the H2 plant growing site of the Research Institute of Karcag. The soil type of the area was meadow chernozem with the main characteristics determined by the Hungarian standards (MSZ 20135:1999) shown in Table 1.

Table 1) The main parameters of the topsoil of the experimental area

pH (KCl)	Total salt content (m/m%)	Humus (m/m%)	P ₂ O ₅ (mg/kg)	K ₂ O (mg/kg)	NO ₂ ⁻ , NO ₃ ⁻ (mg/kg)
4.8	0.04	3.06	101	399	21.3
Na (mg/kg)	Mg (mg/kg)	SO ₄ (mg/kg)	Mn (mg/kg)	Cu (mg/kg)	Zn (mg/kg)
21	458	10.1	483	8.2	1.2

The field experiment was carried out between 27th of April and 10th of September in 2015. Annual precipitation was 414 mm and annual average temperature was 12.1°C respectively. The applied row space was 76.2 cm, the distance of the plants was 5 cm and the depth of sowing was 5 cm as well. The preemergent and postemergent weed control was done by using metolachor and terbutylazine and dicamba+bentazone herbicides and herbicide combinations. The site was free of weeds, and fitotoxic symptoms weren't appeared.

Before harvesting ten panicles were collected from each hybrid and parent line so as to guarantee the reliability of the statistical analysis. The collected panicles were dried for a few days and then the weight of each panicle was measured. After that the panicles were threshed by a laboratory grain thresher. After threshing, the weight of the grains threshed from each panicle was measured in the case of all panicles. The moisture content of the grains varied between 12% and 14%. By the measured data the threshing percentage was calculated using the equation below:

$$T=(P-g)/P*100 \quad (1)$$

Where:

T =Threshing percentage

P = The average weight of the panicle

g = The average weight of the grain in a panicle

The determination of starch content was done by polarimeter which is used to measure the angle of rotation caused by passing polarized light through an optically active substance. During the measurements 2.5 g of milled samples were destructured by 50 ml HCl (1,124 m/m %). After heating and blending the tincture, 10 ml of phosphorous-wolfram acid was added to aggregate protein of the sample. After blending, the tincture was filtered and measurements were done by a polarimeter. The starch content was calculated by the equation below:

$$S = (104[\alpha]) / ([\alpha]D20 * l * m) \quad (2)$$

Where:

S = starch content (m/m%)

[α] = the angle of rotation red during the measurement

[α]D20 = the specific ability of rotation of the evaluated substance

l = the length of the polarimeter tube (dm)

m = the measured amount of the substance (g)

The determination of the protein content was done by the Kjeldahl method: 0.5 g of milled sample was digested with sulphuric acid and the released nitrogen was determined by titration. The amount of protein was calculated from the nitrogen concentration of the sample by multiplying with a conversion factor (6.25).

On the bases of the measured and calculated data, the percentage heterosis was calculated by using the equation below:

$$H = \frac{\left[F1 - \frac{(P1 + P2)}{2} \right]}{\left[\frac{P1 + P2}{2} \right]} * 100 \quad (3)$$

Where:

H = The percentage of heterosis

F1 = The mean of the measured/calculated data of the hybrid

P1 = The mean of the measured/calculated data of the better parent line

P2 = The mean of the measured/calculated data of the vulnerable parent line

Based on the calculated heterosis values, the hybrid combinations were investigated whether they can provide better results than their parent lines by the evaluated viewpoints. So as to determine the potential differences among the hybrids ANOVA was applied. The calculations were performed by using MS Office Excel and R Softwares.

3. Results and discussion

Based on the results the average weight of panicle ranged from 25.10 g to 64.50 g. Hybrid 8 had the highest value of this parameter while Hybrid 2 had the lowest. From the viewpoint of this morphological parameter the observed standard deviations ranged in a large scale from 5.93 g to 19.68 g.

Table 2) Morphological parameters of the investigated hybrids

Hybrid	Weight of panicle			Weight of grains			Threshing%		
	Mean (g)	SD (g)	Heterosis (%)	Mean (g)	SD (g)	Heterosis (%)	Mean (%)	SD (%)	Heterosis (%)
Hybrid 1	35.60	5.93	25.80	24.39	6.44	15.07	32.13	9.27	33.56
Hybrid 2	25.10	19.68	0.88	19.17	13.20	-4.56	29.88	9.75	20.68
Hybrid 3	48.90	13.87	88.08	40.40	11.25	38.36	17.29	2.26	-29.52
Hybrid 4	55.00	12.81	144.99	43.90	10.08	41.84	20.14	2.03	-20.94
Hybrid 5	48.20	10.13	73.38	39.20	7.11	44.57	18.13	4.11	-45.05
Hybrid 6	48.70	9.15	85.17	41.35	8.08	46.68	15.22	1.70	-46.96
Hybrid 7	53.73	16.87	66.93	44.70	13.60	49.67	16.44	2.43	-42.99
Hybrid 8	64.50	15.80	61.25	53.60	12.80	56.20	16.74	2.56	-51.22
Hybrid 9	34.80	11.81	-4.66	20.18	9.31	16.80	40.62	10.46	42.07
Hybrid 10	35.20	12.78	44.56	26.24	11.03	27.16	26.24	8.27	-23.29
Hybrid 11	45.00	7.64	71.76	36.90	6.87	42.11	18.20	2.38	-43.11

The heterosis value for this parameter was negative only in the case of Hybrid 9, hence ten of the investigated hybrid combinations reached a higher panicle weight

than the mean of parent lines' performance. In the case of Hybrid 3, Hybrid 5, Hybrid 6, Hybrid 7, Hybrid 8, Hybrid 10 and Hybrid 11 remarkable heterosis values were calculated while for Hybrid 4 a prominently high outbreeding enhancement was determined with 144.99% heterosis value (*Table 2*).

The average weight of grains of the hybrids ranged from 19.17 g to 53.60 g. From this viewpoint only the Hybrid 2 provided negative heterosis value. Positive hybrid vigour was found in all the other cases. Hybrids providing high positive heterosis values for the weight of panicle reached high heterosis values of the weight of grains as well.

Regarding the threshing percent of the hybrids, the average values ranged from 15.22% to 40.62%. Hybrid 9 gave the highest threshing percent value while Hybrid 6 had the lowest. Thus in the case of Hybrid 9, there was more stem parts in the panicle than other cases while in the case of Hybrid 6 the average ratio of grains in the panicle was higher than in the case of any other investigated hybrids. The standard deviation of the threshing percent for all the hybrids evaluated was recorded as 9.7 g, which means that the deviations were ranged on a large scale. In the case of eight hybrids, the heterosis value of the threshing percent was negative while Hybrid 1, Hybrid 2 and Hybrid 9 produced positive heterosis results for this parameter.

Table 3) Alignment of hybrids by the evaluated morphological parameters

Weight of panicle LSD _{5%} =11.31		Weight of grains LSD _{5%} =9.08		Threshing % LSD _{5%} =5.22	
Group	Hybrid	Group	Hybrid	Group	Hybrid
a	Hybrid 8	a	Hybrid 8	a	Hybrid 9
ab	Hybrid 4	ab	Hybrid 7	b	Hybrid 1
ab	Hybrid 7	b	Hybrid 4	bc	Hybrid 2
b	Hybrid 3	b	Hybrid 6	c	Hybrid 10
b	Hybrid 6	b	Hybrid 3	d	Hybrid 4
b	Hybrid 5	b	Hybrid 5	d	Hybrid 11
bc	Hybrid 11	b	Hybrid 11	d	Hybrid 5
cd	Hybrid 1	c	Hybrid 10	d	Hybrid 3
cd	Hybrid 10	c	Hybrid 1	d	Hybrid 8
cd	Hybrid 9	c	Hybrid 9	d	Hybrid 7
d	Hybrid 2	c	Hybrid 2	d	Hybrid 6

Threshing percent reflects on the ratio of stem parts in the panicle, therefore in the case of eight hybrids with negative heterosis value an enhanced performance were observed by the investigated viewpoint. In the case of positive heterosis values of this parameter, the ratio of stem parts in the panicle was higher than the mean of the parent lines performance, this means that the ratio of grains in the panicle was lower.

According to the results significant differences were found among the hybrids by the viewpoints above. Hybrids with the same letters are in the same group and differ significantly by the evaluated aspect while hybrids with two letters are not significantly different from one another (*Table 3.*).

The highest value of starch content was obtained by Hybrid 6 (72.30%) while the lowest value was calculated for Hybrid 9 with the value of 57.32%. The hybrids' heterosis values for starch was negative in the case of Hybrid 2 and Hybrid 9 while in other cases the value of hybrid vigour was positive. In the case of Hybrid 6 and Hybrid 8 a remarkable outbreeding enhancement was determined from the viewpoint of starch content (*Table 4.*).

Table 4) Starch- and protein contents of the investigated hybrid combinations

Hybrid	Starch content			Protein content		
	Mean (%)	SD (%)	Heterosis (%)	Mean (%)	SD (%)	Heterosis (%)
Hybrid 1	67.78	2.47	8.61	11.03	0.33	-5.99
Hybrid 2	58.29	8.87	-7.42	14.25	1.58	12.59
Hybrid 3	59.85	1.48	2.16	11.34	1.88	-6.80
Hybrid 4	67.92	3.60	9.57	11.19	0.51	-9.02
Hybrid 5	63.50	2.77	2.96	10.72	2.64	-24.28
Hybrid 6	72.30	1.10	26.19	10.59	0.66	-22.51
Hybrid 7	66.27	2.10	6.26	10.97	0.99	-14.49
Hybrid 8	66.95	1.68	13.38	12.59	0.52	-9.13
Hybrid 9	57.32	3.84	-6.55	12.81	2.44	-6.92
Hybrid 10	63.16	8.77	2.25	12.88	1.15	-7.31
Hybrid 11	61.99	2.36	4.56	10.72	0.73	-20.14

The highest value of protein content was obtained by Hybrid 2 (14.25%) while the lowest value was calculated for Hybrid 6 with the value of 10.59%. The results of the hybrids' heterosis values for protein content showed that ten hybrids provided negative values and only Hybrid 2 gave positive value for the heterosis. Hybrid 5 gave the lowest value of heterosis for protein content with the value of -24.28%. According to these results it could be deduced that in the case of the Hybrid 2, the protein content was higher than the average value of its parent lines, whereas in the other cases the mean of the parent lines' protein content were higher than the protein content of the hybrid combination.

Table 5) Alignment of hybrids by their starch- and protein contents

Starch content (%) LSD _{5%} =4.06		Protein content (%) LSD _{5%} =1.33	
Group	Hybrid	Group	Hybrid
a	Hybrid 6	a	Hybrid 2
b	Hybrid 4	b	Hybrid 10
b	Hybrid 1	b	Hybrid 9
bc	Hybrid 8	bc	Hybrid 8
bc	Hybrid 7	cd	Hybrid 3
cd	Hybrid 5	d	Hybrid 4
cd	Hybrid 10	d	Hybrid 1
de	Hybrid 11	d	Hybrid 7
def	Hybrid 3	d	Hybrid 11
ef	Hybrid 2	d	Hybrid 5
f	Hybrid 9	d	Hybrid 6

According to the results significant differences were found among the hybrids by the viewpoints of starch- and protein contents. Hybrids with the same letters can be sorted into the same group by the evaluated aspect while hybrids with two or more letters are not significantly different (*Table 5*).

Conclusions

According to the results significant differences were found among the investigated hybrids from the point of view of the investigated aspects. Considering the aspects of the weight of panicle and weight of grains Hybrid 8 proved to be the most prospective hybrid combination. If the goal of the breeding process is to enhance yields this hybrid combination can be the best among the investigated hybrids. For industrial purposes (e.g. bioethanol production) Hybrid 6 can be the best, hence it achieved 26.19% heterosis value for this parameter. For these kinds of purposes Hybrid 1 and Hybrid 4 are also adequate combinations. Regarding the protein contents Hybrid 2 proved to be the most valuable hybrid. In this case 14.25±1.58% protein content was determined, which makes this combination adequate for foddering. Considering all of the evaluated aspects it can be set up that Hybrid 6 can be a good solution if the aim is to produce grain sorghum with high starch content. In the case of Hybrid 2 the protein content was high, but 19.17±13.20 g grain weight and 29.88±9.75% threshing percent was determined hence this hybrid can be described as a less prospective combination regarding the yields.

REFERENCES

- [1] Gályá, B., Riczu, P., Blaskó, L., Bákonyi V., Tamás, J.: *Examination of the conditions of extreme water balance circumstances (water logging, drought) with environmental information technology tools*. Agrártudományi Közlemények. 69, 79 (2016) (In Hungarian)
 - [2] Nagy A., Riczu P., Tamás J.: *Drought stress monitoring by laboratory and satellite spectral methods in apple orchard*. International Journal of Horticultural Science. 20, 7 (2014)
 - [3] Bartel A. T.: *Hybrid vigor in sorghums*. Agronomy Journal. 41, 147 (1949)
 - [4] Quinby J. R.: *Manifestations of hybrid vigor in sorghum*. Crop Science. 3, 288 (1967)
 - [5] Haussmann B. I. G., Obilana A. B., Blum A., Ayiecho P. O., Schipprack W., Geiger H. H.: *Hybrid performance of sorghum and its relationship to morphological and physiological traits under variable drought stress in Kenya*. Plant Breeding. 117, 223 (1998)
 - [6] Hovny M. R. A., Menshawi M. M., Nagouly O. O.: *Combining ability and heterosis in grain sorghum (*Sorghum bicolor* (L.) Moench)*. Bulletin of Faculty of Agriculture. Cairo University. 52, 47 (2001)
 - [7] Ganesh S., Khan A. K. F., Senthil N.: *Heterosis studies for grain yield characters in sweet sorghum*. Madras Agricultural Journal. 83, 655 (1996)
 - [8] Kambal A. E., Abu-el-gasim E. H.: *Manifestation of heterosis in grain sorghum*. Experimental Agriculture. 12, 33 (1976)
 - [9] Bökfi K., Nagy A., Riczu P., Gyug N., Petis M., Blaskó L., Tamás J.: 2016. *Evaluation of the blood product characteristics of meat meal and hemoglobin with non-invasive methods in the VIS-NIR wavelength*. Acta Agraria Debreceniensis, 69, 49 (2016) (In Hungarian)
 - [10] Thokoza M. L.: *Evaluation of the heterotic potential of sorghum [*Sorghum bicolor* (L.) Moench] adapted to the southern Africa region*. Master's thesis, Texas A&M University. Texas A&M University. (2005)
 - [11] Kambal A. E., Webster O. J.: *Manifestations of Hybrid Vigor in Grain Sorghum and the Relations among the Components of Yield, Weight per Bushel, and Height*. Crop Science. 6, 513 (1996)
 - [12] Erdei, É., Kovácsné Oskolás, H., Tikász, G., Pepó, P.: *Heterosis and interrelationship study on the values of the maize Kernel's major ingredients and its thousand weight*. Cereal Research Communications 41, 170 (2013)
 - [13] Pepó P., Erdei E., Kovácsné Oskolás H., Tóth., Szabó E.: 2011. *Examination of the nutritional values of inbred sorghum lines and their single cross sorghum hybrids*. Plant Production. 60, 83 (2011) (In Hungarian)
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ANTIOXIDANT ACTIVITY, TOTAL FLAVONOID, TOTAL PHENOLIC AND ANTHOCYANIN CONTENTS OF *CYNARA SCOLYMUS L.* LEAVES AND *TRIGONELLA FOENUM-GRÆCUM L.* SEEDS

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Abstract. *In the present comparative study we are analyzing the antioxidant activities, total flavonoid, total phenolic and total anthocyanin contents of artichoke (Cynara scolymus L.) and fenugreek (Trigonella foenum-graceum L.) extracts. Aqueous and alcoholic extracts were made from equal amounts of artichoke leaves and fenugreek seeds. The obtained results are indicating that the aqueous artichoke and fenugreek extracts antioxidant capacities are similar, while the corresponding alcoholic extracts antioxidant capacities are greatly reduced. The total phenolic content of alcoholic artichoke and fenugreek extracts was much greater than in case of the corresponding aqueous extracts. The anthocyanin type of flavonoids were not detected in any of our extracts made of artichoke leaves and fenugreek seeds. In case of artichoke leaf or fenugreek seed extracts, the total flavonoid and total phenolic contents, presumably, have very little if any involvement in the antioxidant capacities of artichoke and fenugreek, respectively.*

Keywords: artichoke, fenugreek, DPPH, flavonoid, polyphenols, anthocyanin

1. Introduction

Artichoke

Teas and extracts made from the leaves of the artichoke plant are a traditional tonic for the liver and gallbladder [1, 2]. Both laboratory and clinical studies strongly suggest artichoke leaf extract to be a good therapeutic option in dyspeptic syndrome (irritable stomach, nervous gastropathy, flatulence, irritable colon, functional biliary tract disease), [2]. In Europe the plant is widely used to treat

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arteriosclerosis and lower cholesterol. Several studies have hinted at the ability of artichoke extract to lower lipid levels. It works by affecting cholesterol synthesis in the liver at several points in the synthetic pathway and by increasing the elimination of cholesterol [1]. The plant chemical constituent cynarin acts as lipolysis-inhibitor in much the same manner as nicotinic acid (niacin), without the gastric upset and flushing that niacin supplements could cause. The diuretic properties of the artichoke are also useful in kidney disease [2].

Fenugreek

Fenugreek (*Trigonella foenum-graecum*) is a medicinal food plant that has the beneficial effect of lowering blood sugar. The bitter seeds called “methi” in India, are used as a condiment, and the leaves are used in teas. Fenugreek contains potent antioxidants that have beneficial effects on the liver and pancreas, making it useful in the treatment of diabetes, high cholesterol, and digestive disorders [3, 4]. The hard, brown, red and yellow seeds are the part used medicinally and in cooking. Traditional uses included bronchial problems, tuberculosis, gout, general body pain, swollen glands, skin problems and low libido.

2. Materials and methods

The artichoke dried leaves were produced by the TTDR 2000 Ltd., Hungary. 10 g of sample was extracted for 5 min with 200 ml of boiling distilled water (Aqueous Artichoke extract, AqA). It was allowed to cool to room temperature (RT), filtered and stored in refrigerator. Another 50 g of dried artichoke leaves were extracted twice with 500 ml aqueous 50% ethanol solution by stirring for 4 hrs on a magnetic stirrer (Alcoholic Artichoke extract, AIA). This extract was filtered, evaporated under vacuum and stored in refrigerator

The fenugreek seeds were produced by TRIGONELLA MED. LTD., Mosonmagyaróvár, Hungary. Fenugreek seeds were dried at 40 °C and powdered. 15 g of the powder was extracted with 300 ml of boiling distilled water for 5 min. The mixture was allowed to cool at RT, filtered and stored in refrigerator (Aqueous Fenugreek extract, AqF). Other 15 g of powdered fenugreek seeds were refluxed on a magnetic stirrer with 300 ml aqueous 80% ethanol for 3 hrs (Alcoholic Fenugreek extract, AIF). The mixture was filtered and the filtrate was concentrated by rotary evaporator and stored in refrigerator.

2.1. Determination of antioxidant capacity by the DPPH method

The DPPH (2,2- Diphenyl-1-picrylhydrazyl, Sigma-Aldrich) method was used to determine the antioxidant capacity of artichoke and fenugreek extracts. The method is based on the scavenging of DPPH radical through the action of an antioxidant that decolourizes the DPPH solution. The procedure was described by

Molyneux (2004) [5]. 200 μ l of extract were added to 300 μ l of methanol and 2400 μ l DPPH solution (22.6 μ g/ml). The mixture was left to stand at room temperature for 30 minutes in the dark and filtered (0.45 μ m) before the absorbance was measured at 517 nm. (UV/VIS Spectrometer, Perkin Elmer Lambda 35). All the measurements were performed in triplicate. The results were expressed as ascorbic acid equivalents by means of the dose-response calibration curve. The sample concentration providing 50 % inhibition (IC₅₀) was calculated from the graph of inhibition percentage against sample concentration. Each extract was measured in triplicate.

2.2. Quantification of total flavonoids

The total flavonoid content of the extract was determined by the aluminium chloride colorimetric method following the procedure described by Dae-Ok Kim et al. (2003) [6]. We have made a reagent solution containing 5 ml (10g/ml) of aluminium chloride, 5 ml of KOAc (potassium acetate, 1M/l), 75 ml of methanol and 140 ml of distilled water (AS). 0.5 ml of the extract was mixed with 4.5 ml of AS, filtered (0.45 μ m) and the absorbance was determined at 415 nm in the spectrophotometer (Perkin Elmer Lambda 35). The concentrations were calculated based on the equation obtained from the standard rutin curve (10, 40, 70, 100 μ g/ml). Results were expressed as mg rutin equivalents. Each extract was measured in triplicate.

2.3. Determination of total phenolic content

Total phenolic content was determined using the method developed by Singleton and Rossi (1965) [7]. Total phenolic content was estimated by the Folin-Ciocalteu colorimetric method, using gallic acid as a standard phenolic compound. 200 μ l of extracts were added to 3000 μ l of distilled water, 500 μ l of Folin-Ciocalteu reagent and 2000 μ l of sodium carbonate solution (15g/100ml), and the mixture was allowed to stand for 20 min at RT. 4300 μ l of distilled water was added and the absorbance was measured at 765 nm after 1 hour incubation period with the spectrophotometer (Perkin Elmer Lambda 35). The total flavonoid contents were calculated from a calibration curve with 50, 100, 300, 500, 750 μ g/ml points and the results were expressed as mg gallic acid equivalent per g dry weight. Each extract was measured in triplicate.

2.4. Determination of total anthocyanins

The total anthocyanin (TA) content was determined using an earlier described method (Lee et al., 2005) [8]. It detects the total monomeric anthocyanin concentration by the pH differential method. The method is a rapid and simple

spectrophotometric application based on the anthocyanin structural transformation that occurs upon a change in pH (colored at pH 1.0 and colorless at pH 4.5). The standard solution was prepared by weighing 82.2 mg of cyanidin-3-glucoside chloride, dissolving in distilled water and diluting to a final volume of 1 L in a volumetric flask. 0.3 ml of extract was added to 2 ml of buffer (pH=1 or pH=4.5) and 1.7 ml of distilled water. Samples were filtered (0.45 μ m), and absorbance recorded using a Perkin Elmer Lambda 35 spectrophotometer at wavelengths of 520 and 700 nm, for solutions at pH 1.0 and pH 4.5, respectively. Results were expressed as cyanidin-3-glucoside (% w/w) equivalents. Total anthocyanin contents were calculated as follows:

$$TA_{(mg/L)} = \left(\frac{A * MW * DF * 10^3}{\epsilon} \right) \div l \quad (2)$$

where A = (A_{520nm} - A_{700nm})pH 1.0 - (A_{520nm} - A_{700nm})pH 4.5; MW (molecular weight) = 449.2 g/mol for cyanidin-3-glucoside; DF = dilution factor; l = path length in cm; ϵ = 26 900 molar extinction coefficient, in L* mol⁻¹ * cm⁻¹, for cyd-3-glu; and 10³ = factor for conversion from g to mg. Each extract was measured in triplicate.

3. Results and discussions

The artichoke and fenugreek are considered to have important health promoting effects, and many of such claims were related to their antioxidant properties that seemed to be correlated with the total flavonoid, total phenolic and anthocyanin content. Therefore we proposed to analyze the artichoke and fenugreek antioxidant activity, total flavonoid, total phenolic and anthocyanin contents. All the experiments were carried out as we described in Materials and methods, and the obtained results are presented in Table 1 and Figure 1.

Table 1) Means and standard error of antioxidant capacity, flavonoid-, phenolic- and anthocyanin content of artichoke and fenugreek extracts (n=3)

Spectrophotometric methods	Aqueous artichoke (AqA)	Alcoholic artichoke (AlA)	Aqueous fenugreek (AqF)	Alcoholic fenugreek (AlF)
Average antioxidant capacity (μ l/ml)	23.43 \pm 0.25	1.80 \pm 0.16	29.83 \pm 0.41	5.91 \pm 0.18
Average total flavonoid content (mg/ml)	5.830 \pm 0.31	16.087 \pm 0.39	2.827 \pm 0.22	32.267 \pm 0.61
Average total phenolic content (mg/g)	5.99 \pm 0.36	12.31 \pm 0.34	1.01 \pm 0.15	1.48 \pm 0.12
Average total anthocyanin content (mg/l)	0	0	0	0

From the obtained data we can conclude that the aqueous artichoke and fenugreek extracts antioxidant capacities were relatively high, while the alcoholic artichoke and fenugreek extracts antioxidant capacities were markedly reduced as compared to their corresponding aqueous counterparts. The aqueous extract compared to the alcoholic extract showed an approximately 16 times greater antioxidant capacity in case of artichoke. In case of fenugreek the aqueous extract showed a 5 time greater antioxidant capacity than the alcoholic extract.

The total flavonoid content of artichoke and fenugreek alcoholic extracts exceeded substantially the flavonoid content seen in both plants derived aqueous extracts. Accordingly, the artichoke specific alcoholic extract total flavonoid content appears 3 times greater as compared to the aqueous extract. The fenugreek total flavonoid content of the alcoholic extracts looks almost 12 times greater than the aqueous extract related values. Moreover, if the two plants specific alcoholic extracts are compared, it looks obvious that the fenugreek values are two times greater than the artichoke values for total flavonoid content suggesting that the fenugreek seeds contain twice as much flavonoid than the artichoke. Surprisingly, when the aqueous extracts of artichoke and fenugreek are compared, the artichoke extract specific total flavonoid content was approximately double to that seen in case of fenugreek extract.

The total phenolic content of artichoke alcoholic extract exceeded more than 2 times the values observed for the artichoke aqueous extract suggesting that the alcoholic artichoke extract contains twice as many phenolic compounds like the aqueous artichoke extract. However, the aqueous and alcoholic fenugreek extracts seemed to contain similar amount of phenolic compounds.

Surprisingly we were unable to detect anthocyanin in any of our artichoke and fenugreek extracts.

Conclusions

- (1). The aqueous artichoke and fenugreek extracts antioxidant capacities are almost the same, and the corresponding alcoholic extracts are showing low values suggesting that the alcoholic extracts antioxidant capacities are greatly reduced.
- (2). The total phenolic content of alcoholic artichoke and fenugreek extracts was much greater than in case of the corresponding aqueous extracts,
- (3). It seems that anthocyanin type of flavonoids are not present in artichoke leaves and fenugreek seeds.
- (4). In case of artichoke leaf or fenugreek seed extracts, the total flavonoid and total phenolic contents, presumably, have very little if any involvement in the antioxidant capacities of artichoke and fenugreek, respectively.
- (5). Both artichoke leaves and fenugreek seeds should have antioxidants other than those that were assessed. It remains to get identified the antioxidant properties ensuring compounds in the case of alcoholic extracts.

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REFERENCES

- [1] K. Kraft, *Phytomedicine* **4**, 369 (1997).
- [2] R. Mabey, *The New Age Herbalist* (Simon & Schuster, New York, 1988).
- [3] J. A. Duke, *The Green Pharmacy* (Rodale Press Emmaus, Pennsylvania, 1997).
- [4] J. Barnes and L. A. Anderson, *Herbal Medicines* (Pharmaceutical Press, London, 2007).
- [5] P. Molyneux, *Songklanakarin J. Sci. and Technol.* **26**, 211 (2004).
- [6] D. O. Kim et al., *J. Agric. Food Chem.* **51**, 6509 (2003).
- [7] V.L. Singleton and J.A. Rossi, *Amer. J. Enol Viticult.* **16**, 144 (1965).
- [8] J. Lee et al., *J. AOAC Int.* **88**, 1269 (2005).